

Risk, Removal, and
Remediation of
Psychopharmaceuticals in the
Aquatic Environment

Charlie J. E. Davey

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Preface – The Octopus Story

In 2018, a study by Edsinger and Dölen generated global headlines for its unorthodox premise of administering the illicit drug 3,4-Methylenedioxymethamphetamine (MDMA) to two octopuses. One octopus could move freely around the environment, while the other was stuck in a cage (Figure 1). Octopuses are solitary animals and normally would not interact with each other, and in this experiment the free octopus would usually prefer to interact with an object in another room rather than the caged octopus. However, after exposure to MDMA, the active ingredient of ecstasy, the octopuses displayed highly pro-social behaviour by becoming interested in one another, interacting, and even touching each other through the bars of the cage (Figure 2). These pro-social effects are strikingly similar to the effects of MDMA in humans.

Figure 1: Schematic of the experiment by Edsinger & Dölen (2018). The free octopus could choose either to be in the room with an object in a cage or in a room with the caged octopus. The free octopus preferred to interact with the object normally, but much preferred to be in the room with the caged octopus after the administration of MDMA. Adapted from Figure 4 of Edsinger & Dölen (2018) with permission from Elsevier under open access licence CC-BY.

Figure 2: Images of the experiment by Edsinger & Dölen (2018). The free octopus would spend most of its time away from the other octopus in the cage but would sometimes investigate before going back to the other room (left panel). After the administration of MDMA, both octopuses would interact and touch each other through the bars, displaying highly unusual social behaviour for this type of animal (right panel). Adapted from Figure 4 of Edsinger & Dölen (2018) with permission from Elsevier under open access licence CC-BY.

The role of MDMA in this study was to trigger a release of a large amount of neurotransmitters in the brains of the octopuses, specifically serotonin. However, the media coverage did not emphasise the main findings of the study, which was that serotonergic neurotransmission plays a conserved role in mediating social behaviour in octopuses. In other words, serotonin's influence on social behaviour is not only limited to vertebrates, but also extends to invertebrates like octopuses. Since humans and octopuses diverged evolutionarily eons ago, Edsinger & Dölen (2018) provided evidence that the neurotransmission mechanism is evolutionarily highly conserved, which supports the premise that the role of serotonin in social behaviour is ancient and conserved across species.

This study has been used as an anecdote, especially to pique the interest of students, demonstrating that chemicals that produce neurological effects in humans can produce the same or similar effects in non-target organisms because of the shared neurological architecture (Edsinger and Dölen, 2018a; Liebeskind et al., 2017a). This is the most fundamental motivation to study the environmental impact of psychopharmaceuticals

Chapter One – Introduction

The Dawn of Psychopharmaceuticals

Before the advent of modern psychopharmacology, the treatment of psychological disorders was largely non-specific and often ineffective. In the 19th and early 20th centuries, treatments such as morphine, potassium bromide, and barbiturates were used primarily for sedation rather than addressing the underlying pathology of mental illnesses (Ban, 2001). These early interventions were often crude and lacked a scientific basis, reflecting the limited understanding of brain function and neurotransmission at the time. In contrast, the psychodynamic and psychoanalytic approaches dominated psychiatric practice in the early 20th century. These approaches focused on psychological rather than biological mechanisms, and pharmacological treatments were not a central part of psychiatric care (Baldessarini, 2014).

This began to change in the 1950s, with the development of new psychopharmacological treatments, starting with Lithium, which was the first medication specifically approved for the treatment of mania to achieve mood stabilisation, providing a targeted intervention for a condition that was previously managed with non-specific sedatives (Baldessarini, 2014; López-Muñoz et al., 2018). Over the following years more treatments for more illnesses started to appear. Chlorpromazine and other antipsychotics (Ban, 2007), Monoamine Oxidase Inhibitors (MAOIs), Tricyclic Antidepressants (Lopez-Munoz and Alamo, 2009; Pereira and Hiroaki-Sato, 2018), and benzodiazepines for anxiety disorders (Baldessarini, 2014) all emerged during the 1950s and 1960s. In the 1980s, modern psychopharmaceuticals began to emerge, with Selective Serotonin Reuptake Inhibitor (SSRI) antidepressants being developed, which became the most prescribed group of psychopharmaceuticals on the market (Bogowicz et al., 2021; Lopez-Munoz and Alamo, 2009; Pereira and Hiroaki-Sato, 2018).

To date, 156 psychopharmaceuticals have been approved for the European market, representing around 14% of all approved pharmaceuticals (Figure 3, EMA, 2025). In 2023 in the Netherlands, 1.5 million people were prescribed psychoanaleptics (psychostimulants), corresponding to almost 8% of the population. The majority of these prescriptions were antidepressants (Zorginstituut Nederland, 2022). In Iceland,

antidepressants are being used by almost 16% of the population, the highest percentage among the OECD countries (OECD, 2023). The current number of market approvals and prescriptions shows that psychopharmaceuticals have become an integral part of the medicinal arsenal across the globe.

Figure 3: Cumulative number of authorised pharmaceuticals (green) and psychopharmaceuticals (blue) available on the EU market by year. Data from the European Medicines Agency (EMA, 2025).

After the advent of SSRIs in the 1990s, scientific literature discussing the occurrence of psychopharmaceuticals in the environment started to appear, and the effects of psychopharmaceuticals on the environment began to be studied (Daughton and Ternes, 1999; Halling-Sørensen et al., 1998). Yet, despite this increasing scientific awareness there was still limited attention for these compounds by regulatory agencies, as (psycho)pharmaceuticals¹ were not typically considered as environmental pollutants at the time. Moreover, available chemical analyses up to this period were more limited in scope, leading to only a trickle of new psychopharmaceutical occurrence data. It was only since the turn of the millennium that there has been an increase in research into the occurrence and effects of (psycho)pharmaceuticals in the environment (Boxall et al., 2012; Boxall and Brooks, 2024; OECD, 2019a; Wilkinson et al., 2022). These advances subsequently led to the first environmental hazard and risk assessments being advised

¹The term (psycho)pharmaceuticals refers to pharmaceuticals in general, but naturally includes psychopharmaceuticals, while the term psychopharmaceuticals refers solely to the psychoactive pharmaceuticals.

(OECD, 2019a), and subsequently mandated by the EU in 2006 before a novel (psycho)pharmaceutical could get market approval (Spindler et al., 2007).

Hence, psychopharmaceuticals experienced a dramatic turnaround in only a few decades, since they only came on the market during the second half of the 20th century, discussions on the occurrence starting in the 1990s, and legislation on the hazards and risks came into force by the mid-2000s. However, much of the research efforts over these last years have been directed to pharmaceuticals in general, and not to psychopharmaceuticals specifically. This begs the question to what extent the (eco)toxicological effects of psychopharmaceuticals differ from other pharmaceuticals from an environmental risk assessment perspective.

Psychopharmaceuticals are a Unique Class of Environmental Contaminants

The primary difference between the environmental effects of psychopharmaceuticals and other pharmaceuticals is due to the different modes of action of neuroactive drugs. Psychopharmaceuticals interact with the nervous and neurological systems of the body and have been placed in the Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical (ATC) class of N (Nervous system) by the World Health Organisation (WHO, 2018). While the effects they cause in the environment can be diverse, they notably alter behaviour, such as in the case of the octopuses in the preface. Examples of behavioural changes include changes in feeding, social interactions, swimming behaviour, locomotion, and predator avoidance (Brodin et al., 2014a; Cervený et al., 2020a; Painter et al., 2009a; Raman et al., 2024a; Schultz et al., 2011a; Valenti et al., 2012a; Versteegen et al., 2025b).

While many studies have shown adverse effects of psychopharmaceuticals on non-target organisms at laboratory and mesocosm scales (Cunha et al., 2019a; Raman et al., 2024a; Schuijt et al., 2023; Sehonova et al., 2019, 2018; Versteegen et al., 2025b, 2025c, 2025a), there are only a few that demonstrated their effects in nature. This is because field studies on the adverse behavioural effects of psychopharmaceuticals specifically are difficult because

behavioural effects are more subtle than non-behavioural effects. Moreover, the presence of complex mixtures of (psycho)pharmaceuticals and other pollutants makes it difficult to unravel the contribution of individual compounds to the observed effects. Nonetheless, laboratory studies indicated that effects may occur at environmentally relevant concentrations (Cunha et al., 2019a, 2017a; Kubec et al., 2019; Parrott and Metcalfe, 2017; Sehonova et al., 2019, 2018).

Aside from the unique mode of action, the physical behaviour of psychopharmaceuticals in the environment also differs from other pharmaceuticals. Psychopharmaceuticals and their metabolites and other transformation products generally enter the aquatic environment through wastewater discharges due to insufficient removal by the Wastewater Treatment Plants (WWTPs, Figure 4). The reason for the insufficient removal can vary from compound to compound, but physicochemical properties can naturally help to explain why many psychopharmaceuticals are difficult to remove. For example, since psychopharmaceuticals are often designed for chronic use due to the types of conditions they treat (e.g. depression), they tend to have long metabolic half-lives, tending to range from days (e.g. carbamazepine) to weeks (e.g. fluoxetine) opposed to common pharmaceuticals such as diclofenac (2h), penicillin (0.9h), or aspirin (4h) (Wishart et al, 2018). These longer metabolic half-lives explain the broadly lower biodegradability of psychopharmaceuticals in WWTPs. The WWTP degradation rates of gabapentin, oxazepam, and carbamazepine are among the slowest reported in the WATSON database of Dutch WWTPs. Gabapentin has even a slower degradation rate than perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA), a notoriously persistent compound (See SI in Nolte et al., 2020; RIVM, 2023).

Figure 4: Diagram illustrating the different routes by which (psycho)pharmaceuticals can enter both the aquatic and terrestrial environment. Diagram adapted from the OECD “Pharmaceutical residues in freshwater: Hazards and policy responses” report (OECD, 2019a).

Wastewater Treatment

Currently, up to 60–70% of the consumed (psycho)pharmaceuticals, illicit drugs, and their respective transformation products are not removed by WWTPs and end up in surface waters (OECD, 2019a; Zhou et al., 2009). This limited removal, leading to their presence in the environment, coupled with the unique and often more subtle ecotoxicological mode of action at relatively low concentrations (e.g. ng/L) may lead to risks to the aquatic environment (Painter et al., 2009a; Schultz et al., 2011a).

Many modern WWTPs rely on sorption and biodegradation to remove micropollutants such as psychopharmaceuticals. Conventional Activated Sludge (CAS) systems, for example, perform a sequence of primary sedimentation → aeration → secondary sedimentation. Micropollutants can adsorb to particulate matter, such as sludge, in either sedimentation steps, or be transformed by microorganisms in the sludge during the aeration step, to then be adsorbed in the secondary sedimentation. Sludge from the secondary sedimentation step is recirculated back into the aeration step to introduce acclimatised biota to the biodegradation step, enhancing the biodegradation potential (Deegan et al., 2011). More up to date WWTPs still use the same principles as CAS, such as the University of Cape Town (UCT) setup, which splits the aeration step into an anaerobic → anoxic → aerobic sequenced treatment via the use of separated tanks (van Nieuwenhuijzen et al., 2009), or the carousel layout which uses a long ditch with aerators to create conditions similar to a UCT setup. These setups with split aeration processes are specifically designed to remove nitrogen and phosphorus (Deegan et al., 2011; van Nieuwenhuijzen et al., 2009) and not specifically designed for micropollutant removal, which is why large amounts psychopharmaceuticals may pass through WWTPs unchanged and enter the aquatic environment.

In response to poor micropollutant removal, many countries intend to upgrade their WWTPs using so-called advanced treatments. The EU's revised urban wastewater treatment directive (UWWTD, European Commission, 2024) mandates that from 2025 WWTPs connected to populations of more than 100,000 must include advanced treatment

technologies (Pistocchi et al., 2022a). Advanced treatments include advanced oxidations, such as ozone treatment, UV/peroxide treatment, or can include more adsorption-based treatments, such as Granulated or Powdered Active Carbon (GAC & PAC) and sand filtration. Nations such as Switzerland and federal states within Germany have already started to implement advanced treatments, while the Netherlands and the rest of the EU are planning to follow suit in the coming decades (Bourgin et al., 2018a; DVGW and DWA, 2023; European Commission, 2024a; Gretzschel et al., 2020; STOWA, 2024).

Part of the ongoing discussion on advanced treatment technologies is the associated capital, energy demand, and CO₂ emissions associated with the deployment and operation of those technologies. Additionally, there are many countries and regions where wastewater treatment is not an economic priority, and even some areas of EU countries lack even a basic CAS-level setup (van Dijk et al., 2023). In response to these challenges, “nature-based” or “bio-based” solutions to wastewater treatment have been proposed. These treatments involve the utilisation of natural systems to polish WWTP effluent by harnessing the inherent capabilities of plants, animals, microbes, and natural materials to remove contaminants. Furthermore, abiotic processes such as photodegradation, hydrolysis, or adsorption to natural matter can lead to further removal of contaminants. Aside from the often lower operating costs of these systems, some setups also have the added benefit of promoting biodiversity, such as constructed wetlands (Cross et al., 2021; Vassalle et al., 2023; Verlicchi and Zambello, 2014).

Conventional treatments such as CAS and UCT, advanced treatments such as ozone and GAC, and nature-based solutions all have advantages and disadvantages, and are often designed for different scenarios or to remove different substances from the water. There is no ‘one size fits all’ solution to remove all different chemicals present in the influent. This makes it important to accurately qualify and quantify the efficiencies of these widely varying removal techniques in order to compare them in the context of psychopharmaceutical removal.

Risk, Removal, and Risk-Based Removal

In the context of (psycho)pharmaceutical pollution, the terms risk and removal are used extensively, and the present thesis combines these metrics into a novel concept called risk-based removal. To understand risk-based removal, first the concepts of **risk** and **removal** need to be clearly defined:

Environmental risk in the context of chemical pollution is defined as the ratio between the concentration of a pollutant in the environment and the concentration at which that pollutant is expected to exceed an ecotoxic threshold (Righthand side, Figure 5). Often, the ecotoxic threshold value is a Predicted No Effect Concentration (PNEC), which is generally used in deriving environmental quality standards. When sufficient ecotoxicity data are available, the ecotoxic threshold may also be derived from a Species Sensitivity Distribution (SSD, Posthuma et al., 2002). A risk can be expected if either the concentration is too high, or the ecotoxic threshold is very low, or a combination of these two. Based on the ratio between the environmental concentration and the ecotoxic threshold, a Risk Quotient (RQ) is calculated, where an $RQ > 1$ is considered to be a potential risk. However, the risk equation can also be used outside of regulatory contexts as a more qualitative tool to assess and compare different pollutants, as proposed in this thesis.

Removal, or removal efficiency in a WWTP context is simply a comparison of the concentration of a pollutant entering and leaving the WWTP, often expressed as a percentage of the influent concentration (Lefthand side, Figure 5). The removal percentage indicates how well or how poorly a WWTP or specific treatment technology is performing for a specific pollutant, or reversely, how easy or difficult it is to remove a pollutant from the wastewater. Flat percentage-based removal targets for selected micropollutants have to-date been the norm in many countries (Bourgin et al., 2018; STOWA, 2020; Svahn and Borg, 2024). However, the UWWTD proposes progressively more rigorous measures over time for WWTPs that are connected to larger populations, which currently still need to meet an 80% flat removal target (European Commission, 2024).

An environmental risk can be due to a low removal efficiency, high prescription and use, high inherent toxicity, or a combination thereof, as well as other factors like low dilution upon entering the environment. As such, percentile removal efficiency is not indicative of risk reduction, as the remaining concentration in the water may still pose a risk to the aquatic environment. This leaves flat percentile removal targets as redundant in the context of reducing environmental risk. The current thesis uses risk in tandem with removal in multiple chapters to contextualise risk, but furthermore, introduces risk-based removal as a novel concept which combines both risk and removal to better evaluate the potential of a treatment technology to reduce environmental risks. By replacing concentration with a sum of risk quotients (RQs) in the standard removal efficiency equation, risk-based removal can be calculated (Centre, Figure 5).

Figure 5: Graphic showing how the risk and removal equations are combined into the risk-based removal equation. Where C_{Pre} is the pre-treatment concentration, C_{Post} is the post-treatment concentration, Removal % is the concentration-based removal expressed as a percentage, C is the concentration (both pre and post treatment), $PNEC$ is the predicted no effect concentration and RQ is the Risk Quotient.

Risk-based removal allows for a comparison of treatment technologies in terms of environmental risk, however it requires a lot of data since it is calculated based the sum of the RQs, since the removal percentage would be identical to the concentration-based removal if done on a compound by-compound basis. Still, since around 66% of (psycho)pharmaceuticals demonstrate additive mixture effects (Kidd et al., 2024a; Martin et al., 2021), the method of summing RQs for (psycho)pharmaceuticals has been argued for to bridge knowledge gaps (Backhaus, 2016). The UWWTD leaves room for a 'risk-based approach' to determine if advanced treatment is needed for smaller WWTPs in certain circumstances. For example, if an effluent outlet leads to a sensitive ecosystem, or if there is the possibility of affecting

sources for drinking water, or outflow into a system with low dilution. Discussions regarding removal targets are ongoing outside the UWWTD, where risk-based removal targets are considered to be a viable option (European Commission, 2024), especially when compared to flat, concentration-based removal targets (Bourgin et al., 2018; Eggen et al., 2014; STOWA, 2020; Svahn and Borg, 2024).

Knowledge Gaps and Aims

With an ever-increasing population using psychopharmaceuticals, accompanied by an increased awareness of mental illness, the concentrations of these compounds in the aquatic environment are foreseen to further increase. Hence, further intervention is needed, and the challenge of psychopharmaceutical removal is being increasingly addressed. Yet, key knowledge gaps for this very relevant and understudied group of emerging contaminants remain.

Prior to the beginning of this project, a comprehensive risk assessment of the presence of psychopharmaceuticals had not been performed. Cunha et al. (2019) performed a risk assessment of 7 psychopharmaceuticals, 6 of which were benzodiazepines. The risk assessment itself only used two PNECs derived from measured ecotoxicity data, and Cunha et al. (2019) lamented the lack of data for the selected compounds, with the title of his general discussion being “*Uncertainties, limitations, and recommendations*”. Cunha et al. (2019) acknowledged large data and knowledge gaps which hamper proper risk assessment for many (psycho)pharmaceuticals. Specifically, the availability of occurrence and ecotoxicity data remained very limited.

Moreover, many psychopharmaceuticals are not included in WWTP monitoring lists (RIVM, 2023), so the removal efficiencies for both conventional and advanced treatments, such as those laid out in the UWWTD, may also remain unknown. These missing data are further compounded by a lack of standardised testing of the micropollutant removal efficiencies of advanced treatments, making comparisons between different treatments challenging (Fischer et al., 2019a)her et al., 2019a). Removal studies tend to offer removal rates without discussion or assessment of the effects

on the environment and implicitly assume a high removal rate equals a low environmental risk. This may not be the case, but it would require the use of risk-based removal to properly assess this.

Therefore, the present thesis aimed to assess the risk, removal, and remediation of psychopharmaceuticals in the aquatic environment. To this end, five objectives to remedy the current knowledge gaps were pursued:

1. To identify psychopharmaceuticals that represent a high risk for the aquatic environment
2. To define for which psychopharmaceuticals missing occurrence and ecotoxicity data hamper environmental risk assessment
3. To determine occurrence, mass-based, and risk-based removal of psychopharmaceuticals in a modern conventional WWTP
4. To determine occurrence, mass-based and risk-based removal of psychopharmaceuticals by common advanced treatment techniques
5. To assess the effectiveness of an alternative nature-based treatment technique for risk-based removal of psychopharmaceuticals

Outline of the Thesis

Figure 6: Overview of the empirical chapters of the present thesis.

Based on the conclusions from Cunha et al. (2016), it was clear that a more comprehensive risk assessment needed to be performed. This was the primary aim of Chapter 2 (Figure 6), which deemed to take a wide definition of psychopharmaceuticals to include all ATC-N pharmaceuticals, as well as neuroactive illicit drugs.

To address the first objective, a risk assessment was performed for all compounds for which enough data was available. The risk assessment carried out in Chapter 2 was designed to prioritise and give context to psychopharmaceuticals in the environment, also taking prescription volumes into account, and to act as a new baseline for future studies. In response to the second objective, Chapter 2 also addressed data scarcity by scoring psychopharmaceuticals on their data availability and quality, concerning both occurrence and ecotoxicity data. It also analysed psychopharmaceuticals by therapeutic group, to see if there might be 'hidden risks' of under/unstudied compounds that pose a risk to the environment that we simply are unaware of.

Based on the prioritisations of Chapter 2, new data needed to be generated for highly prescribed, high risk, and understudied psychopharmaceuticals. These new data needed to include concentrations in the wastewater effluent, along with new WWTP removal efficiency data. With the advent of new treatment technologies on the horizon, and with increasing implementation, a baseline for conventional wastewater treatment needed to be established first. To this

end, Chapter 3 addressed the third objective by assessing the occurrence, removal, and risks of psychopharmaceuticals in a conventional wastewater treatment plant. This chapter aimed to generate new data, as well as to progress the discussion on risk-based removal, which merits a removal technology based on risk-reduction, rather than simply on reducing concentrations.

Chapter 4 addressed the fourth objective of this thesis by evaluating two advanced treatments: ozone and GAC, employing concentration-based and risk-based removal. These treatments were chosen to represent two commonly employed advanced treatment techniques covering an oxidative and adsorption-based technique. The two treatments were compared directly, while models were deployed to assess a worst-case scenario for the ozone treatment in the event that toxic by-products were produced.

Finally, in the same vein as Chapter 4, Chapter 5 aimed to assess the concentration-based and risk-based removal of psychopharmaceuticals in a potential biobased solution that utilised an algal-mussel cascade, thus addressing the final objective. By utilising the natural adsorption capacity of algae, and then using mussels to filter the algae, and therewith psychopharmaceuticals, a potential low-cost, low energy, low-tech alternative to advanced treatments such as ozone or GAC was evaluated.

By addressing the five objectives, the present thesis aimed to provide a broad and holistic view of the challenges associated with the presence of psychopharmaceuticals in the aquatic environment, focusing not only on the occurrence, but also on their removal and the risks involved. Simultaneously, the thesis focused on end-of-pipe solutions to this problem. The thesis ends with a synthesis in Chapter 6, in which the main findings of the previous chapters are discussed, conclusions are drawn, and the future outlook for remediating psychopharmaceutical pollution is laid out.

Chapter Two - Occurrence, Hazard, and Risk of Psychopharmaceuticals and Illicit Drugs in European Surface Waters

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Abstract

This study aimed to provide insights into the risk posed by psychopharmaceuticals and illicit drugs in European surface waters, and to identify current knowledge gaps hampering this risk assessment. First, the availability and quality of data on the concentrations of psychopharmaceuticals and illicit drugs in surface waters (*occurrence*) and on the toxicity to aquatic organisms (*hazard*) were reviewed. If both occurrence and ecotoxicity data were available, risk quotients (*risk*) were calculated. Where abundant ecotoxicity data were available, a species sensitivity distribution (*SSD*) was constructed, from which the hazardous concentration for 5% of the species (*HC₅*) was derived, allowing to derive integrated multi-species risks.

A total of 702 compounds were categorised as psychopharmaceuticals and illicit drugs based on a combination of all 502 anatomical therapeutic class (*ATC*) 'N' pharmaceuticals and a list of illicit drugs according to the Dutch Opium Act. Of these, 343 (49%) returned occurrence data, while only 105 (15%) returned ecotoxicity data. Moreover, many ecotoxicity tests used irrelevant endpoints for neurologically active compounds, such as mortality, which may underestimate the hazard of psychopharmaceuticals. Due to data limitations, risks could only be assessed for 87 (12%) compounds, with 23 (3.3%) compounds indicating a potential risk, and several highly prescribed drugs returned neither occurrence nor ecotoxicity data. Primary bottlenecks in risk calculation included the lack of ecotoxicity data, a lack of diversity of test species and ecotoxicological end points, and large disparities between well studied and understudied compounds for both occurrence and toxicity data. This study identified which compounds merit concern, as well as the many compounds that lack the data for any calculation of risk, driving research priorities. Despite the large knowledge gaps, we concluded that the presence of a substantial part (26%) of data-rich psychopharmaceuticals in surface waters present an ecological risk for aquatic non-target organisms.

1: Introduction

Psychoactive pharmaceuticals, also known as psychopharmaceuticals, are a class of pharmaceuticals primarily used to treat mental disorders and illnesses, as well as other conditions relating to the nervous system, such as analgesics (painkillers) and anaesthetics. These psychopharmaceuticals are vital for our modern society, and their use has been steeply increasing around the world due to a multitude of factors, such as growing number of psychopharmaceutical-based treatments, growing global access to psychopharmaceuticals, growing global population, an ageing population in several regions, loss of social stigma, and increased availability of mental health treatment (European Medicines Agency, 2021; Gao et al., 2013; Massey et al., 2018; Read et al., 2014; World Health Organization, 2011).

Psychopharmaceuticals often alter the neurochemistry of the brain, by changing the concentrations and uptake of neurotransmitters such as serotonin and dopamine and/or by agonising or antagonising specific receptors (Jóźwiak-Bebenista and Nowak, 2014; Wrobel, 2007). However, their activity is not limited to the brain, such as in the case of analgesics which work on the nervous system (Ghanem et al., 2016; Graham and Scott, 2005; Jóźwiak-Bebenista and Nowak, 2014). In 1976, the WHO created The Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical (ATC) classification system, a systematic approach to classify pharmaceuticals into therapeutic groupings based on the organ or biological system on which they act, as well as on their pharmacological and chemical properties, otherwise known as the Mechanism of Action (MOA). The ATC system distinguishes 14 categories in which psychopharmaceuticals are classified, with ATC-N standing for nervous system (WHO Collaborating Centre for Drug Statistics Methodology, 2018). Of the over 4000 pharmaceuticals administered worldwide, 502 belong to the ATC-N class (Wishart et al., 2018). In addition to psychopharmaceuticals, illicit drugs such as stimulants, dissociatives, hallucinogenics, illicit opioids and cannabinoids can have strong effects on the nervous system as well, having a similar MOA as psychopharmaceuticals. Yet, studies on illicit drugs tend to consider these in isolation (e.g. Deng et al., 2020; Huizer et al., 2021; Li et al., 2016; Thomas et al., 2012),

even though some illicit compounds are screened as candidates for therapeutic uses (e.g. ketamine, cannabis, MDMA, Aan Het Rot et al., 2012; Ebbert et al., 2018; Krystal et al., 2019; Mathew et al., 2008; Sessa, 2017). Hence, it makes sense to jointly assess the presence, hazard, and risks of psychopharmaceuticals and illicit drugs in the aquatic environment.

Increased use has led to the widespread occurrence of psychopharmaceuticals and their transformation products in the aquatic environment (aus der Beek et al., 2016). Pharmaceuticals have been reported in the aquatic environment since the 1960s (Stumm-Zollinger and Fair, 1965), but specific concern for psychopharmaceuticals was only raised in the late 1990s (Daughton and Ternes, 1999; Halling-Sørensen et al., 1998). Consequently, there has been a significant increase in the amount of data on the occurrence of psychopharmaceuticals and their transformation products in surface waters, attributed also to advancements in analytical techniques such as LC-HRMS (Heberer, 2002; Luo et al., 2014; Ort et al., 2014; Richardson, 2007), which can detect pharmaceuticals in the ng to pg/l range (e.g. Zrnčić et al., 2014).

Wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) are a major source of psychopharmaceutical and illicit drug residues entering the environment, to such a point that wastewater has become a frequently studied medium to reveal drug use trends in the connected populations (Deng et al., 2020; Huizer et al., 2021; Ort et al., 2014; ter Laak et al., 2010; van Nuijs et al., 2011). Currently, up to 60-70% of the consumed pharmaceuticals, illicit drugs and the respective transformation products are not removed by WWTPs and end up in surface waters, depending on the physicochemical properties of the compounds and the setup of the WWTP. Once in the aquatic environment, the fate and persistence of psychopharmaceuticals can vary considerably between the different compounds, with some degrading very quickly, which are therefore not being detected in the environment, while some others have reported half-lives ($t_{1/2}$) that can exceed one year. For example, carbamazepine has a $t_{1/2}$ of 2400-10,000 h, while paracetamol has a $t_{1/2}$ of 40-350 h (Andreozzi et al., 2003; Yamamoto et al., 2009; Zou et al., 2015). This is, however, an understudied field (Bu et al., 2016), emphasising

the need to further study the fate of (psycho)pharmaceuticals in the aquatic environment.

Whether or not the presence of psychopharmaceuticals and illicit drugs in the aquatic environment leads to adverse effects on non-target species typically depends on their sensitivity to these compounds. Since the neural and nervous architecture of humans is shared across many different organisms that deviated in evolutionarily terms eons ago (Edsinger and Dölen, 2018; Weiger, 1997), psychopharmaceuticals and illicit drugs designed to interact with the human nervous system may also successfully interact with the nervous system of non-target organisms, with potential negative ecological impacts (Claessens et al., 2013; Schwarz et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2021). For example, antidepressants can affect predatory behaviour in bass, impacts tissue metabolic capacities, and may compromise the adaptive responses in trout when accumulated through gills or through the food chain (Best et al., 2014; Bisesi et al., 2016, 2014). Adverse effects of illicit drugs have also been observed, but are considerably less studied than the effects of conventional pharmaceuticals (Mohan et al., 2021). Outside the aquatic environment, acute effects of psychopharmaceuticals such as changes in physiology and foraging behaviour have been reported for birds (Bean et al., 2014), which are susceptible to exposure through the food chain (Bean et al., 2018; Lazarus et al., 2015), as well as through direct exposure to sewage sludge (Bean et al., 2014).

Beyond ecological effects, there is also concern about human safety (Kümmerer, 2010), because of the presence of psychopharmaceuticals in drinking water (Baken et al., 2018; Houtman et al., 2014), and in vegetables grown using recycled water (Fu et al., 2019; Goldstein et al., 2014; Kim et al., 2017; Paltiel et al., 2016). Both psychopharmaceuticals and illicit drugs have the potential to disrupt so-called 'infochemicals', which are compounds used for intra-species communications (e.g., navigation, predator avoidance, mating behaviour, etc), since psychopharmaceuticals can mimic natural infochemicals in structure (Van Donk et al., 2016; Vera-Chang et al., 2018). Therefore, endpoints that derive from neurological and infochemical interactions are more sensitive than the classical endpoints (i.e., mortality, growth, and reproduction), and are

likely to be of high ecological relevance for compounds that produce these effects. Despite the increasing amount of pharmaceuticals, psychopharmaceuticals, and illicit drugs present in the environment, the number of studies on their occurrence, hazards, and risks has been relatively stagnant when compared to other drivers of ecological changes, such as habitat loss and climate change (Bernhardt et al., 2017). In addition, the focus is often on the same few psychopharmaceuticals and illicit drugs (e.g., carbamazepine, paracetamol, fluoxetine) rather than on the newer or more used compounds such as escitalopram (Elsevier B.V., 2020a, 2020b). It is therefore of utmost importance to determine the contribution of psychopharmaceuticals and illicit drugs to the presently ongoing degradation of environmental quality by assessing the environmental risk posed by these chemicals, and to put such risks into context by using metrics such as prescription data.

Ecological risk assessments are used to determine which compounds merit concern by weighing the concentrations in the environment (occurrence) and the effect concentrations (hazard) to produce risk quotients (RQs), which informs of the likelihood of effects occurring in the environment. Under this system, an RQ of 1 or higher means that the concentration of a compound in the environment has surpassed the minimum concentration to expect ecotoxic effects. Averaging the calculated RQs for all species for which ecotoxicity data are available provides a median risk for a specific compound (species-level risk). Alternatively, when sufficient ecotoxicity data are available, Species Sensitivity Distributions (SSDs) can be generated, which integrate all available ecotoxicity data, allowing the derivation of the Hazardous Concentration for 5% of the species (HC5), which is then entered into the RQ calculations instead of the species-specific effect concentrations. Hence, this method can be considered as an integrated multiple species risk assessment (Posthuma et al., 2001). However, SSDs require extensive ecotoxicity data to be considered robust, and multiple taxonomic groups to be considered more representative of natural communities (European Commission, 2018; Wheeler et al., 2002). Therefore, deriving an SSD may only be feasible for a limited number of data-rich compounds.

Despite the rise in the use of psychopharmaceuticals and illicit drugs, scientific attention to the presence in the environment, ecotoxicological hazards, and environmental risks of these compounds is still rather limited. Currently, reliable environmental risk assessments are hampered by a limited insight into the availability of data on the occurrence in the aquatic environment and the hazard to non-target organisms. Therefore, the aim of the present study was to review the data on occurrence and ecotoxicological hazard of psychopharmaceuticals and illicit drugs in European surface waters, paying attention to the accompanying uncertainties and knowledge gaps. To this end we provided an ecological risk assessment of psychopharmaceuticals and illicit drugs in European surface waters by weighing their occurrence and hazard. We contextualised these risks using (Dutch) prescription data.

2: Methods

2.1: Selection and classification of psychopharmaceuticals and illicit drugs

We based our selection of psychopharmaceuticals on the ATC-N list of 502 chemicals (WHO Collaborating Centre for Drug Statistics Methodology, 2018). Illicit drugs, such as stimulants, dissociatives, hallucinogenics, illicit opioids and cannabinoids, were added to this list by using the Opium Act of the Netherlands, containing 282 illicit compounds. Illicit and recreational drugs such as caffeine, nicotine, cocaine, THC, and amphetamines were merged to make a 'Stimulants & Illicits' class, since the ATC categories of these select compounds (e.g., cocaine as an anaesthetic) were deemed inappropriate. Since the ATC-N list also includes compounds that are used as illicit drugs (e.g., opioids), duplicates were removed. The resulting list totalled to 702 compounds (Table 1, Table S1). CAS numbers were obtained from DrugBank and PubChem (Kim et al., 2021; Wishart et al., 2018).

Table 1: Numbers of ATC-N psychopharmaceuticals and illicit drugs

Type (Source)	Number of Compounds
ATC-N (DrugBank)	502
N01 - Anaesthetics	43
N02 - Analgesics	75
N03 - Anti-Epileptics	40
N04 - Anti-Parkinson's	34
N05 - Psycholeptics	166
N06 - Psychoanaleptics	104
N07 - Other	41
Illicit Drugs (NL Opium Act)	282
Total (Duplicates Removed)	702

2.2: Occurrence data retrieval, filtering, and confidence score

To retrieve data on the occurrence of psychopharmaceuticals and illicit drugs in surface waters, the EU's IPCHEM monitoring platform (European Commission, 2021) was used, which contains 18 environmental occurrence databases. Four of these databases contained psychopharmaceuticals and illicit drugs, and data were extracted in July 2021 (Table S2). These four databases were the German UBA "Pharmaceuticals in the Environment"

database (Eike et al., 2019), the NORMAN Network database (NORMAN, 2021), the French Naiades Database (Naiades, 2020), and the EU WATERBASE database (EEA, 2021). In addition, we were given access to two Dutch databases that were not represented in IPCHEM. These were the WKP (Rijkswaterstaat, 2021) and the RIWA databases ("RIWA-Rijn," 2021b). To maximise the amount of data collected, the top 50 most prescribed drugs in the Netherlands from 2015 to 2020 (Zorginstituut Nederland, 2022) that did not have data in the aforementioned databases were manually searched for in literature by using the search terms "*<Drug name>*," *environmental*, *environment*, *occurrence*, *detection*, *detected*, *surface water*" in Google Scholar in June 2021.

Occurrence data were filtered for European surface waters only (Table S3), removing values for other water matrices, such as sewage effluent, groundwater, etc. False positives, such as nitrophenol being confused with phenol by search engines, were also removed. If the database flagged any data as 'questionable', these data were not used. Outliers that were unusual or unrealistically high values (e.g., 1×10^{11} mg/l) were either verified when the original source agreed with the database, corrected when the source disagreed with the database or else deleted if the original source was unavailable. Upon merging the data from the six databases, any duplicates were removed by inspecting sources, monitoring locations, monitoring location codes, and dates. For all data below the limit of detection (<LOD), the 90th percentile was calculated for all <LOD data per compound (Weltje and Sumpter, 2017), which helped to provide enough data to calculate the risk for compounds for which all data were <LOD.

An occurrence data confidence score was created as an indication of the amount and range of environmental occurrence data per compound. Since not all compounds have the same quantity and diversity of occurrence data, this will serve as an indication of data quantity and diversity. It should be noted that the occurrence confidence score was made before the LOD adjustments, meaning that values below or above the LOD are treated equally in the confidence assessment. The total score was calculated from 3 sub-scores: the number of entries (measurement frequency), countries (spatial distribution), and years (temporal distribution):

$$\text{Occurrence Confidence Score} = \frac{\# \text{ Entries}}{57} \times \frac{\# \text{ Countries}}{12} \times \frac{\# \text{ Years}}{2}$$

Equation 1: Occurrence data scoring system, with #Entries ≤ 57, #Countries ≤ 12, and #Years ≤ 2. These numbers are the median values for each of those categories (see Tables S5 and S7). I.e., the median number of entries was 57, the median number of countries was 12, and the median number of years was 2.

2.3: Ecotoxicity data retrieval, filtering, and confidence score

Ecotoxicity data were extracted from the US EPA ECOTOX Knowledgebase (EPA, 2013) and the German UBA ETOX database (Umweltbundesamt, 2008) in July 2021. In all cases, both compound names and CAS numbers were used as search criteria. In addition, the top 50 most prescribed drugs in the Netherlands in the years 2015 to 2020 (Zorginstituut Nederland, 2022) that did not have data in the aforementioned databases were manually searched for in literature by using the search terms '<Drug Name>', *ecotoxicity*, *ecotoxicology*' in Google Scholar in June 2021.

Ecotoxicity studies with no results, no stated endpoint, or irrelevant endpoints (i.e., bioaccumulation factors) were removed. To maximise the usable data, values recorded as below or above lowest or highest test concentration were adjusted to the lowest or highest test concentration, respectively (e.g., <1 µg became 1 µg, and >1 µg became 1 µg). Outliers that were unusual or unrealistic were either verified when the original source agreed with the database, corrected when the source disagreed with the database or else deleted if the original source was unavailable.

For studies that reported multiple endpoints per compound, only the most sensitive relevant endpoint was used

to avoid cases for which studies with multiple endpoints held a greater weight than studies with a single endpoint. The ecotoxicity data included many different measures of toxicity, including EC_x (Effective Concentration), LC_x (Lethal Concentration), LOEC (Lowest Observed Effect Concentration), NOEC (No Observed Effect Concentration) and MATC (Maximum Acceptable Toxicant Concentration). To maximise the amount of usable data, these were extrapolated to either acute EC₅₀ values (Effective Concentration for 50% of the exposed organisms) or to chronic NOEC values (No Observed Effect Concentration), following the methods for extrapolation described by Posthuma et al. (2019). To this end, the first step was to categorise datapoints as either “chronic” or “acute”, following the criteria of ECETOC (ECETOC, 1993), with acute and sub-chronic ecotoxicity data being merged as “acute” (Table S4). Secondly, all measures of toxicity were put into two categories, NOEC or EC₅₀, based on the original measure of toxicity (Posthuma et al., 2019). These two steps yielded four categories of data: acute NOEC, chronic NOEC, acute EC₅₀ and chronic EC₅₀. Acute NOEC values were multiplied by 1/3 to give chronic NOEC values, and chronic EC₅₀ values were multiplied by 3 to give acute EC₅₀ values. This resulted in two final data categories: the (extrapolated) chronic NOEC (denoted as cNOEC) and the (extrapolated) acute EC₅₀ (denoted as aEC₅₀) ecotoxicity data, which were then used for all further analyses in the study.

If enough ecotoxicity data were available, SSDs were generated to derive HC₅ values, allowing for an integrated multispecies measure of the hazard of that specific compound. To avoid that lacking ecotoxicity data hampered our analysis, SSDs were constructed based on a minimum number of 5 data points using the US EPA “SSD Generator” (EPA, 2016). Different SSDs were produced for cNOEC and aEC₅₀ values. aHC₅ (acute) and cHC₅ (chronic HC₅) values, defined as the hazardous concentration for 5% of species, were derived from the SSD plots of the respective compounds.

In order to assess the quantity and diversity of the ecotoxicity data per compound, we assigned a confidence score to each compound's cHC₅, aHC₅, cNOEC, and aEC50 values based on the TG27 criteria (European Commission, 2018). For each compound we scored the number of datapoints (out of a maximum of 10) and for taxa (out of a maximum of 8). These were then multiplied to create an ecotoxicity data score between 0 and 1 (Equation 2).

$$\text{Ecotoxicity Confidence Score} = \frac{\# \text{ Entries}}{10^*} \times \frac{\# \text{ Taxa}}{8^*}$$

Equation 2: Ecotoxicity data scoring system, with #Entries ≤ 10 and #Taxa ≤ 8
**Based on TG27 criteria*

2.4: Ecological risk assessment and confidence scores

By weighing the occurrence and ecotoxicity data, the ecological risk for each compound was assessed. Two-dimensional matrices of risk quotients (RQs) were created where each occurrence value was divided by each aEC50, cNOEC, aHC₅, or cHC₅ value per compound. Consequently, each compound could have up to four associated RQ matrices. To compare the effect of including the 90th percentile of the <LOD data (see 2.2), risk matrices were also made without the <LOD data.

$$RQ = \frac{\text{Concentration in the Environment}}{\text{Effect Concentration}}$$

Equation 3: Calculation of Risk Quotients (RQs), where effect concentration can be aEC50, cNOEC, aHC₅, or cHC₅ values.

The calculated RQs were then plotted in a logarithmic boxplot, and the percentage of RQ > 1 was determined, indicating a potential risk. A risk confidence score was calculated for each type of the four risk analysis using the following formula:

$$\text{Risk Confidence Score} = \text{Occurrence Score} \times \text{Ecotoxicity Score}$$

Equation 4: Calculation of risk confidence score.

All confidence scores were simplified into 5 categories (Table 2). Ecotoxicity data uses an adjusted lower boundary

due to the nature of the scoring system described in 2.3. All numerical confidence scores can be found in the supplementary information (Table S9).

Table 2: Simplified scoring system for all confidence scores.

<i>Confidence Score Category</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Range (Ecotox)</i>	<i>Range (Occurrence/Risk)</i>
<i>VH</i>	Very High	>0.75	>0.75
<i>H</i>	High	0.5 - <0.75	0.5 - <0.75
<i>M</i>	Medium	0.1 - <0.5	0.1 - <0.5
<i>L</i>	Low	0.015 - <0.1	0.01 - <0.1
<i>VL</i>	Very Low	<0.015	<0.01

2.5: Statistical Analyses

Pearson correlations were performed to assess relations between (Dutch) prescription data (Zorginstituut Nederland, 2022) and other variables, namely occurrence, occurrence data quantity (I.e. raw number of entries per compound), occurrence data confidence, ecotoxicity, ecotoxicity data quantity, ecotoxicity data confidence, and risk. A second series of Pearson correlations were performed to assess relations between risk (both cNOEC and aEC50) and these same variables. These correlations were log-transformed and performed using native Excel functions, with formulae embedded in Table S10. T-tests were performed on the cumulative data for occurrence, cNOEC and aEC50 data per compound class to test for significance between compound classes using native Excel Functions (Table S11).

3: Results and discussion

3.1: Data availability for the selected compounds

For 343 out of 702 (49%) of compounds, occurrence data were reported in European surface waters, but for 194 (28% of the total, or 57% of the number of compounds with occurrence data), the concentration in the environment was below the LOD, leaving 149 compounds (21%) with at least one occurrence datapoint above the LOD. Only for 105 psychopharmaceuticals (15%) ecotoxicity data were available, immediately highlighting that ecotoxicity data were even less available than occurrence data. Only for 87 (12%) compounds both occurrence and ecotoxicity data were available, allowing for a risk assessment. An overview of occurrence, ecotoxicity and risk data can be found in tables S5, S6 and S7, respectively. The NORMAN database provided most of the occurrence data in this study (Table 3), because it includes both literature studies and monitoring data. We noticed that there is a lack of parity between the multi-national occurrence databases, most notably the UBA, NORMAN and WATERBASE databases, which contain outdated references to each other. WATERBASE, RIWA, WKP, and NAIADES returned relatively low amounts of data, likely because these are general monitoring databases, which focus on other contaminants. This highlights the low priority of psychopharmaceuticals compared to legacy contaminants such as solvents and persistent organic pollutants. The occurrence literature search did not return any additional results for the countries included in this study (Table S3). Considering that the EPA and UBA databases are both collections of current ecotoxicity literature, there was a large lack of parity between the two ecotoxicity databases, with the EPA database being far larger than the UBA database. Moreover, additional ecotoxicity data were found during the present literature search.

Table 3: Summary of databases used, including geographic location, timespan, data type, positive (>LOD) and negative (<LOD) detections.

Database	Location	Years	Data Type	#Compounds After Cleaning/Filtering (Positive Detection)	#Compounds After Cleaning/Filtering (Negative Detection)
UBA 'Pharmaceuticals in the Environment'	DE + Worldwide	1997-2016	Occurrence (Literature)	82	74
NORMAN	**Europe	2000-2016	Occurrence (Literature + Monitoring)	121	330
WATERBASE	EU + EEA	1987-2019	Occurrence (Monitoring)	7	18
Naiades	FR	2015-2020	Occurrence (Monitoring)	17	20
RIMA	NL	2015-2020	Occurrence (Monitoring)	22	22
WKP	NL	1989-2019	Occurrence (Monitoring)	25	30
Occurrence Literature*	**Europe	2012-2019	Occurrence (Literature)	0	-
EPA ECOTOX	-	1939-2021	Ecotoxicity	94	-
UBA ETOX	-	1964-2017	Ecotoxicity	20	-
Ecotoxicity Literature*	-	2008-2020	Ecotoxicity	8	-

*Only top 50 most prescribed drugs based on yearly average DDD in the Netherlands were searched for in literature.

**See table S3 for countries and regions incorporated.

3.2: Occurrence of psychopharmaceuticals and illicit drugs in European surface waters

Over half of all psychopharmaceuticals and illicit drugs did not return occurrence data (Figure 7). Of the 343 (49%) psychopharmaceuticals occurrence data was available, only 52 (7%) compounds had the highest possible occurrence data confidence, while for almost all others (278, 40%) the confidence was medium or lower (Table S5). For 340 compounds the concentration was below the LOD, and so the 90th percentile procedure was used for those datapoints (Figure 7). Lithium presented by far the highest median concentration (0.016 mg/l), likely due to its natural occurrence as a mineral. In addition, common solvents such as diethyl ether, trichloroethylene, and phenol, were also present in high median concentrations due to uses in other applications such as industrial solvents. Common analgesics such as paracetamol, salicylamide, salicylic acid, aspirin, and ibuprofen, as well as carbamazepine, were also present in high concentrations (Figure S5).

Figure 7: Breakdown of the occurrence data showing the number of compounds that did not return data, only returned <LOD data, returned both <LOD and positive data, and only returned positive data.

The low number of data entries per compound contributed most to the generally low occurrence confidence when compared to the number of countries and years. This

indicates that there is a large disparity between well studied and understudied compounds in terms of raw data, with five compounds (caffeine, carbamazepine, chloroform, trichloroethylene, and ibuprofen) out of 702 compounds accounting for over 50% of all occurrence data (Table S5), with caffeine alone accounting for almost 20% of positive detection data. Importantly, occurrence data were missing for common and highly prescribed compounds such as betahistine, pyridostigmine, and distigmine (Tables S5, S8). For the illicit compounds, 127 out of 199 did not return any occurrence data, which were often obscure 'new psychoactive substances', or 'smartdrugs' (Table S5, Castiglioni et al., 2021; Weinstein et al., 2017). Other compounds without data included discontinued psychopharmaceuticals, such as hexapropymate, metamizole, and iproniazid.

Mean occurrence concentration, occurrence data quantity, and occurrence data confidence all showed a positive relation to Dutch prescription data (Conc.: $r = 0.207$, $p = 0.015$, Quant.: $r = 0.234$, $p = 0.006$, Conf.: $r = 0.299$, $p < 0.001$, Table S10). That is to say, the more a compound is prescribed, the higher its concentration in the environment, the higher the amount of data available, and the better its confidence score (data variety).

Table 4: Mean concentration, median concentration, standard deviation (S.D.), and median occurrence confidence per compound class. Median confidence is reported as low (L) or medium (M). Concentrations include values calculated from <LOD data as described in 2.2.

Class	Mean Conc. (mg/l)	Median Conc. (mg/l)	S.D.	Median Confidence
Anaesthetic	5.63×10^{-3}	6.00×10^{-5}	8.82×10^{-2}	M
Analgesic	2.12×10^{-1}	2.50×10^{-5}	9.93	L
Antiepileptic	1.21×10^{-2}	6.10×10^{-5}	7.12×10^{-1}	M
Anti-Parkinson's	7.53×10^{-6}	5.00×10^{-6}	1.01×10^{-5}	L
Psycholeptics	3.23×10^{-1}	5.40×10^{-5}	3.08	L
Psychoanaleptics	2.89×10^{-5}	5.90×10^{-6}	1.06×10^{-4}	L
Other	6.63×10^{-3}	3.90×10^{-6}	7.94×10^{-2}	L
Stimulants/Illicits	1.92×10^{-4}	8.70×10^{-5}	7.45×10^{-4}	L

When considering the different drug classes (Table 4), Stimulants/Illicits were present in the highest median concentration (8.70×10^{-5} mg/l), which can be solely attributed to the data dominance of caffeine (Table S5). The lowest median concentration (3.90×10^{-6} mg/l) was presented by the

'other' class. However, the highest and lowest median concentration per class differed only a factor of 26, whereas the difference within the Psycholeptics group, for example, was a factor of over 10,000. The T-tests showed that the median concentrations differed significantly between classes, except for the 'other' class and all other classes (Table S11). The range in the median concentrations within classes were much wider, partly attributed to a small number of compounds present in high concentrations, e.g., Lithium in the Psycholeptics class, paracetamol in the analgesics class, and carbamazepine in the antiepileptics class. This indicates that pharmaceutical class is generally not the governing property for environmental occurrence, and other properties such as persistence and prescription may better predict the concentrations in the environment.

To maximise the amount of occurrence data, we utilised all data below the LOD by taking the 90th percentile of the collective LODs per compound as described by Weltje and Sumpter (2017). While this method allows the evaluation of risks for compounds that otherwise would have lacked any occurrence data (see 3.4), it may, however, overestimate the occurrence for these compounds. Therefore, we also included occurrence values for compounds using positive detections only to compare the method (Table S5). The median of medians for dataset using the <LOD method was 4.85×10^{-6} mg/l, while the median of medians for the dataset not using the method was 5.63×10^{-6} mg/l, a 16% difference. However, by including the <LOD data, for 21 additional compounds the risk could be calculated (Table S7), giving merit to the method of Weltje and Sumpter (2017).

3.3: Aquatic ecotoxicity of psychopharmaceuticals and illicit drugs

105 (15%) psychopharmaceuticals returned ecotoxicity data, with none of the compounds achieving the requirements for a maximal ecotoxicity data confidence score. While there are numerous compounds that appear to be quite toxic, the top 10 most toxic compounds all had a low or very low data confidence, leaving the hazard assessment quite ambiguous (Table S6). Compounds with very high data confidence included carbamazepine, chloroform, paracetamol, ibuprofen, fluoxetine, phenol, and trichloroethylene. Carbamazepine demonstrated the highest toxicity of all

compounds and with a very high data score (cNOEC = 0.01 mg/l, S6). For both the cNOEC and the aEC50 datasets, the TG27 requires higher plants as one of the species groups to be included to provide an ecosystem-wide approach, which were lacking for all compounds. Yet, even without higher plants as a mandatory category, no compound would have achieved the maximum confidence score for either cNOEC or aEC50 (Table S6). Only 10 compounds achieved a high or very high data confidence, with over half of all compounds having a low or very low confidence (Table S6). As for the occurrence data, only a few compounds (phenol, trichloroethylene, carbamazepine & chloroform) accounted for over 50% of all ecotoxicity data, with phenol accounting for 25%. Therefore, ecotoxicity data were also characterised by a large disparity between well studied and understudied compounds. Most of the raw ecotoxicity data (61%) were extrapolated into an aEC50, which was because older studies tended to report acute results rather than chronic.

Table 5: Median ecotoxicity (mg/l), standard deviation (S.D.), and ecotoxicity data confidence score per compound class for both ecotoxicity datasets.

Class	Median cNOEC (mg/l)	cNOEC S.D.	cNOEC Conf.	Median aEC50 (mg/l)	aEC50 S.D.	aEC50 Conf.
Anaesthetic	6.3	211	M	42	951	L
Analgesic	1.0	153	L	102.3	5173023	L
Antiepileptic	0.047	274	L	56.4	426	L
Anti-Parkinson's	0.891	-	L	58.6	307	L
Psycholeptics	2.943	83	L	65.5	2249	L
Psychoanaleptics	0.056	146	L	1.7	327	M
Other	0.013	6	L	0.242	84	L
Stimulants/Illicits	0.085	257	L	47.4	1154	L

Considering inter-class differences in ecotoxicity (Table 5), there was no clear indication as to which compound class was more toxic. For example, according to the cNOEC data, Stimulants/Illicits were the most toxic (0.08 mg/l), while anaesthetics were the least toxic (6.3 mg/l). However, according to the aEC50 data, both of these two classes exhibited a very similar toxicity (47 and 42 mg/l respectively). The T-tests showed that there were only a few statistical differences in toxicity between compound classes, with the exception for differences between anaesthetics and Psychoanaleptics for both datasets, which is likely due to the

high cNOEC values for the antidepressants in the Psychoanaleptics class (Table S11). Aside from the notable exception of anaesthetics and Psychoanaleptics, the broad lack of significant differences in ecotoxicity between compound groups could be related to the low confidence scores of all compound classes (Table 5), making it difficult to draw firm conclusions as to which class is most toxic. Indeed, the top 5 most toxic Psychoanaleptics had a low or very low confidence, while 3 out of 5 of the most toxic anaesthetics had a high or higher data confidence, which could indicate that poor data quality explains why the T-tests showed a significant difference between these two classes. Like for the occurrence data, the intra-class differences were much larger than the inter-class differences, as reflected by the large standard deviations. This highlights that each compound needs to be assessed independently, and groupings such as therapeutic class obviously do not reflect species-specific nor compound-specific sensitivities.

For only 11 out of 702 compounds enough data were available to generate SSDs based on the non-stringent criteria used here (i.e., a minimum of five species), with none reaching the TG27 requirements of 10 diverse species. There was a lack of test species diversity, as fish, crustaceans, and algae accounted for almost 75% of all test species and data for invertebrates, insects, molluscs, plants, worms and amphibians are largely lacking (Figure 8). This clearly calls for more extensive and more diverse ecotoxicity data. To combat this lack in ecotoxicity diversity and data, for all psychopharmaceuticals in use ecotoxicity data should be generated that follow the protocol in TG27. While it may seem counter-intuitive to include higher plants as test species for psychoactive compounds, we argue that this creates a level playing field between species and chemical classes. In addition, psychopharmaceuticals may exert ecotoxic effects on higher plants that we simply do not know about due to a total lack of data, which was the case in the past for herbicide effects on animals (Perkins et al., 2000; Tsui and Chu, 2003). Including such data would help to obtain a better estimation of the hazard of psychopharmaceuticals by means of an SSD, aiding a reliable estimation of the risk on a multiple species level. We do, however, acknowledge that testing many different species may be unfeasible, which calls for

prioritisation. An additional and alternative approach could be to run more *in silico* tests since there have been strides to move away from animal testing in recent years (Scholz et al., 2013). As such, *in silico* methods, like QSARs (Schüürmann et al., 2007), have been improving in recent years with the use of machine learning (Lovrić et al., 2021; Wu et al., 2021). Another *in vitro* alternative is cellular bioassays (Fent, 2007; Lammer et al., 2009), although there are concerns over the ecological relevance of such bioassays (Schirmer, 2006). While it is beyond the scope of this study to go into detail about *in silico/in vitro* to *in vivo* extrapolation, it is an interesting topic for future research (Bell et al., 2018).

Unlike for occurrence data, for which there is a validated procedure for dealing <LOD data (Weltje and Sumpter, 2017), such a procedure is lacking for hazard data. Following our pragmatic approach to adjust ecotoxicity data recorded as below or above the lowest or highest test concentration to the lowest or highest test concentration, we might respectively under- or over-estimate ecotoxicity. Exact effect concentrations were not established in only a small number (6%) of the datapoints used in this study. However, our approach still maximises the number of ecotoxicity data which is relevant given the lack of data. Only 13% of the ecotoxicity data considered behavioural end points (Figure 8). Since psychopharmaceuticals are designed to influence behaviour, and behavioural effects occur by definition at lower concentrations than survival, toxicity may be underestimated when using only non-behavioural endpoints.

Figure 8: Proportion of taxa within the ecotoxicity data (Top) and breakdown of the studied ecotoxicity endpoints (Bottom) showing the proportion of non-behavioural to behavioural endpoints, and the breakdown of behavioural endpoints.

3.4: Risks of psychopharmaceuticals in European surface waters

Only for 87 out of 702 (12%) compounds enough occurrence and ecotoxicity data were available to calculate indicative environmental risks, for which the chronic results are visualised in Figures 9 and 10, where data above an RQ of 1 (red line) are indicative of risk (Table S7). Table 6 shows the 20 out of 87 compounds that demonstrated a potential risk based on the % of RQs above 1 from the cNOEC analyses, while an additional 3 compounds indicated a potential risk based on the aEC50 results (Table S7) resulting in 23 compounds carrying a potential (at least 1 RQ>1) risk. The five riskiest compounds in this analysis were risperidone, carbamazepine, paracetamol, cocaine, and ibuprofen, for which at least 10% of the RQs above 1. In addition, the cHC₅ results showed that fluoxetine also carried a high risk (35%, Figure 10, Table 6). However, only for carbamazepine, paracetamol, fluoxetine, and ibuprofen the confidence of this risk assessment was high or very high. Carbamazepine stands out as the only compound in any analysis to have both a median risk above one, and very high confidence (Figure 10). Moreover, for many of the compounds for which a risk could be assessed (56 out of 87 compounds) the confidence scores were below 1% (Table S9), and thus are labelled as having very low confidence.

For only 11 out of 702 compounds sufficient ecotoxicity data were available to generate SSDs and, therefore, to calculate integrated multi species risks. However, none of these SSDs met the TG 27 criteria, so these results should be interpreted with caution (Figures 10, S7b, Table S7). Comparing the results of Figures 9 and 10 reveals that the risk for compounds based on the cHC₅ are higher than those based on the individual ecotoxicity data (see e.g., carbamazepine). Since SSDs provide an estimation of a multi-species hazard that is closer to being ecosystem wide, and therefore provide a more robust estimation of the actual hazard, our results indicate that ecosystems are indeed vulnerable to psychopharmaceuticals.

Table 6: Compounds that demonstrated a potential risk based on the cNOEC dataset, along with confidence. Where applicable, the cHC5 results are also included, as are the whole drug classes for reference.

Drug/Class	cNOEC Risk (Mean)	cNOEC Risk (Median)	cNOEC Risk (%)	cHC5 Risk (Mean)	cHC5 Risk (Median)	cHC5 Risk (%)	Data Confidence
Anaesthetics	1.38x10⁻¹	6.04x10⁻⁶	0.22%	-	-	-	M
Chloroform	7.57x10 ⁺¹	5.68x10 ⁻⁶	0.25%	1.99	1.59x10 ⁻⁴	1.85%	H
Phenol	3.12	6.80x10 ⁻⁵	0.14%	4.59x10 ⁻¹	5.53x10 ⁻³	0.23%	M
Trichloroethylene	4.18	7.36x10 ⁻⁶	0.18%	2.21x10 ⁻²	5.19x10 ⁻⁴	0.00%	H
Analgesics	7.85x10⁻⁵	1.38x10⁻⁵	6.69%	-	-	-	L
Ibuprofen	2.52x10 ⁺⁶	4.00x10 ⁻⁴	6.53%	1.52x10 ⁺⁵	6.35x10 ⁻¹	33.35%	VH
Paracetamol	5.33x10 ⁺⁶	5.30x10 ⁻⁴	16.92%	8.16x10 ⁺⁵	4.41x10 ⁻¹	40.22%	H
Salicylic acid	1.03	2.52x10 ⁻⁶	0.18%	1.65	1.03x10 ⁻⁴	0.74%	M
Tramadol	3.57x10 ⁺¹	1.23x10 ⁻⁴	0.09%	-	-	-	L
Psycholeptics	7.60x10⁺³	3.76x10⁻⁶	4.79%	-	-	-	VL
Diazepam	2.55x10 ⁻¹	2.26x10 ⁻⁶	0.11%	-	-	-	M
Oxazepam	1.03x10 ⁺⁵	1.75x10 ⁻¹	9.20%	-	-	-	L
Pentobarbital	1.18x10 ⁺²	2.57x10 ⁻⁶	4.00%	5.58x10 ⁻²	2.09x10 ⁻²	0.00%	L
Temazepam	3.39x10 ⁺⁴	5.65x10 ⁻³	1.42%	-	-	-	L
Clozapine	1.92x10 ⁺²	5.59x10 ⁻⁴	7.71%	-	-	-	L
Risperidone	2.58x10 ⁺¹	6.67	100.0%	-	-	-	L
Lithium	2.75x10 ⁻¹	1.95x10 ⁻⁴	0.07%	-	-	-	VL
Psychoaleptics	3.05x10⁺³	4.29x10⁻⁵	2.16%	-	-	-	L
Citalopram	3.00x10 ⁻¹	4.03x10 ⁻⁵	0.71%	-	-	-	M
Fluoxetine	4.27x10 ⁺⁴	3.80x10 ⁻⁴	3.40%	6.51	4.41x10 ⁻¹	35.57%	VH
Flvoxamine	2.30x10 ⁻¹	1.98x10 ⁻⁵	1.39%	-	-	-	L
Antiepileptics	1.39x10⁺⁶	2.16x10⁻⁵	9.65%	-	-	-	L
Carbamazepine	1.11x10 ⁺⁷	4.90x10 ⁻³	9.74%	5.60x10 ⁺⁵	2.61	85.37%	VH
Stimulants/Illicit	2.62x10⁺¹	1.99x10⁻⁵	16.46%	-	-	-	L
Gafrine	1.76x10 ⁺²	2.00x10 ⁻³	16.48%	-	-	-	M
Cocaine	7.45	2.35x10 ⁻¹	10.17%	-	-	-	L
Anti-Parkinson's	1.40x10⁻⁶	1.40x10⁻⁶	0.00%	-	-	-	VL
Other	2.32x10⁻⁴	5.13x10⁻⁵	0.00%	-	-	-	VL

Figure 9: Risk quotient boxplot based on occurrence and (extrapolated) chronic NOEC ecotoxicity data. Whiskers represent upper and lower quartiles, while the box represents middle upper and middle lower. The central line indicates the median value. Compounds have been grouped and colour-coded based on therapeutic class. Confidence level is indicated in the floating text by each box. (LV=Very Low, L=Low, M=Medium, H=High, VH=Very High).

Figure 10: Risk quotient boxplot based on occurrence and HC_5 values calculated from (extrapolated) chronic NOEC ecotoxicity data. Whiskers represent upper and lower quartiles, while the box represents middle upper and middle lower. The central line indicates the median value. Compounds have been colour-coded based on therapeutic class. Confidence level is indicated in the floating text by each box (LV=Very Low, L=Low, M=Medium, H=High, VH=Very High).

The most prescribed compounds are also the most well studied, e.g., carbamazepine, paracetamol, ibuprofen, and fluoxetine collectively accounted for 23% of the ecotoxicity data and 28% of the occurrence data. When comparing the Dutch prescription data in defined daily doses to the calculated risks, the compounds that carry the highest risk are often also the most used and prescribed (Table S8). Nonetheless, Pearson correlations (Table S10) did not indicate that prescription correlated to risk.

The amount of occurrence data positively correlated with a higher observed risk (cNOEC: $r = 0.656$, $p < 0.001$, aEC50: $r = 0.659$, $p < 0.001$), as did the amount of cNOEC data ($r = 0.590$, $p < 0.001$), and aEC50 data ($r = 0.556$, $p < 0.001$). Confidence in both ecotoxicity datasets also correlate to risk (cNOEC: $r = 0.487$, $p = 0.001$, aEC50: $r = 0.460$, $p = 0.006$) (Table S10). Hence, the better a compound is studied, the higher the resulting calculated risk. This is worrisome, since this may indicate that many poorly studied compounds may carry hidden risks and that more research is needed into the occurrence and hazards of psychopharmaceuticals to elucidate if these hidden risks are present.

In contrast to the general observations discussed above, not for all commonly prescribed compounds reliable data were available (Figure 11). Evaluating the data plotted in Figure 11 in more detail reveals that risperidone (37th most prescribed in NL, Table S8) demonstrated the highest median risk of all compounds, but with a confidence on the cusp of 'low' and 'very low' (Table S9) and therefore its calculated risk cannot be considered reliable. Similarly, risk could not be calculated for betahistine (7th most prescribed in NL, Table S8) due to a lack of both ecotoxicity and occurrence data. For the sedative tramadol, numerous occurrence data entries were obtained, resulting in a maximum occurrence data score, yet only one ecotoxicity datapoint was found. Even for the most prescribed psychopharmaceutical, paroxetine, the risk was calculated with only a medium confidence, owing to a lack of ecotoxicity data. Since illicit drugs do not have prescription data, we were not able to perform a similar comparison. However, it is notable that some illicit stimulants demonstrated some risk, e.g., cocaine (Table 6). The stimulants group, which consists of many illicit and recreational drugs (caffeine, nicotine, etc), included multiple compounds with very high

occurrence confidence, but low or no ecotoxicity confidence (Table S9).

Figure 11: Scatter plot showing the distributions of ecotoxicity (right) and occurrence (Left) data scores vs (Dutch) prescription rank (Centre Axis) for the top 100 prescribed psychopharmaceuticals. Both cNOEC and aEC50 are shown on the ecotoxicity side (Right).

The present study differs from other risk assessments, in that we did not include additional assessment factors. This was done because we did not intend to derive environmental quality standards but rather aimed to calculate the risk of adverse effects on non-target organisms based on measured concentrations of psychopharmaceuticals in European surface waters and measured effect concentrations. This approach, therefore, leads to a data-driven quantification of the risks of psychopharmaceuticals in surface waters, which is less stringent than other assessments that do incorporate these assessment factors.

3.5: General Discussion

The present study demonstrated that for psychopharmaceuticals, inter-class differences were smaller than intra-class differences, emphasising that each psychopharmaceutical should be assessed individually and that making assumptions based on related drugs ('cross

reading') could be problematic in a regulatory setting. When considering the chemical structures of psychopharmaceuticals of a certain class, there can be very major differences. The SSRI class of antidepressants highlights this very well (See Table 1 in Silva et al., 2012), since compounds within this class have a high degree of variability in chemical structure, even though this group has a common pharmacological MOA. As an alternative to class categorization, groupings based on chemical structure may therefore be further explored.

We found that only for 15% of the psychopharmaceuticals ecotoxicity data were available. This appears to be about 19% for human pharmaceuticals in general (Gunnarsson et al., 2019), indicating that the lack of data is not just limited to psychopharmaceuticals. As highlighted by Gunnarsson et al. (Gunnarsson et al., 2019), this stems from mandatory ecotoxicity testing during clinical trials only starting in 2006 in the EU and not at all in the US, indicating that data are missing for legacy (prior to 2006) pharmaceuticals. Comparing psychopharmaceuticals in general to other anthropogenic compounds revealed that they have lower cumulative chronic NOECs than other industrial chemicals, but higher when compared to biocides, pesticides and general pharmaceuticals. This was still the case when common solvents were removed from the psychopharmaceutical series (van Dijk et al., 2021). This outcome likely stems from the fact that biocides and pesticides are designed to be toxic, and as Gunnarsson (2019) points out, pharmaceuticals that disrupt the endocrine system tend to be the most toxic. In addition, as shown in Figure 8, the ecotoxicity data in this study was lacking behavioural endpoints, which may suggest that the cumulative NOECs presented in Figure 12 may be lower with better ecotoxicity data. Nonetheless, in the EU, psychopharmaceuticals, along with pharmaceuticals, are regulated by the European Medicines Agency (EMA), and the EU Pharmaceutical legislation does not provide environmental protection goals, unlike legislation for industrial chemicals. Greater regulatory harmonisation of (psycho)pharmaceuticals with other industrially produced compounds can help to alleviate both the lack of data presented in the current study, as well as the risk through a more coherent regulatory framework. Indeed, the need for a 'one substance – one assessment' approach, proposes an assessment that does not differentiate between

use class, but rather on the individual chemical (van Dijk et al., 2021).

Figure 12: Comparison of cNOEC values for various groups of anthropogenic compound classes. Psychopharmaceutical and Psychopharmaceutical (W/O Solvents) series are from the present study, other series were taken from (Gunnarsson et al., 2019; Gustavsson et al., 2017; van Dijk et al., 2021) Note that assessment factors were not included in this plot.

A 2022 study on pharmaceutical occurrence in global rivers yielded somewhat comparable results to the occurrence data presented here (Wilkinson et al., 2022). Interestingly, the concentrations of most compounds were higher in the global rivers than in European surface waters (median concentrations of e.g. paracetamol were 296 vs 148 ng/l in the present study, gabapentin 272 vs 200 ng/l, caffeine 500 vs 98 ng/l, nicotine 128 vs 40 ng/l), with the notable exception of carbamazepine, which showed higher concentrations in the present study (29 vs 73 ng/l). This, however, is in line with the study of Wilkinson et al. (2022), since they noted that anticonvulsant concentrations vary heavily depending geographic region.

A 2014 risk assessment of pharmaceuticals in French waters using a PNEC-based risk assessment found paracetamol, ibuprofen, oxazepam and carbamazepine to present a “likely” risk (Bouissou-Schurtz et al., 2014). This broadly agrees with the results presented here (Table 6,

Figures 9 and 10), although Bouissou-Schurtz (2014) considered a much smaller geographical area and only seven psychopharmaceuticals. It is interesting to note that Bouissou-Schurtz (2014) identified five pharmaceuticals to pose a risk, four of which being psychopharmaceuticals. In contrast, a case study of two WWTPs in Italy found that the three psychopharmaceuticals included in the study (propyphenazone, carbamazepine and diazepam) were less of a risk than other pharmaceutical groups, such as antibiotics (Al Aukidy et al., 2012). A review on the risks of antidepressants to fish yielded comparable results as those shown by the chC_5 results of the present study (Figure 9). (Gould et al., 2021) reported a median RQ of 0.41 for Fluoxetine, compared to 0.44 in the present study. Sertraline differed by a factor of 10 (0.01 vs 0.001 in the present study). The most notable difference was for Venlafaxine, for which Gould et al. (2021) reported a median RQ of 0.66, the highest in the study, while we reported 3.1×10^{-4} . However, we did not create an SSD for venlafaxine due to insufficient ecotoxicity data, and Gould et al. (2021) only perform risk assessments for fish, which may account for the differences observed between the two studies. Nonetheless, the present study, along with some of the aforementioned studies, indeed reports risks for some psychopharmaceuticals in the aquatic environment.

Beyond surface waters, risks have also been reported for psychopharmaceuticals in terrestrial environments, namely soils that have been treated with sewage sludge (Aydın et al., 2022; Camotti Bastos et al., 2020; Martín et al., 2012; Mejías et al., 2021). Such studies tend to focus on other pharmaceuticals, such as antibiotics and endocrine disruptors, since these have a higher risk than psychopharmaceuticals. Soil-based studies also show that the risk posed by psychopharmaceuticals appears to be less than those presented in the current study, which may indicate that the aquatic environment is the more sensitive ecosystem. However, carbamazepine, sertraline, ibuprofen, and fluoxetine have demonstrated risks in soils in some studies (Martín et al., 2012; Mejías et al., 2021) which demonstrate that wastewater effluent is not the only source of environmental psychopharmaceutical risk, and that our arguments for more data also extends to other ecosystems.

3.6: Study limitations and future research

This study did not focus on specific locations or situations, though site specific risk assessment can be of relevance, since prescription, consumption, and removal of psychopharmaceuticals may depend on local factors. Temporal variation can also be relevant, as prescriptions can vary depending on the time of the year (Heald et al., 2021; Winkler et al., 2019). Furthermore, population densities in different WWTP catchment areas, WWTP removal efficiencies, and drought conditions (Sjerps et al., 2017) influence occurrence. Events such as natural disasters and the COVID-19 pandemic can influence prescription and consumption patterns of psychopharmaceuticals (Andalo, 2020; Boehnke et al., 2021; Palmer and Seoudi, 2021; Robinson, 2021; Usher et al., 2012). Despite using European occurrence data, we only used prescription data from the Netherlands, as finding prescription data from all European countries was not feasible. Yet, this does mean that conclusions based on prescription data may not be fully generalisable. As such, as a follow up and refinement of the present study, site specific risk assessments may also investigate local cases, such as a single nation or region, accounting for specific and temporal differences. We also could not verify every datapoint (both ecotoxicity and occurrence) due to the large amount of data points, and only focused verification efforts on outliers.

We defined psychopharmaceuticals as the ATC-N class plus illicit drugs according to the Dutch Opium Act. The ATC system gives an ATC code to a compound based on its uses in past and present treatments but overlooks a drug's MOA when that MOA is not specifically employed in a medical treatment. For example, the muscle relaxant phenprobamate is in the ATC-M class (Muscular system), and has no ATC-N number associated to it, yet it has displayed sedative effects (Demir et al., 2015). Other examples include illicit compounds that are being screened for various therapeutic uses (Aan Het Rot et al., 2012; Mathew et al., 2008; Sessa, 2017). Therefore, many of the non-ATC-N pharmaceuticals can in principle exert relevant MOAs, which may affect relevant behavioural endpoints. However, due to the infeasibility of checking all compounds for these MOAs, these were not included. This also lends itself in favour of a 'one substance – one assessment'

style approach, where non-psychopharmaceuticals (in the strict sense) should be screened for behavioural ecotoxicological endpoints alongside pharmaceuticals. In addition, this will need to be performed not only for new chemicals, but also for (highly used) legacy chemicals. However, we do acknowledge that this is a costly recommendation, and thus could be supplemented with other types of ecotoxicity testing, as discussed in 3.3.

Transformation products can be found in higher concentrations than parent compounds in the environment (Hans-Rudolf Buser et al., 1999; Langford and Thomas, 2011; Zhang et al., 2008), and are generally more mobile and harder to remove by WWTPs (Rivera-Utrilla et al., 2013). The toxicity of transformation products is of concern, since many transformation products may still be biologically active, and thus exert a specific toxicity above baseline toxicity through a viable MOA (Celiz et al., 2009; Escher and Fenner, 2011; Neuwoehner et al., 2009). The lack of quantitative occurrence data on transformation products is often a practical issue since detection by techniques such as LCMS requires standards for these transformation products. In the case of transformation products, these standards are often more expensive compared to the parent compound, or might not exist at all as an analytical standard and therefore must be synthesised *de novo* at large financial costs (Hernández et al., 2011; Wong and MacLeod, 2009). The lack of availability, or the large investments involved, often deter researchers from detecting transformation products, unless the study is specifically focussed on transformation products for reasons such as calculating consumption of illicit drugs (Ort et al., 2014; Thomas et al., 2012), or utilises parent:metabolite ratios to predict metabolite concentrations (de Jongh et al., 2012; ter Laak et al., 2014). The transformation product challenge also extends to ecotoxicity data, even more so, since ecotoxicity experiments require higher volumes. Hence, transformation products are often overlooked in both pharmaceutical occurrence and ecotoxicity studies (Celiz et al., 2009; Charnaud et al., 2019; Cleuvers, 2003; Fram and Belitz, 2011; Frédéric and Yves, 2014; Kar and Roy, 2012; Mompelat et al., 2009; Vestel et al., 2016).

This study did not incorporate mixture toxicity into the hazard assessment. For psychopharmaceutical mixture toxicity only a limited number of studies are available. For example, additive mixture effects have been demonstrated for SSRIs (Christensen et al., 2007), and for a mixture of carbamazepine and ibuprofen (Cleuvers, 2004). These mixture toxicity experiments represent realistic scenarios, since the compounds present in these mixtures have indeed been demonstrated to be jointly present in surface water samples, as listed in the data bases used in this study (Patrolecco et al., 2013). Moreover, in the occurrence databases (Table 3) many other examples of jointly present psychopharmaceuticals can be found. This should thus be considered in future, more focused, risk assessments. Future studies should also screen for transformation products in environmental monitoring and investigate their ecotoxicological impact, alongside other parent drugs and transformation products in mixture toxicity tests. Focus should be given to compounds that are highly used, present a risk, or have low data confidence, as defined in the present study.

4: Conclusions

Our findings revealed a lack of both occurrence and ecotoxicity data, hampering a reliable environmental risk assessment of most psychopharmaceuticals, with ecotoxicity data being the scarcest. Moreover, the limited data were also not spread uniformly, with a handful of well researched compounds dominating both occurrence and ecotoxicity data. Non-behavioural endpoints and only a few test species were dominating the ecotoxicity data. Thus, many compounds may present a risk that cannot be estimated due to missing or skewed data. This is alarming, since we showed that better studied compounds carried higher risks. We found that the most prescribed compounds in the Netherlands were the most studied and occurred most frequently. However, many of the highly prescribed psychopharmaceuticals still lack proper data. Common illicit drugs also demonstrated risks, and generally provided good occurrence data, but lacked ecotoxicity data. Furthermore, intra-class differences were larger than inter-class differences, emphasising that therapeutic grouping may not be an appropriate way to categorise compounds and that each compound should rather be individually assessed for risk. Despite the presently identified large knowledge gaps, we conclude that the presence of a substantial part of data-rich psychopharmaceuticals in surface waters present an ecological risk for aquatic non-target organisms.

Acknowledgments & Supplementary Information

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Chapter Three - Presence, Removal, and Risks of Psychopharmaceuticals in Wastewater Streams

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Abstract

Psychopharmaceuticals are used to treat psychological disorders and other conditions relating to the nervous system and are known to affect non-target organisms at low concentrations. Their occurrence in the water cycle remains an understudied topic, with data lacking for many compounds, and risks not accounted for in removal targets. Therefore, the current study aimed to provide insights into the presence, removal, and risks of psychopharmaceuticals in wastewater. Furthermore, the use of risk assessment in the context of proposed legislation is discussed. 30 highly used psychopharmaceuticals were studied during one week in the wastewater of the Amsterdam West Wastewater Treatment Plant (WWTP) using solid phase extraction and Ultra High Performance Liquid Chromatography–Quadrupole Time of Flight–High Resolution Mass Spectrometry (UHPLC–qTOF–HRMS). 20 target compounds were detected in the influent (17 ng – 99 µg/L) and 16 in the effluent (34 ng/L – 17 µg/L).

Removal efficiencies during treatment ranged from 24% to >99%. Paracetamol, amphetamine, fluoxetine, levetiracetam, phenacetin, and sertraline demonstrated almost complete removal, while tramadol, lidocaine, lamotrigine, fluvoxamine and carbamazepine reported removals below 50%, with lidocaine demonstrating the lowest removal (24%). Utilising existing ecotoxicity data, a preliminary risk assessment was performed to contextualise the calculated removal efficiencies. Here, sertraline and ibuprofen still demonstrated a potential risk, despite high removal efficiencies of both compounds. The present study highlights that wastewater contains abundant numbers and ecotoxicologically relevant concentrations of psychopharmaceuticals that are insufficiently removed by the WWTP. The implementation of risk-based removal targets in legislation is discussed, in order to facilitate the reduction in emissions of psychopharmaceuticals, for example by adequate WWTP upgrades with advanced treatments in order to ensure a toxic free environment.

1: Introduction

Psychopharmaceuticals are a subclass of pharmaceuticals designed to treat medical conditions relating to the nervous system. They are classified by the World Health Organisation as ATC-N (WHO, 2018) and are a vital tool in modern medicine, with a growing population that uses them on a regular basis (European Medicines Agency, 2021). The growth in their use is fuelled by several factors such as growing and aging populations, a loss of social stigma of the underlying diseases (e.g. depression), and a growing number of psychopharmaceuticals entering global markets (Bean et al., 2018; Gao et al., 2013; Massey et al., 2018; Read et al., 2014; World Health Organization, 2011). In the Netherlands alone 2.9 million people, corresponding to 17% of the population, were prescribed psychopharmaceuticals in 2021 (Zorginstituut Nederland, 2022).

After use, psychopharmaceuticals are excreted by the human body, as parent compounds and/or transformation products, and enter the sewage system. These compounds are often polar and persistent, and therefore are not removed effectively by wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs). Thus WWTPs are a continuous source of psychopharmaceuticals into the aquatic environment (Cunha et al., 2019, 2017; Delli Compagni et al., 2020; Gago-Ferrero et al., 2019; X. Wang et al., 2020). Psychopharmaceuticals have been shown to have adverse ecotoxicological effects on many aquatic species, due to similar neurochemical architecture shared between humans and other non-target species (Edsinger and Dölen, 2018; Liebeskind et al., 2017). Psychopharmaceuticals can alter the behaviour of non-target organisms, leading to changes in feeding, social interactions, and predator avoidance (Brodin et al., 2014; Cerveny et al., 2020; Painter et al., 2009; Schultz et al., 2011; Valenti et al., 2012), amongst others. These ecotoxicological effects have been demonstrated at environmentally relevant concentrations in surface waters (Schultz et al., 2011). Despite large data gaps still hindering proper risk assessment, where data are available it is clear that the presence of psychopharmaceuticals can pose a risk to the aquatic ecosystems (Davey et al., 2022).

Liquid Chromatography-High Resolution Mass Spectrometry (LC-HRMS) techniques have improved over recent years, which has led to an increase in occurrence data for psychopharmaceuticals (Heberer, 2002; Luo et al., 2014; Ort et al., 2014; Richardson, 2007). Often it is antidepressants, antiepileptics and painkillers that occur in the highest concentrations (Davey et al., 2022), with an extreme example of paracetamol, fluoxetine, and carbamazepine found in concentrations approaching or exceeding 1 mg/L in Almeria WWTP effluent in Spain (Bueno et al., 2012). The high effluent concentrations have led to the occurrence of pharmaceuticals in surface waters around the world (aus der Beek et al., 2016; Davey et al., 2022; Fonseca et al., 2020; Gago-Ferrero et al., 2020; Mheidli et al., 2022; Nozaki et al., 2023; Silva et al., 2011; Wilkinson et al., 2022). The prevalence of these compounds in effluent and surface waters has triggered scientists and institutions to monitor these compounds (Rijkswaterstaat, 2021; RIWA-Rijn, 2021a) and to build databases of occurrence data (Eike et al., 2019; NORMAN, 2021).

At the same time, many highly prescribed or used compounds are still understudied, sometimes due to a lack of (affordable) analytical standards (Davey et al., 2022), or are widely unmonitored (Rijkswaterstaat, 2024, 2021). Even for the compounds that have been analysed, many still lack measured WWTP removal data (Fawzi et al., 2021). In the coming decades, many Dutch WWTPs will undergo upgrades to improve water treatment (Spit et al., 2023) as is expected throughout Europe (van Dijk et al., 2023). The EU's proposal for an urban wastewater treatment directive (European Commission, 2022) proposes progressively more rigorous measures over time. It is vital to understand how well these upgrades can increase the removal of psychopharmaceuticals, yet discussions on how to measure removals remain ongoing.

One proposal for defining removal targets in the urban wastewater treatment directive is a risk-based approach determined by the member state (See Article 18, European Commission, 2022). By comparing the effluent concentration and the ecotoxicity of a compound, a conservative risk assessment can be performed to determine if a psychopharmaceutical might present an ecological risk. A risk can be due to a low removal efficiency, high prescription and

use, high inherent toxicity, or a combination thereof. As such, the risk assessment approach could allow for a more granular look into removal efficiencies of micropollutants, which could be an advantage over flat removal targets (Bourgin et al., 2018; STOWA, 2020; Svahn and Borg, 2024) or population caps for treatment levels (European Commission, 2022).

Therefore, the current study is aimed to perform target screening on psychopharmaceutical occurrence in influent and effluent samples from the Amsterdam West WWTP during one week. LC-HRMS is used to measure concentrations of psychopharmaceuticals from a preselected target list of compounds that was based on their risk in literature, or high prescription and use. Using the quantitative target data, we investigate the removal efficiencies of these compounds and contextualise the data by performing a preliminary risk assessment using existing ecotoxicity data. This pairing of ecotoxicity to removal is to investigate the merits and drawbacks of such a method, should it be used in legislation.

2: Methods & Materials

Supplementary Information (SI) for this manuscript can be found in an Excel file containing 14 supplementary tables. Details on the tables can be found at the top of each sheet. A new extraction method for all compounds was developed for this study. A full explanation and results of the method validation can be found in the method validation supplementary document, and in section SI-8 of the Supplementary Information (SI) excel file. The method validation indicated that 30 of the 42 target compounds had sufficient recoveries and limited matrix effects, and therefore are included in the study.

2.1: Target Compound Selection

Psychopharmaceuticals, as defined in (Davey et al., 2022), are around 700 compounds based on the ATC-N class of pharmaceuticals (WHO, 2018), and were supplemented in the present study with other psychoactive compounds (e.g. caffeine, illicit drugs). From the 700 potential compounds, the present study focused on highly prescribed compounds based on Dutch prescription data (SI-2, (Zorginstituut Nederland, 2022), supplemented with commonly used compounds (e.g., caffeine, over-the-counter analgesics) and compounds that were understudied in literature, or had been shown to demonstrate a risk in surface waters (Davey et al., 2022). This resulted in a target list of 42 compounds (SI-1), which was shortened to 30 after method validation (see Method Validation supplementary, SI-5).

2.2: Materials

Amsterdam West WWTP was used for the samples in this study. It was built between 2003-2005 and is connected to 767,000 population equivalents and local industry at time of sampling. The WWTP uses primary sedimentation, activated sludge (modified University of Cape Town, mUCT) process, followed by a secondary sedimentation tank, and is attached to a combined sewage system (van Nieuwenhuijzen et al., 2009). A total of 7 effluent and 7 influent samples were analysed, taken by Waternet (Amsterdam water authorities) and supplied via KWR Water Research Institute. The samples were taken over 7 consecutive days between 18th and 24th

March 2021 (SI-3). The samples were 24 h composite samples and were collected using an autosampler that collected volume-proportional samples of 50 mL every 350 m³; this resulted in at least 300 subsamples per sample. The specific week was picked to be a representative 'normal' week as it fell outside holiday seasons and without specific events in the WWTP catchment area. A subsample of 250-300 mL of each sampling day, collected in HDPE bottles, was transported to the lab where the samples were stored at -20 °C within 24 hr of sampling until extraction. Before analysis, the samples were put in 4 °C to defrost overnight and extracted the next day.

The labelled and unlabelled standards used for both the method optimization and measurements were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Chemie (Schnellendorf, Germany) (See SI-4). All unlabelled standards were analytical grade Certified Reference Materials ($\geq 98\%$ purity). Stock solutions were prepared using MeOH and stored at -20 °C. Oasis HLB cartridges (6 cc, 150 mg) were purchased from Waters (Etten-Leur, the Netherlands). The solvents used for solid phase extraction (SPE), chromatographic separation and stock solutions were of LC-MS grade from Biosolve (Valkenswaard, the Netherlands), and ultra-pure water used for SPE, and separation was produced by a Milli-Q® Direct Water Purification System from Merck (Damstadt, Germany).

2.3: Solid Phase Extraction

Effluent samples were spiked with 1 µg/L of labelled internal standards and shaken at 90 rpm for 30 minutes. Prior to SPE, outlets, tubes, and adapters were cleaned with 10 mL of ultrapure water followed by 10 mL of MeOH to prevent cross-contamination between SPE batches. The SPE method was based on Asghar et al. (2018). Conditioning of the Oasis HLB cartridge (150 mg, 6cc) was done with 6 mL MeOH and 6 mL ultrapure water. After sample loading (50 mL, in duplicate), the cartridge was dried for 30 minutes under vacuum and washed with 6 mL of ultrapure water. Before elution, a 0.22 µm polypropylene syringe filter was placed in between the cartridge and SPE inlet. Elution was achieved with 2x5 mL MeOH under vacuum. The collected elution fractions were evaporated under a gentle nitrogen flow at 37°C to <1 mL and reconstituted to 1 mL in MeOH. Elution fractions were diluted 5 times with ultrapure water prior to analysis in order to better

match the mobile phase of the LC separation. A concentration factor of 10 was achieved with the SPE and evaporation method as described above.

For the influent samples, 5 mL of influent was diluted with 45 mL of ultrapure water, yielding 50 mL of diluted influent. These diluted samples were then extracted in the same manner as described for the effluent samples. The influent samples achieved a concentration factor of only 1 due to the initial dilution.

2.4: LC-HRMS method

Liquid chromatography of the samples was performed with an ultrahigh-performance LC system (Nexera 30 Schimadzu, Den Bosch, The Netherlands). The LC column used was an Acquity UPLC CSH C18 column (130 Å, 2.1 × 150 mm, 1.7 µm, Waters Corporation, Milford) kept at a temperature of 40 °C. The mobile phases consisted of ultrapure water (Milli-Q) with 0.05% acetic acid (A) and MeOH (B). The gradient started with a 7-minute equilibration at 10% B and gradually increased to 100% B in 10 minutes, held at 100% B for 5 minutes, and back to 10% B in 0.5 minutes, totalling 22.5 minutes. The flow rate was 0.3 mL/min and the injection volume 20 µL. For compounds above the linear quantification range, a second round of injections was performed with an injection volume of 5 µL.

The LC was coupled to a maXis 4G quadrupole time-of-flight HRMS (qToF/HRMS) upgraded with HD collision cell and ESI source (Bruker Daltonics, Leiderdorp, The Netherlands). ESI+ and ESI- were achieved in individual runs by acquiring HRMS1 spectra for 20-1,000 m/z with a resolving power of 30,000-60,000 at full width half maximum (FWHM), with a spray voltage of +3.5 kV and -3.5 kV for positive and negative modes respectively. The HRMS was calibrated prior to analysis of the samples and individual injections in both ESI+ and ESI- modes using a 2 mM sodium acetate solution in H₂O:MeOH (1:1, v:v) direct injection. Per-sample internal calibration was achieved using a 50 µM sodium acetate solution in H₂O:MeOH (1:1, v:v) infused with a 20 µl loop injection. Qualification of target compounds was based on the mass accuracy of full-scan HRMS spectra and MS/MS ions acquired in data-independent MS/MS mode (DIA), and their

retention time match with the calibration series (2.5). In total 32 psychopharmaceuticals passed the sensitivity and separation criteria (SI-5); for these SPE method validation was performed (see Method Validation Supplementary document & SI-8).

2.5: Qualification & Quantification Method

Qualification of psychopharmaceuticals was carried out with TASQ version 2021.0 316 (Bruker Daltonics, Leiderdorp, the Netherlands) using bbCID MS/MS data to find precursor (quantifier) and fragment (qualifier) ions matching existing spectra in Massbank (Horai et al., 2010). Some compounds did not use qualifier ions in the method due to poor fragmentation, or because the analyte had matching fragmentations with its labelled internal standard which interfered with qualification (SI-6).

During quantification, only the chromatograms with a retention time (RT) of >1 minute, RT tolerance of ± 0.3 minutes, mass tolerance of 0.002 Da, a detectable qualifier ion, mSigma of <100, and a peak intensity of >1000 were considered. Target chromatograms were compared to calibration and IS chromatograms to check if the automated integration was successful, and manually integrated if not. Calibration curves for quantification were calculated by analysing ultrapure water spiked with target compounds, and serially diluted to obtain 18 concentration levels for all target compounds (SI-7). The 18 solutions were further spiked to contain 10 $\mu\text{g/L}$ of IS. Concentration calibration was achieved using the calibration series in TASQ, with a minimum of 7 levels with a residual of <30% and a linear R^2 of >0.99. The calibration range was optimised per compound per analysis to obtain the lowest feasible LOD and the highest quantifiable concentration. Sample IS area was compared to calibration IS area to determine the per-sample recoveries and adjust for losses. Amphetamine, bupropion and phenacetin used IS of other comparable, but not identical, compounds, and are therefore considered as semi-quantified (SI-4). Further analyses were carried out in Microsoft Excel where blank concentrations were subtracted, duplicates averaged, and dilution factors were accounted for to give final sample concentrations (SI-11).

2.6: Removal Efficiency and Risk Analysis

Removal percentage is calculated per compound by taking the ratio of the effluent and influent on each of the days of sampling. Because there is a residence time of approximately 1 day in the Amsterdam West WWTP, the removal can be calculated for 6 days. If a compound was below the LOD or the LOQ in the effluent, then the LOD or LOQ was used to determine the minimum removal efficiency for that compound.

To contextualise removals, a preliminary risk assessment was performed on the effluent data, using readily available ecotoxicity data. Freshwater Predicted No Effect Concentration (PNEC) values were taken from the NORMAN PNEC database (SI-10, NORMAN, 2021). To show how risk can inform required removal efficiencies, risk quotients (RQs) were calculated per compound per day of effluent sampling using the measured effluent concentrations divided by the PNECs. From these data, risk boxplots were created showing the variation in risk over the 7 days. During this non-conservative preliminary risk analysis, no further assessment factors were applied, contrary to what is standardly done for deriving environmental quality standards. For compounds below the LOD or the LOQ in the effluent, the LOD or LOQ was used for the risk calculation.

With regards to the antidepressant citalopram, there are two stereoisomers in use in the Netherlands i.e. citalopram and escitalopram. The analytical method used does not distinguish the isomers and therefore the combined concentrations for both isomers are reported. To correct for this in the correlations and risk analysis, the prescriptions for citalopram and escitalopram were added together, and used the more conservative PNEC (escitalopram) for the risk analysis.

2.7: Correlations and Expected Load

To test the reliability of the gathered data, Pearson correlations were run with log-transformed Dutch prescription data from 2021 for the 26 compounds that were only prescribed and not sold over-the-counter, taken from GIPDatabank (SI-2, 12, (Zorginstituut Nederland, 2022). To

adjust for human metabolism, excretion fractions (EF) were taken from DrugBank (Wishart et al., 2018) or the European Medicines Agency (EMA, See SI-13) if not available on DrugBank, and median values were used if a range was presented. The EFs were multiplied with the Number of DDDs (Defined Daily Doses, i.e. prescription) and the DDD size (dose size, SI-2, (NIPH, 2024) to get the expected load (Equation 5, SI-12). This calculation was designed to test if the gathered data is in line with other literature (Davey et al., 2022; He et al., 2020; Oosterhuis et al., 2013; ter Laak et al., 2010).

$$\text{Expected Load} = \text{DDDs} \cdot \text{EF} \cdot \text{DDD size}$$

Equation 5: Calculation used for Expected Load in sewage system.

3: Results and Discussion

3.1: Wastewater Occurrence

3.1.1: Influent Occurrence

20 out of the 30 measurable compounds were detected in Amsterdam West influent above their LOQs, while paroxetine could be detected but not be quantified and 9 compounds could not be detected (below LOD, SI-9). Concentrations of all quantifiable psychopharmaceuticals ranged from 24.6 ng/L to 96 µg/L (SI-11). The relative standard deviation for inter-day differences was 35% on average, including compounds with some sampling days <LOQ. Thus, the daily variation for psychopharmaceuticals quantified in influent is fairly low, which is to be expected with the prescription instructions and consumption habits for this type of pharmaceuticals. Caffeine is mainly used recreationally, and amphetamine is known to be used illicitly and therefore may have had higher daily variations, however the relative inter-day standard deviations for these two compounds fall in line with the other compounds (SI-11).

Figure 13: Concentrations of the 20 quantifiable psychopharmaceuticals in Amsterdam West WWTP influent. The boxplots show the variation cross the 7 days tested (with exception for fluoxetine (2), phenacetin (2), and sertraline (5)), where the box and whiskers represent quartiles and the line inside the box represents the median.

Concentrations in the influent correlated with metabolism-adjusted prescription data (i.e. Expected Load, SI-12) from the same year $r(25) = 0.63$, $p = <0.05$ (SI-12). Mianserin did not have excretion data, and so could not be included in the correlation. These results are in line with previous literature on pharmaceuticals (Davey et al., 2022; He et al., 2020; Oosterhuis et al., 2013; ter Laak et al., 2010) and are indicative of the reliability of the data gathered. The three compounds with the highest concentrations were paracetamol (acetaminophen), caffeine, and ibuprofen, which are over-the-counter analgesics (paracetamol and ibuprofen) and a legal recreational stimulant. Because of how these compounds are consumed, these are not included in the correlation (SI-13).

3.1.2: Effluent Occurrence

16 out of the 30 measurable compounds were detected in the Amsterdam West effluent above their LOQs, with 8 compounds being below the LOD and 6 compounds detected but unquantifiable (SI-9). Concentrations in effluent ranged from 4 ng/L to 1.6 µg/L (SI-11). The relative standard deviations for inter-day differences were 34% on average. Compounds with some days reporting concentrations <LOQ have higher relative standard deviations. Rainfall might affect concentrations in this combined sewer system, however the weather in Amsterdam during the period of sampling was quite consistent (overcast, no precipitation, and daytime highs of 8-11°C) (Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute, 2023).

Figure 14: Concentrations of the 16 quantifiable psychopharmaceuticals detected above the LOQs in Amsterdam West WWTP effluent. The boxplots show the variation across the 7 days tested (with exception for pregabalin (6), topiramate (6), citalopram (6), quetiapine (5), clozapine (3), and amitriptyline (3)).

Effluent concentrations did not correlate with prescription data from the same year $r(25) = 0.26, p = 0.21$ (SI-12), as was expected due to different fate of the chemicals within the WWTP (see 3.2). Like the influent, highly used and over-the-counter compounds such as ibuprofen and caffeine showed high effluent concentrations, with the notable exception of paracetamol, which was below the LOD in effluent (SI-9). Gabapentin showed the highest median concentrations, explained by the high expected load (SI-12) in combination with limited WWTP removal efficiency (see 3.2).

3.2: Removal Efficiencies and Preliminary Risk Analysis

A total of 20 compounds had sufficient data for the removal efficiency to be calculated. All these compounds showed positive removal, except for lidocaine and lamotrigine that showed a negative removal (thus a higher concentration in the effluent compared to influent) on one to two days (Figure 15 and SI-11). Eight compounds (phenacetin, amphetamine, caffeine, clozapine, amitriptyline, levetiracetam, fluoxetine, and paracetamol) returned >99% removals.

Figure 15: Removal efficiencies (concentration ratio of effluent over influent, expressed as percentages) of the psychopharmaceuticals found in Amsterdam West WWTP ordered by increasing median removal. The boxplots show the variation in removal across the days tested, where the box and whiskers represent quartiles, and the line inside the box represents the median concentration.

16 compounds could be quantified in the effluent and could therefore be compared to PNECs to perform a preliminary risk assessment. 14 compounds were below the LOD or LOQ, but could still be compared to PNECs using these parameters. Sertraline and ibuprofen show a definitive risk (Figure 16), while clozapine, fluvoxamine, amitriptyline, caffeine, venlafaxine and citalopram show at least one day less than one order of magnitude away from demonstrating a risk (SI-10).

Figure 16: Risk quotient (RQ) boxplots for the 16 psychopharmaceuticals found in Amsterdam West WWTP effluent, and the 14 compounds below the LOD/LOQ represented by dashes, ordered by increasing median risk. The boxplots show the variation across the days, where the box and whiskers represent quartiles, and the line inside the box represents the median risk. An RQ of >1 (without further assessment factors) has been highlighted in red.

4: General Discussion

4.1: Compatibility to Literature

When comparing the concentrations found to literature databases, the current study generally reports significantly lower effluent concentrations, even when filtering only for the Netherlands (Eike et al., 2019; NORMAN, 2021; Rijkswaterstaat, 2021). Furthermore, while all of the 30 compounds searched for do appear in the European databases, 5 compounds (aripiprazole, phenacetin, phenytoin, pregabalin, and topiramate) have not been included in monitoring data or studies in the Netherlands to the best of the authors knowledge. This remains true when accounting also for surface water monitoring (Rijkswaterstaat, 2021, Table SI-13). Given the differences in factors such as individual WWTP removal and national prescription regimes, it is important to have local data when assessing risk, and so the present study helps to fill some of the local data gaps for the Netherlands.

4.2: Removal-Risk Pairing and PNEC robustness

The current study pairs WWTP removal efficiency to ecotoxicity in a preliminary risk assessment of the effluent concentration to contextualise removal efficiencies. Specifically, we show that compounds that do meet general chemical removal targets (Bourgin et al., 2018; STOWA, 2020; Svahn and Borg, 2024) can still produce a risk (e.g. sertraline and ibuprofen, Figure 16) while other compounds that do not meet the targets do not pose a risk. The approach further allows the deduction of the cause of these risks. For example, sertraline has the lowest PNEC, which produced the highest RQs (S10), indicating that it is the high ecotoxicity of this compound which contributes most to the risk. In the case of ibuprofen, it is a combination of its moderate ecotoxicity, and high load that produces the risk (S10, Figure 13).

The preliminary risk analysis used the lowest freshwater PNECs taken from the NORMAN Network (NORMAN, 2021), aiming to keep the risk assessment simple using readily available data. These PNECs contain a mixture of PNECs derived from both experimental data and modelled data, and use different assessment factors (SI-10, the present study did

not add any additional assessment factors). The NORMAN database allows for details per entry (yet often these are missing), such as if acute or chronic data was used, or what the exact endpoints were. Missing ecotoxicity data is known to be a major limitation in risk assessment for psychopharmaceuticals (Davey et al., 2022), and this extends to the NORMAN PNECs. By coupling removal to ecotoxicity better insights can be gained than looking solely at removal (see 4.3). However, more extensive ecotoxicity data and robust (chronic) PNECs could provide more accurate risk assessments, as would behavioural endpoints, which can be more sensitive than non-behavioural endpoints and are of specific interest for psychopharmaceuticals (Davey et al., 2022; Raman et al., 2024a; Schuijt et al., 2023).

4.3: Removal and Risks of Comparable Psychopharmaceuticals

Despite the high removal efficiency of ibuprofen, it still demonstrates the highest risk of all quantifiable compounds in this study with an RQ range of 15-25 (SI-10), presumably due to its high use volumes and moderate ecotoxicity (SI-9, 10). The risk derived from ibuprofen is a result of the approximately 3% of parent compound not removed (SI-11). While ibuprofen is also used as an anti-inflammatory drug, both paracetamol and ibuprofen can be used as over-the-counter analgesics, or painkillers. Both drugs can be used for mild treatment of similar pain-related conditions, and for many people can be used interchangeably (Drugs.com, 2023a, 2023b). Phenacetin, a related compound to paracetamol, showed a very high removal, and no risk. The results suggest that the use of aniline-derived analgesics (ATC N02BE) such as paracetamol and phenacetin instead of ibuprofen, when used as an analgesic, could reduce potential ecological risks. Considering paracetamol and ibuprofen are both over-the-counter drugs, such a substitution could be stimulated via public awareness campaigns. This is in line with suggestions for an awareness campaign via eco-labelling for over-the-counter products (OECD, 2019).

The SSRI antidepressants citalopram and sertraline potentially demonstrate a similar case, despite the limitations mentioned in 4.2. Citalopram (including escitalopram) showed a removal efficiency of 60-100%, while sertraline showed a range between 49-97%. Sertraline demonstrated a potential

risk while citalopram did not (Figure 16), even when using the more conservative PNEC for escitalopram. This is despite the fact that sertraline had the lowest concentration of all compounds quantified in the effluent (Figure 14), indicating that its risk comes from the high ecotoxicity of the compound (SI-10). Additionally, (es)citalopram and sertraline had similar amounts consumed in 2021 (2000 and 2300 kg respectively, SI-2) despite citalopram being the most prescribed psychopharmaceutical in the Netherlands in terms of DDDs, roughly double the amount for sertraline. The smaller difference in loads comes from the fact that the DDD size for sertraline is 50 mg, while citalopram is 20 mg, and escitalopram 10 mg. The lower dose sizes indicates that citalopram, and especially escitalopram are far more efficient treatments in terms of chemical used.

The recommendations by the OECD (OECD, 2019) indicate a number of use-orientated options to reduce pharmaceutical residues. As psychopharmaceuticals are often used to treat chronic mental health and nervous conditions, some of these options are either not applicable or difficult to achieve (e.g. reduction in incidence, or reduction in self-prescription). Yet, the comparison between (es)citalopram and sertraline this gives credence to some of the OECD suggestions, namely the optimisation of dosing when it can be assured that the quality of treatment to the patient remains the same.

4.4: Transformation Products

The current study did not quantify transformation products, i.e. human metabolites and transformation products formed in the sewer system, WWTP or environment, as this would require (labelled) analytical standards of a spectrum of potential metabolites which are not easily available. There are legitimate reasons for studying transformation products, especially since these compounds may be found in higher concentrations than their parent compounds and be biologically active and thus pose a risk (de Jongh et al., 2012; Maculewicz et al., 2022; ter Laak et al., 2014; Zhi et al., 2021). Using non-target/suspect screening (Helmus et al., 2022) to identify transformation products, followed by (semi-) quantification to identify potential risky compounds, and only

then followed by full quantification could be a potential risk-driven approach.

4.5: Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive Proposal and Advanced Treatments

The EU's proposal for an urban wastewater treatment directive (European Commission, 2022) proposes progressively more rigorous measures over time, starting from 2025 for WWTPs connected to over 100k population to include advanced treatment technologies. There are numerous options for advanced treatments (Angeles et al., 2019), and the proposal places the selection of the treatment type on the member state, including selection criteria, with some suggestions. A risk-based approach (Article 18), such as the one presented here, is presented as one such suggestion. The results from the current study clearly show the benefits of this risk-based approach, such as establishing the cause of the risk (high loads, high toxicity, etc.). Coupling toxicity to removal could be advantageous in fine-tuning removals when resources are limited, however concerns relating to ecotoxicity data would need to be addressed in order for these types of risk assessment to be considered robust.

5: Conclusions

This study developed an analytical method to quantify the occurrence of psychopharmaceuticals in Amsterdam West WWTP influent and effluent, in order to estimate the WWTP removal efficiency and conduct a preliminary risk analysis based on effluent concentrations to inform removal targets.

While some compounds showed >99% median removal, others varied between 24 to 98%. This shows that modern conventional WWTPs are currently not capable of effectively removing many psychopharmaceuticals, and two compounds (ibuprofen and sertraline) even demonstrated an ecological risk despite high removal. Furthermore, risks may be assessed as more severe when factoring in missing ecotoxicological data, such as sensitive behavioural endpoints, or even the lack of experimental data. In combination, these missing data may lead to even higher ecological risk than those estimated in this study. Therefore, it is important to investigate options of reducing the ecological risk of psychopharmaceuticals, such as intra-class substitutions and advanced WWTP treatments. With further study, it may be possible to integrate risk assessment into removal targets in policy in order to come to a toxic free environment.

Acknowledgements & Supplementary Information

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Chapter Four - Wastewater Remediation of Pharmaceuticals with Ozone and Granular Active Carbon: A Risk-Driven Approach

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Abstract

This study aimed to investigate the removal efficiency of (psycho)pharmaceuticals by ozonation and granular active carbon (GAC) in wastewater effluent, using risk as the metric for adequate removal instead of aqueous concentrations. Conventionally treated effluent was further treated with ozone or GAC until there was a 25% reduced UVA254 absorbance, to allow for a direct comparison of the two treatment types. Samples were analysed using Ultra High-Performance Liquid Chromatography–Quadrupole Time of Flight–High Resolution Mass Spectrometry (UHPLC-qTOF-HRMS), where 20 (psycho)pharmaceuticals were quantified, and their risk was assessed using Predicted No Effect Concentrations (PNECs). A further assessment was performed using Quantitative Structural Activity Relationships (QSARs) for both parent compounds and their Oxidation Transformation Products (OTPs) to compare the relative toxicity of new species being formed by the ozone treatment.

The total median removal efficiency across all compounds was $60\pm 3\%$ for ozone in terms of concentration, yielding a $73\pm 2\%$ reduction in terms of risk for the parent compounds, while the median removal efficiency for GAC is $57\pm 9\%$ as expressed in concentration, and $46\pm 11\%$ in terms of risk reduction. When factoring in the OTP toxicity, the median risk reduction for ozone flips to $-274\pm 124\%$, indicating that there may be an increase in risk during ozonation. Pearson correlations on molecular descriptors indicated that ozone removal most strongly correlated with the number of activated aromatic rings ($r = 0.65$), while for GAC the topological polar surface area correlated strongest with removal ($r = 0.54$), therefore indicating that ozone and GAC target different types of molecules. The study demonstrates the merits of a risk-driven approach over concentration-based removal targets in current legislation, but also highlighted some drawbacks, especially with regards to data gaps and model accuracies.

1: Introduction

Pharmaceuticals have become essential in modern medicine, contributing to increased physical and mental health, and to a higher standard of living for many people around the world (Kümmerer, 2010). Psychopharmaceuticals, defined by the World Health Organisation under the Anatomical Therapeutic Class of N (ATC-N, WHO Collaborating Centre for Drug Statistics Methodology, 2018), are a subclass of pharmaceuticals designed to treat medical conditions related to the nervous system, often by altering the neurochemistry of the human brain (Jozwiak-Bebenista and Nowak, 2014; Wrobel, 2007). A growing number of people use psychopharmaceuticals on a regular basis, fuelled by several factors such as growing and aging populations, a loss of social stigmas of the underlying diseases (e.g. depression), and a growing number of psychopharmaceuticals entering global markets (Bean et al., 2018; European Medicines Agency, 2021; Gao et al., 2013; Massey et al., 2018; Read et al., 2014; World Health Organization, 2011).

In surface waters, psychopharmaceuticals have been shown to be a unique class of contaminants by exerting both lethal and sub-lethal adverse effects on many aquatic species, which is due to the similar neurochemical architecture shared between humans and other non-target species (Edsinger and Dölen, 2018; Liebeskind et al., 2017). Importantly, the sub-lethal effects of psychopharmaceuticals can alter the behaviour of non-target organisms, leading to changes in feeding, social interactions, predator avoidance, and locomotion, amongst other effects (Brodin et al., 2014; Cerveny et al., 2020; Painter et al., 2009; Raman et al., 2024a, 2024b; Schultz et al., 2011; Valenti et al., 2012). These ecotoxicological effects have been demonstrated at environmentally relevant concentrations (Schultz et al., 2011), although an absence of effects has also been demonstrated (Versteegen et al., 2025). Despite large data gaps still hindering proper risk assessment, it is evident that the presence of psychopharmaceuticals can pose risks to the aquatic ecosystem (Davey et al., 2022; Kidd et al., 2024; Kisielius et al., 2023; Raman et al., 2024a; Spilsbury et al., 2024a).

Psychopharmaceuticals enter the aquatic environment through wastewater discharges due to insufficient removal by Wastewater Treatment Plants (WWTPs, Davey et al., 2025a; Hale et al., 2022; van Dijk et al., 2023). Since psychopharmaceuticals are often designed for chronic use due to the types of conditions they treat (e.g. depression), they tend to have long metabolic half-lives, ranging from days (e.g. carbamazepine) to weeks (e.g. fluoxetine) opposed to common pharmaceuticals with much shorter half-lives in the order of minutes to hours (Wishart et al., 2018), which in turn leads to lower biodegradation rates in traditional WWTPs (Nolte et al., 2020). Conventional Activated Sludge (CAS) WWTPs usually consist of a combination of a primary sedimentation step, aeration/activated sludge step, followed by a secondary sedimentation step. These WWTPs are mainly designed to remove nutrients and reduce biochemical oxygen demand and are reliant on adsorption to sludge and biodegradation to remove the bulk of micropollutants, which is why many psychopharmaceuticals still enter the aquatic environment (Choi et al., 2018; Davey et al., 2025a; Ferrando-Climent et al., 2012; Gurke et al., 2015). Removal efficiencies of many (psycho)pharmaceuticals by conventional treatment methods do not meet targets (Davey et al., 2025a), and some psychopharmaceuticals can demonstrate concentration-based removal efficiencies of less than 50% in modern WWTPs (Davey et al., 2025a; Gurke et al., 2015). While WWTP effluent is not the only contributing factor to occurrence of (psycho)pharmaceuticals in the environment, with intermittent sources including storm overflow, spillage, and dumping (OECD, 2019), it remains the primary and continuous source of (psycho)pharmaceuticals into the environment (Cunha et al., 2019, 2017; Delli Compagni et al., 2020; Gago-Ferrero et al., 2019; OECD, 2019; Wang et al., 2020).

Advanced treatments in WWTPs include at least one additional step after conventional CAS treatment, (Kosek et al., 2020; Logar et al., 2014; Rout et al., 2021) and have demonstrated significantly higher removals for many micropollutants when compared to conventional treatments (González et al., 2016), albeit with increases to the capital, operation, and maintenance costs of WWTPs (Logar et al., 2014; Tarpani and Azapagic, 2018). Advanced treatment is a broad term that can refer to multiple different treatment techniques, such as Advanced Oxidation Processes (AOPs), which

may use ozone or ultra-violet light (UV) in combination with H₂O₂ and other catalysts (Bourgin et al., 2018; Hübner et al., 2024; Miklos et al., 2018). Another example of advanced treatments are adsorption/biodegradation-based processes, such as sand filtration and active carbon (granular or powdered) (Altmann et al., 2016; Streicher et al., 2016; Svahn and Borg, 2024; Xing et al., 2008; Zhang et al., 2011). In addition, so-called nature-based solutions (NBS) may also be considered advanced treatments, which refer to techniques that utilise natural systems and biota, such as natural and constructed wetlands or algae, to bind and biodegrade the micropollutants, and try to reduce the capital and operational costs (Davey et al., 2025b; de Wilt et al., 2016; Lei et al., 2023; Maeng et al., 2010; Oruganti et al., 2022; Sossalla et al., 2021).

Unlike the adsorptive techniques, AOPs are known to produce by-products, known as Oxidative Transformation Products (OTPs), which can be toxic to aquatic ecosystems, and their potential formation may negate the environmental benefits from parent compound removal (Gulde et al., 2021; Helmus et al., 2025; Zilberman et al., 2023). In response, AOPs are generally only used if an additional biofilter is used afterwards, such as GAC or sand filtration. While analytical advances do allow for the semi-quantification of transformation products, including OTPs (Helmus et al., 2025), there is still a lack of data for OTPs, especially for individual OTPs (Jesus et al., 2022; Zilberman et al., 2023). Without accurate occurrence data or ecotoxicity data, risk assessment on individual OTPs remains a challenge, with most OTP toxicity studies focusing on mixture bioassays (Affek et al., 2020; Dantas et al., 2011; Jesus et al., 2022; Stalter et al., 2010; Völker et al., 2019; Yacouba et al., 2021; Zilberman et al., 2023).

However, while inaccurate and only used by some environmental risk assessors as a last resort (Belanger et al., 2021), and not by others (EMA, 2024), Quantitative Structural Activity Relationships (QSAR) models can be used to provide an estimation of the ecotoxicity of a compound provided the structure of the compound is known, and therefore provide a qualitative, preliminary risk assessment. This type of risk assessment would not be comparable to assessments used to derive environmental quality standards (EMA, 2024; Spilsbury

et al., 2024b; Wess, 2021), but would advance the scientific discussion on OTPs, specifically through the lens of prioritisation. This approach would also compliment other risk-based approaches to psychopharmaceutical remediation (Davey et al., 2025a).

In recent years, there has been a growing consensus for the need for advanced treatments to help to further remove micropollutants, including (psycho)pharmaceuticals, from wastewater effluent (Eggen et al., 2014; Pistocchi et al., 2022a; Svahn and Borg, 2024; van Dijk et al., 2023). The EU's revised urban wastewater treatment directive (European Commission, 2024) proposes progressively more rigorous measures over time, starting from 2025 for WWTPs that are connected to populations of over 150k to include advanced treatment technologies. The UWWTD also sets concentration-based removal targets of 80% for 12 guide substances once quaternary (advanced) treatment has been implemented. The UWWTD leaves room for a 'risk-based approach' to determine if advanced treatment is needed for smaller WWTPs in certain circumstances, such as an outlet into a sensitive ecosystem affecting sources for drinking water or into a system with low dilution. Discussions are ongoing outside the UWWTD regarding the removal targets, with risk-based removal targets seen as a viable option provided that enough high quality ecotoxicity data are available (European Commission, 2024; Kisielius et al., 2023) especially when compared to concentration-based removal targets (Bourgin et al., 2018; Eggen et al., 2014; STOWA, 2020; Svahn and Borg, 2024).

While studies have shown that both adsorptive and AOP methods can yield high removals for psychopharmaceuticals (Angeles et al., 2019; Bourgin et al., 2018; Guillossou et al., 2020; Kårelid et al., 2017; Miklos et al., 2018; Svahn and Borg, 2024), there have been concerns about the lack of comparability between different advanced treatment techniques due to inconsistent experimental approaches (Fischer et al., 2019; Hübner et al., 2024). Notably, removal efficiencies between adsorptive and oxidative methods may be quite different based on the specific physicochemical properties of the compounds (Guillossou et al., 2020; Zoumpouli et al., 2020), yet determining which advanced treatment is better placed to remove these

compounds become complex due to differing dosages used in those experiments (Altmann et al., 2016; de Wilt et al., 2018; Guillossou et al., 2020; Haro et al., 2021; Hübner et al., 2024; Kårelid et al., 2017; Miklos et al., 2018; Phan et al., 2022; Pistocchi et al., 2022a; Spilsbury et al., 2024b; Streicher et al., 2016; Völker et al., 2019; Xing et al., 2008; Zoumpouli et al., 2020). One method to harmonise the results to allow direct comparison of removals by different technologies is the UVA254 method developed by Altmann et al. (2016), which has been validated in recent lab- and pilot-scale ozone experiments (Macsek et al., 2025; Phan et al., 2022) and active carbon experiments (Streicher et al., 2016). Here, the UV absorbance at 254 nm is measured during treatment until there is predetermined drop in absorbance (e.g. 25%) correlating to a drop in micropollutant concentration. Direct comparison of advanced treatments is needed for better decision making around scaling to pilot setups, which has been hindered by the lack of homogeneity of experimental setups (Fischer et al., 2019; Hübner et al., 2024).

Given that psychopharmaceuticals have unique modes of action, their use is increasing, and current WWTP removals are sub-optimal, further investigation into advanced treatment techniques to reduce the impact of these compounds on the aquatic environment is imperative. As such, risk assessments can be used to evaluate environmental impact and can aid in the understanding of the impact of OTPs. Therefore, the present study aimed to test the risk-based removal efficiencies for psychopharmaceuticals for ozone and GAC as two commonly used advanced treatment methods. To this end, firstly a preliminary risk assessment as an indicator for successful remediation of psychopharmaceuticals was employed, and secondly a further risk analysis was performed on OTPs from ozonation using a simple mass balance approach coupled with ecotoxicity QSAR models.

2: Methods

2.1: Materials and Target List

The target list included 30 psychopharmaceuticals, following the method developed by (Davey et al., 2025a), which are all from the ATC-N class of pharmaceuticals. We complemented this list by adding 5 pharmaceuticals that are not considered psychopharmaceuticals (ATC-N), but are highly studied, to maximise comparability to literature data (SI-1, column K). The isotopically labelled and unlabelled internal standards (SI-1) used for both the method optimization and measurements were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Chemie (Schnelldorf, Germany). Stock solutions were prepared using MeOH and stored at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Oasis HLB cartridges (6 cc, 150 mg) were purchased from Waters (Etten-Leur, the Netherlands). The solvents used for solid phase extraction (SPE), chromatographic separation and stock solutions were of LC-MS grade from Biosolve (Valkenswaard, the Netherlands), and ultra-pure water used for SPE, and separation was produced by a Milli-Q® Direct Water Purification System from Merck (Damstadt, Germany).

2.2: Samples & Treatments

Ozone and GAC were chosen as advanced treatment types, since these are commonly applied (Kosek et al., 2020; Logar et al., 2014; Rout et al., 2021; van Dijk et al., 2023). Effluent samples were obtained from the Bennekom wastewater treatment plant (51.997205, 5.658341) on 02/08/2022 and 03/08/2022. The treatment plant uses a CAS setup and is connected to a population of 20,000 inhabitant equivalents (de Wilt et al., 2018) and has been used for other effluent polishing experiments (Lei et al., 2023). The ozone and GAC treatment of the effluent was carried out at the Netherlands Institute of Ecology (NIOO-KNAW, Wageningen, the Netherlands) on the same day as sampling. Two effluent batches of 1,200 L and 1,350 L were collected for further treatment with ozone and GAC respectively (sample names PreOZ and PreGAC). These batches were subsequently used in another study for long-term mesocosm experiments to study non-lethal food web effects of differently treated effluents, hence the large volumes.

The effluent batches were treated until there was a 25% reduction of UV absorbance at 254 nm (UVA254), which allowed a straightforward method for comparing removal efficiency of trace contaminants across different advanced treatment methods (Altmann et al., 2016; Stapf et al., 2016). A 25% reduction in UVA254 corresponds with an ozone dosage of approximately 0.2-0.5 g O₃/g DOC and a GAC dosage of approximately 4g/L and indicates average organic micropollutant removals of >80% based on previous experiments (Altmann et al., 2016; Macsek et al., 2025; Phan et al., 2022). The dissolved organic carbon (DOC) concentration of the wastewater before treatment was 10 mg/L.

Four effluent batches of 300 L were ozonated with an ozone generator with pure oxygen until UVA254 was reduced by 25% (37 minutes of exposure) after which the effluent batches treated with ozone were mixed. Granular activated carbon (Hydrffin AR 8 x 30 diameter, 0.8-1 mm) was used as sorption material in the GAC treatment. The GAC treatment was done in two batches, with one of the tanks filled with 450 L of wastewater and 1850 g of activated carbon, the second tank was filled with 900 L of wastewater and 3700 g of activated carbon, reflecting an estimated GAC dosage of 4.1 g/L. Again, the treatment with GAC was stopped when the UVA254 was reduced by 25%, (5 hours and 15 minutes of exposure). Directly after the treatment, the activated carbon particles were removed using a 0.425 mm filter, after which the effluent batches treated with GAC were homogenised by mixing. No additional (psycho)pharmaceuticals were added to the samples, and all analytes were already present in the effluent before treatment.

After treatment, 100 ml samples were collected in dark HDPE bottles (DS2185-0004, Thermo Scientific) using grab sampling. The samples from the Ozone treatment were taken from the untreated effluent before ("Pre-Ozone", 2 samples) and after ozonation ("Post-Ozone") from each batch (8 in total), while the samples from the GAC treatment were taken from the untreated effluent before ("Pre-GAC", 2 samples) and after ("Post-GAC") each batch (4 samples total), leading to 14 samples overall. All samples were stored at -20 °C and transported to the Institute for Biodiversity and Ecosystem Dynamics (IBED) at the University of Amsterdam

(the Netherlands) for further analysis. Prior to analyses, samples were thawed overnight in 4 °C before extraction in October 2023.

2.3: Solid Phase Extraction

The extraction method used in this study is detailed in Davey et al. (2025a). Briefly, after thawing, samples were spiked with labelled standards and shaken at 90 rpm for 30 minutes. Outlets, tubes, and adapters were cleaned with ultrapure water followed by methanol. Conditioning of the Oasis HLB cartridge (150 mg, 6cc) was done with 6 mL MeOH and 6 mL ultrapure water. After sample loading (50 mL, in duplicate), the cartridge was dried for 30 minutes under vacuum and washed with 6 mL of ultrapure water. Before elution, a 0.22 µm polypropylene syringe filter was placed in between the cartridge and SPE inlet. Elution was achieved with 2x5 mL methanol under vacuum. The collected elution fractions were evaporated under a gentle nitrogen flow at 37 °C to <1 mL and reconstituted to 1 mL in methanol for storage until analysis.

2.4: UHPLC-HRMS Method

The analytical method used here was the same as Davey et al. (2025a). Briefly, a LC system (Nexera 30 Shimadzu, Den Bosch, The Netherlands) was coupled to a maXis 4G quadrupole time-of-flight HRMS (qToF/HRMS) upgraded with HD collision cell and ESI source (Bruker Daltonics, Leiderdorp, The Netherlands). The LC column used was an Acquity UPLC CSH C18 column (130 Å, 2.1 × 150 mm, 1.7 µm, Waters Corporation, Milford) kept at a temperature of 40 °C. The mobile phases consisted of ultrapure water (Milli-Q) with 0.05% acetic acid (A) and MeOH (B). The gradient started with a 7-minute equilibration at 10% B and gradually increased to 100% B in 10 minutes, held at 100% B for 5 mins, and back to 10% B in 0.5 minutes, totalling 22.5 minutes. The flow rate was 0.3 mL/min and the injection volume 20 µL. For compounds above the linear quantification range, a second round of injections was performed with an injection volume of 5 µL. The samples were analysed in both positive and negative mode, acquiring HRMS1 spectra for 20-1,000 m/z with a resolving power of 30,000-60,000 at full width half maximum

(FWHM), with a spray voltage of +3.5 kV and -3.5 kV for positive and negative modes respectively.

Qualification and quantification of psychopharmaceuticals was carried out with TASQ version 2021.0 316 (Bruker Daltonics, Leiderdorp, the Netherlands). Qualification of target compounds was based on the mass accuracy of full-scan HRMS spectra and MS/MS ions acquired in data-independent MS/MS mode (DIA), and their retention time match with the calibration series.

During quantification, only chromatograms with a retention time (RT) of >1 minute, RT tolerance of ± 0.3 minutes, mass tolerance of 0.002 Da, detectable qualifier ion, mSigma of <100, and a peak intensity of >1000, were considered (See SI-1 for further details). Calibration curves for quantification were calculated by analysing ultrapure water spiked with target compounds and serially diluted to obtain 18 concentration levels. The 18 solutions were further spiked to contain 10 $\mu\text{g/L}$ of Internal Standard (IS). Concentration calibration was achieved using the calibration series in compared to calibration IS area to determine the per-sample recoveries and adjust for losses. For more information on the quantification method, see Davey et al. (2025a). The instrumental and methodological limits of detection and quantification (LoD/LoQ) can be found in SI-5, columns Z-AA.

2.5: Method Validation

The method for 30 selected psychopharmaceuticals was validated in a previous study (Davey et al. 2025a), while the method for an additional 5 pharmaceuticals was validated in the present study (SI-2). The method validation followed the same workflow as Davey et al. (2025a), where 5 sample types were made in order estimate the matrix effects and recovery efficiency for each of the 5 new pharmaceuticals. Only recoveries and matrix effects of between 60-140% were considered acceptable. The method validation results are reported in SI-2. Two compounds (caffeine and clonidine) were removed from further study due to contamination issues for caffeine and bad calibration results for clonidine (SI-3), thus the study included 33 compounds.

2.6: Removal Efficiencies and Preliminary Risk Analysis

After quantification, blank subtractions, and dilution adjustments, concentration-based removal efficiencies per compound were calculated using equation 6 for both advanced treatment methods (SI-4):

$$\text{Concentration Based Removal \%} = \frac{(C_{Pre} - C_{Post})}{C_{Pre}} * 100$$

Equation 6: Calculation for concentration-based removal efficiencies

Where C_{Pre} is the pre-treatment concentration, C_{Post} is the post-treatment concentration, and *Concentration Based Removal %* is the concentration-based removal expressed as a percentage.

A second removal calculation was also performed using the sum of the concentrations of all compounds per sample to allow direct comparison to risk-based removal (equation 7):

$$\text{Total Concentration Based Removal \%} = \frac{(\sum C_{Pre} - \sum C_{Post})}{\sum C_{Pre}} * 100$$

Equation 7: Calculation for the total concentration-based removal efficiencies

A preliminary risk analysis was performed to better understand the impact of the removal efficiencies by factoring the ecotoxicity of each compound to come to risk-based removal efficiencies. Risk quotients (RQs) were calculated per compound using Equation 8, based on the lowest available freshwater Predicted No Effect Concentration (PNEC) values taken from the NORMAN database (NORMAN, 2021).

$$RQ = \frac{C}{PNEC}$$

Equation 8: Calculation for Risk Quotients (RQs).

Where C is the concentration (both pre and post treatment), $PNEC$ is the predicted no effect concentration and RQ is the Risk Quotient.

Risk-based removal efficiencies for the treatments were then calculated in the same manner as total concentration-based removal efficiencies; however, using RQ instead of concentration (Equation 9, SI-5):

$$\text{Risk Based Removal \%} = \frac{(\sum RQ_{Pre} - \sum RQ_{Post})}{\sum RQ_{Pre}} * 100$$

Equation 9: Calculation for risk-based removal efficiencies

Where RQ_{Pre} is the pre-treatment Risk Quotient, RQ_{Post} is the post-treatment Risk Quotient, and *Risk Based Removal %* is the risk-based removal expressed as a percentage.

Risk-based removal can only be calculated for the sum of the RQs, since the risk-based removal percentage would be identical to the concentration-based removal if done on a compound by-compound basis. Around 66% of (psycho)pharmaceuticals demonstrate additive mixture effects (Kidd et al., 2024; Martin et al., 2021), thus the method of summing RQs for (psycho)pharmaceuticals has been argued for to bridge knowledge gaps (Backhaus, 2016).

While the PNECs sometimes contained assessment factors according to the source used (SI-5, column C) no further assessment factors or dilution factors were applied during the preliminary risk assessment, contrary to what is done for deriving environmental quality standards (Van Leeuwen et al., 1996). For compounds below Limit of Quantification (LOQ), or the Limit of Detection (LOD), the LOQ or LOD were used respectively for a worst-case risk calculation, which is then explicitly indicated in the results section.

2.7: Oxidation Transformation Product Risk Analysis

A literature search for expected oxidation transformation products (OTPs) from the ozone treatment was conducted for all parent compounds that returned a measurable concentration in the pre-treated effluent. The search was carried out in June 2024 using both Google Scholar and ScienceDirect using the search terms "<Compound Name>, Oxidation Transformation Product, OTP, Ozone, Pharmaceutical" (Alharbi et al., 2022; Borowska et al., 2016; Dantas et al., 2011; Gulde et al., 2021; Hamdi El Najjar et al., 2014; Henning et al., 2018; Kharel et al., 2022; Melin et al., 2021; Méndez-Arriaga et al., 2011; Nika et al., 2021; Shen et al., 2011; Sierra-Olea et al., 2023; Voigt et al., 2021; Yacouba et al., 2021; Yargeau and Danylo, 2015; Yu et al., 2017; Zilberman et al., 2023; Zucker et al., 2018).

The OECD Toolbox was used to generate ecotoxicity data for the OTPs found in literature (QSAR Toolbox Version 4.7, Schultz et al., 2018). Simplified Molecular-Input Line-Entry System (SMILES) or the chemical structure were used as input data for the QSAR toolbox (the SMILES for all OTPs are provided in SI-6). The lowest Chronic ecotoxicity Value (ChV) was taken from the QSARs for use as a PNEC. If the QSARs returned no ChV, or if the QSAR was outside of its applicability domain, then only an Effect Concentration (EC50) or a Lethal Concentration (LC50) was used with an assessment factor of 1000 to bring the EC50 or LC50 in line with the chronic ecotoxicity values. The QSAR PNECs were converted into molar PNECs to account for OTP mass differences, and the lowest OTP molar PNEC for each pharmaceutical (i.e. the most toxic OTP) was compared to molar PNEC of the parent to produce the toxicity difference between the parent compound and its most toxic TP (SI-6, column N). Using this relative worst-case toxicity factor of the OTP, a further risk assessment was performed to calculate the maximum risk possible if all removed parent compound would be transformed into the most toxic OTP as a worst-case scenario:

$$OTP Risk = \frac{QSAR_{parent}}{QSAR_{OTP}} * \Delta RQ$$

Equation 10: Calculation for the risk posed by Oxidation Transformation Products (OTPs) during ozonation.

Where: $QSAR_{parent}$ is the molar PNEC as predicted by the QSAR model for the parent, $QSAR_{OTP}$ is the molar PNEC as predicted by the QSAR model for the OTP, and ΔRQ is the change in RQ from the ozone treatment.

2.8: Statistical Analysis

Paired T-tests were performed comparing the concentrations before and after treatment for each treatment type to test if significant removal had occurred. Since the ozone and GAC treatment occurred on separate days (see 2.2), a Mann-Whitney U test was performed as an independent non-parametric test comparing the removals of each treatment type. Analysis was performed in Microsoft Excel (see SI-7). Pearson correlations were run comparing the removal percentages of both treatments against structural molecular descriptors obtained from Chemicalize (ChemAxon, 2024).

3: Results and Discussion

3.1: Concentrations and Concentration-Based Removal Efficiencies

Out of 33 target compounds 22 were detected in at least one sample, however clozapine and quetiapine returned unreliable results (SI-4), leaving the final of total quantified compounds as 20 out of 33. Concentrations range from 1 ng/l to 2.5 µg/l (SI-4). Hydrochlorothiazide, gabapentin, and pregabalin were the compounds with the highest concentrations, returning concentrations above 1 µg/l before treatment and remaining the highest concentrations after treatment. The effluent concentrations found in the present study are higher than in another recent Dutch study at a WWTP in Amsterdam (Davey et al., 2025a). For example, carbamazepine is 5 times higher in the present study, and pregabalin and lamotrigine are one order of magnitude higher. The results in Bennekom, however, are in line with European medians (See Table SI-14 in Davey et al, 2025a).

Figure 17 shows the concentration-based removal efficiencies for the 20 quantified compounds, where removals range from -128% to 97% (median $63 \pm 5\%$, $p < 0.05$) for ozone, and from -15% to 71% (median $54 \pm 9\%$, $p < 0.05$) for GAC. The Mann-Whitney U test showed a significant difference between the removals of the two treatment types ($p < 0.05$, $r = 0.37$, SI-07). Two compounds returned a higher median concentration after treatment and thus showed negative removal; these were topiramate with $-128 \pm 57\%$ in ozone and sertraline with $-15 \pm 8\%$ in GAC. For these compounds deconjugation cannot be an explanation for the negative removal, since neither of these compounds have conjugated metabolites (Wishart et al., 2018, 2006). Analytical artefacts due to the proximity to the LOQ of these two compounds may explain the negative removal. Large standard deviations in removals (Figure 17) of fluoxetine and amitriptyline, for example, are due to one or more of the samples being <LOQ, see SI-4 for full results.

Figure 17: Median concentration-based removal efficiencies for the 20 quantified compounds calculated for treatment by GAC (n=4) or ozone (n=8), with error bars presenting the standard deviation. Negative removals for Topiramate (ozone = -128%) and sertraline (GAC = -7%) are not shown in this figure.

The Pearson correlations indicated that for ozone, the number of activated aromatic rings correlated with better removal ($r = 0.65$), while the fraction of carbon atoms that are SP^3 -hybridised negatively correlated with removal the most ($r = -0.63$). This confirms that ozone is behaving as expected in this study, as the electrophilic ozone can attack the electron rich activated aromatic rings (e.g. diclofenac, carbamazepine, paracetamol, etc, Figure 17), while it struggles to attack SP^3 bonds, with compounds that lack aromatic rings and are SP^3 rich, such as gabapentin and pregabalin, showing the lowest removal efficiencies by ozone (SI-8). The correlations agree with the qualitative analysis by Zoumpouli et al. (2020), which identified reactive and non-reactive functional groups in ozone removal. For GAC, topological polar surface area correlated strongest with removal ($r = 0.54$), while $\log K_{ow}$ correlated the most negatively ($r = -0.46$). Again, this is in line with what can be expected for an absorptive material, with compounds with higher polar surface areas able to interact with the surface of the GAC, while compounds such as amitriptyline are non-polar and very lipophilic returning very low GAC removals (Figure 17). Since ozone favours electron-rich aromatics and GAC favours polar molecules, the two treatment types can target different compounds, as shown by the inverse of the Pearson correlation between the two treatment types across all the molecular descriptors (SI-8).

Making direct comparisons to removal efficiencies found in literature remains difficult, due a lack of standardisation in testing methodologies (Fischer et al., 2019; Hübner et al., 2024) and differences in dosages between studies (Altmann et al., 2016; de Wilt et al., 2018; Guillossou et al., 2020; Haro et al., 2021; Hübner et al., 2024; Kårelid et al., 2017; Miklos et al., 2018; Phan et al., 2022; Pistocchi et al., 2022a; Spilsbury et al., 2024b; Streicher et al., 2016; Völker et al., 2019; Xing et al., 2008; Zoumpouli et al., 2020). The dosage and exposure time used this study have been shown to produce removals of >80% for micropollutants in studies with dosages and exposure times (Altmann et al., 2016; Macsek et al., 2025; Phan et al., 2022). The results presented here for removal by ozonation are broadly in line with other literature. Similar removal rates to Bourgin et al. (2018) after ozone treatment were found for carbamazepine, diclofenac and sulfamethoxazole (>90% removal, SI-4), and compared to Spilsbury et al. (2024b) the present study had

significantly better ozone removal at a comparable dose of 0.35 g O₃ /g DOC. However, for other compounds, removal efficiencies were slightly lower than those of other lab-, or pilot-scale experiments (Bourgin et al., 2018; Kharel et al., 2020; van Dijk et al., 2023). For GAC, removal efficiencies found here were substantially lower than those reported in literature. This is likely due to the lower dose used in the present study compared to literature (Kårelid et al., 2017; van Dijk et al., 2023), as well as the lack of a biofilm in the present study. GAC is commonly implemented as a fixed bed adsorber with biofilm development that can provide additional biodegradation over longer operation (Kårelid et al., 2017). Here, virgin GAC was used as a purely adsorptive substrate, with the dosage and contact time being similar to other GAC studies (Haro et al., 2021; Xing et al., 2008). However, using Powdered Activated Carbon (PAC) to increase sorption surface area, or extending the operation of GAC to allow for a biofilm to form, incurring biodegradation potential may improve the removals presented here (Kårelid et al., 2017; Streicher et al., 2016; Svahn and Borg, 2024).

3.2: Risk Analysis

Ecotoxicological preliminary risks for the parent compounds were calculated for all 33 compounds present in the study (Figure 18, SI-5), since LOD and LOQ values were used as surrogates for the compounds that could not be quantified or detected, to present a worst-case scenario. Here, ibuprofen, diclofenac, and sertraline present a risk in the untreated effluent (RQs of 21, 13, and 1.3 respectively). Diclofenac, citalopram, amitriptyline, clozapine, carbamazepine, venlafaxine, sulfamethoxazole, aripiprazole, propranolol, and lamotrigine had RQs of over 0.1, meaning they were within 1 order of magnitude to a risk. Aripiprazole was within an order of magnitude to an RQ of 1 despite all measurements being below the LOQ, due to the small distance between the potentially toxic concentrations and the LOQ. The median RQs were 0.025, 0.013, 0.023, 0.014 for Pre-Ozone, Post-Ozone, Pre-GAC, and Post-GAC respectively.

Figure 18: Risk quotients for all 33 compounds in the study, for all 4 samples. The red line indicates where a risk is seen (i.e. $RQ > 1$) and the error bars indicate the standard deviation. Striped bars indicate that the risk assessment was based on the LOD or LOQ. Asterisks next to the names indicate the assessment factor used by the NORMAN database. * = 10, ** = 50, *** = 100, **** = 1000 (QSARS only), no asterisk indicates no assessment factor present.

The PNECs obtained from the NORMAN database originate from diverse sources. While many were from literature, 9 out of 30 were QSAR predicted, and the assessment factors used in the NORMAN database ranged from 0 to 1000 (SI-5). The use of the NORMAN PNECs was a pragmatic choice due to their availability, however the shortcomings of these PNECs has been discussed before (Davey et al., 2025a). The risk assessment performed here is illustrative and not designed to be compared to EMA style risk assessments, since the ecotoxicity data for those are generally lacking (Kisielius et al., 2023; Spilsbury et al., 2024a; Wess, 2021). For the mentioned highest risk compounds, the PNECs were based on literature data, and had assessment factors of only 10-50 applied (Figure 18, NORMAN, 2021).

3.3: OTP Toxicity and QSAR Data gap Filling

146 structures of known OTPs that might be formed by ozone treatment were obtained from literature for 17 of the 22 detected compounds (SI-6) (Alharbi et al., 2022; Borowska et al., 2016; Dantas et al., 2011; Gulde et al., 2021; Hamdi El Najjar et al., 2014; Henning et al., 2018; Kharel et al., 2022; Melin et al., 2021; Méndez-Arriaga et al., 2011; Nika et al., 2021; Shen et al., 2011; Sierra-Olea et al., 2023; Voigt et al., 2021; Yacouba et al., 2021; Yargeau and Danylo, 2015; Yu et al., 2017; Zilberman et al., 2023; Zucker et al., 2018). The number of OTPs per parent compound range from 4 to 30. Most of the OTPs returned ChVs, with only 18 OTPs returning an EC/LC50 value and requiring an assessment factor (SI-6). Based upon the QSAR calculations, the risk of most OTPs that could be produced by the ozone treatment is greater than the risk that was removed by it, where a total of 29 OTP structures returned ecotoxicity values lower than their parents, and thus more toxic. For diclofenac, sertraline, citalopram, propranolol, amitriptyline, sulfamethoxazole, carbamazepine, venlafaxine, hydrochlorothiazide, gabapentin, and paracetamol the possible contribution of the most toxic OTP to the toxicity of the effluent was higher than the toxicity by the parent compound that was removed (Figure 19, SI-6). In the case of paracetamol, the most toxic OTP was around 100 times more toxic than the parent compound on molar basis. As a result of the OTP analysis, citalopram, amitriptyline, carbamazepine, and hydrochlorothiazide went from no predicted risk based

only on the parent compound, to a predicted risk based on parent and OTP after ozonation (Figure 19).

Figure 19: Risk quotients of 17 detected parent compounds including a worst-case risk estimation of probable OTPs after ozonation. Error bars indicate standard deviation.

The formation of ecotoxic OTPs has been discussed in literature (Affek et al., 2020; Gulde et al., 2021; Zilberman et al., 2023), but the exact effects of individual OTPs in these studies are difficult to unravel due to the lack of OTP standards, and most studies on OTP toxicity being broad-scope bioassays on ozonated water (Affek et al., 2020). The analysis performed here attempted to bridge this gap by estimating the individual OTP toxicity using *in silico* methods and is broadly in agreement with literature that the formation of OTPs can be detrimental to the ecosystem without an additional treatment step to remove them. However, it should be reiterated that the actual concentrations of the OTPs were unknown, and thus the analysis performed and shown in Figure 4 should be seen as a worst-case scenario which may not reflect the real situation.

When assessing the risk of pharmaceuticals, many studies neglect transformation products for practical reasons (Davey et al., 2025a, 2022). The current lack of analytical standards leads to large uncertainties in quantification, and including analytes without standards is often advised against

(European Commission, 2002). Additionally, the lack of standards leads to a lack of ecotoxicity data for these transformation products. While the use of QSARs on the confirmed OTP structures provided data to fill gaps, there is still many missing data to accurately estimate the risk after ozonation. Firstly, there are probably more OTP structures than those reported in literature (Helmus et al., 2025), and there were some compounds with missing literature on OTP structures (SI-6). There are also the OTP structures of human metabolites of the psychopharmaceuticals, which were available only for some pharmaceuticals (Henning et al., 2018; Kharel et al., 2022; Nika et al., 2021; Sierra-Olea et al., 2023; Zucker et al., 2018), and which are not included here but could add to the risks. Secondly, there are some general limitations with the use of QSARs. Quality and performance of the models are highly dependent on the training dataset and thereby applicability domain (Aljallal et al., 2024). However, none of the QSARs used in the present study were outside the applicability domain. Toxicological mode of action is also a limitation for QSARs. Like the PNECs, behavioural endpoints are not covered in the QSARs, although they might be vital to understanding the ecological impact of psychopharmaceuticals (Burgoon et al., 2024; Raman et al., 2024a).

3.4: Risk-Based Removal Efficiencies

Comparing total concentration-based removal efficiencies to risk-based removal efficiencies when not factoring in OTP toxicity, the summed median concentration-based removal efficiency across all compounds was $60\pm 3\%$ for ozone yielding a $73\pm 2\%$ risk-based removal, while the summed median concentration-based removal efficiency for GAC is $57\pm 9\%$ and $46\pm 11\%$ in terms of risk reduction. When factoring in the worst-case OTP toxicity, the risk-based removal efficiency for ozone flips to $-274\pm 124\%$, indicating that there may be an increase in risk during ozonation. Thus, ozone is slightly better at removal of parent compounds in terms of mass, but due to the expected creation of OTPs the risk to the environment is potentially even increased after ozonation (SI-5).

The use of risk as a method of contextualising removal efficiencies is a novel approach (Davey et al., 2025a, 2025b;

Spilsbury et al., 2024b), as often toxicity is not factored into studies on removal efficiencies of treatment technologies. Additionally, policy goals are often expressed as removal efficiencies in terms of concentration and not in terms of risk (Bourgin et al., 2018; European Commission, 2024; STOWA, 2020; Svahn and Borg, 2024). However, the worst-case risk analysis in this work reflects a scenario where risk is evaluated in terms of PNECs for standard ecotoxicity test endpoints such as growth, reproduction, or mortality, as well as the known limitations of the PNECs which have been discussed before (Davey et al., 2025a). This includes the lack reflection of more complex interactions such as behavioural effects in available ecotoxicity studies, or ecosystem dynamics such as changes in food webs, for which effects can be non-monotonic (Raman et al., 2024a, 2024b). Availability of such data would increase the accuracy of the risk assessment but also add to the complexity of the assessment (Davey et al., 2022; Schuijt et al., 2021). Still, the risk-based evaluation of removal efficiencies by treatment technologies used in the current study has clear benefits over traditional concentration-based removal efficiencies, as it relates much better to the endpoint of a protected and healthy ecosystem. Such a risk-driven approach has been discussed as a model for policy makers but is not yet applied generally in policies (European Commission, 2024, 2022).

Despite the specified limitations, the present study demonstrates the value in using models to fill in for missing experimental ecotoxicity data, even if the results should be interpreted as more qualitative than quantitative. Ecotoxicity tests are costly, time consuming, and may provide a limited view on risks related to ecological functioning and have ethical questions attached to them. Modelling can negate some of these concerns and allow for far more compounds to be included in the analysis, elucidating potential risks. Combined with higher throughput laboratory methods, such as non-target screening tools with structure generation (Helmus et al., 2022), and novel semi-quantitative LCMS methods (Liigand et al., 2020), there is a potential for a high throughput risk assessment to be performed using new and existing LCMS occurrence data, or even modelled data (Zillien et al., 2024).

3.5: Implications for Wastewater Treatment

In this study, ozone outperformed GAC both in terms of concentration-based removal and in terms of risk-based removal (SI-5). However, the advantage of ozone may disappear due to the formation of toxic OTPs, which is also reflected in the literature (Affek et al., 2020; Gulde et al., 2021; Zilberman et al., 2023). The inverse of the Pearson correlations between the two treatment types across the molecular descriptors indicates that GAC works well on compounds which ozone does not (SI-8), which has also been shown in other studies (Kårelid et al., 2017). This is why in practice ozone and other AOPs are in tandem with an adsorptive technique such as GAC, PAC, or other biofiltration methods (Zilberman et al., 2023). This type of tandem setup is already used in many existing and pilot advanced treatment setups for especially drinking water treatment and to a lesser extent wastewater treatment (Heringa et al., 2011; Itzel et al., 2020, 2018; Kharel et al., 2021; Knopp et al., 2016; Völker et al., 2019). However, there are still arguments against the deployment of widespread advanced treatments, citing the upfront and running costs of advanced treatments. This argument is compounded by the lack of tertiary treatments (e.g. CAS) in large parts of Europe (van Dijk et al., 2023), which should be the priority in those regions. Some estimations indicate that advanced treatment costs can be up to two times the current operating costs of a WWTP, with GAC being more expensive than ozone to implement (Tarpani and Azapagic, 2018).

Lowering the operating costs of advanced treatments can lower the barrier to their adoption (Garrone et al., 2018), which may be possible by lowering dosages if it can be assured that the risks are sufficiently low, even when taking temporal variation of influent concentrations into account (Pistocchi et al., 2022b). Utilising risk-based removal, or other risk-based approaches, as have been discussed in the EU (European Commission, 2024), could provide a potential way to reduce the dose of advanced treatments. A potential workflow for reducing advanced treatment dosage could use the UVA₂₅₄ method alongside non-target and semi-quantitative methods used in tandem with OTP structure and toxicity prediction perform a preliminary risk assessment on OTPs (Helmus et al., 2025, 2022; Liigand et al., 2020; Wishart et al., 2022). If done

on a tandem ozone-GAC setup, the dosage of both ozone and GAC, as measured by UVA₂₅₄, could be raised or lowered based on predetermined risk thresholds of both parent compounds and OTP. This workflow could allow for a more dynamic system when compared to the current flat, percentage-based removal targets (European Commission, 2024).

However, major knowledge gaps would need to be addressed first, such as robust ecotoxicity data (Kisielius et al., 2023; Moermond et al., 2016), and concerns over the identity, quantity and toxicity of biological metabolites and OTPs of the psychopharmaceuticals. It may be possible to also use bioassays and effect-based studies as combined with effect directed analysis to aid in answering the question of ecotoxicity of OTPs after ozonation (Brack et al., 2016; Bröcker et al., 2022; Cheng et al., 2023; Dopp et al., 2021; Kienle et al., 2022; Richardson et al., 2007; Richardson and Ternes, 2014) with an alternative being broader mesocosm-style experiments (Grantham et al., 2012; Raman et al., 2024b).

4: Conclusions

The present study investigated a risk-driven approach to directly assess the environmental risk and removal efficiencies of two advanced wastewater treatment technologies on (psycho)pharmaceuticals, i.e. ozone and GAC. Ozone performed better in terms of both concentration-based removal and risk-based removal for parent compounds. When QSARs were utilised to fill ecotoxicity data gaps on OTPs in a worst-case scenario, the results give a strong indication that ozone produces toxic byproducts that not only negate the risk reduction but may even increase the toxicity of the ozonated effluent. Furthermore, analysis on molecular descriptors indicates that ozone and GAC can remove different, complementary groups of (psycho)pharmaceuticals. Combined with the concerns over OTP toxicity, a tandem ozone-GAC setups would therefore be recommended. Finally, the study demonstrates the merits of novel methodologies, namely the UVA₂₅₄ method for direct comparison of different treatment methods, and the risk-driven approach over flat concentration-based removal targets as a metric for removal. Future workflows should include semi-quantitative risk assessment for OTPs to further elucidate the potential risk of these transformation products.

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Chapter Five - Removal of Psychopharmaceuticals from WWTP Effluent by an Algae-Mussel Trophic Cascade: A Potential Nature-Based Solution?

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Abstract

Psychopharmaceuticals are an emerging group of hazardous contaminants that pose a risk to the aquatic environment. Yet, modern wastewater treatment plants (WWTP) do not remove them sufficiently to alleviate these risks. The present study aimed therefore to explore the effectiveness of an alternative nature-based tertiary treatment of WWTP effluent to remove psychopharmaceuticals. To this end, an algae-mussel trophic cascade setup was designed in which algae were grown in effluent over the course of 11 days and subsequently fed to mussels for a further 3 days. Removal of 30 psychopharmaceuticals for each of the treatments (algae, mussels, algae + mussels) was calculated relative to control samples, and removal efficiency was contextualised by performing an indicative risk assessment.

12 psychopharmaceuticals were quantified during the experiment, with 11 encountered in all treatments. The compounds fell into 3 categories: positive removal (citalopram, lamotrigine, and venlafaxine), negative removal (carbamazepine, gabapentin, and pregabalin), and no significant changes in concentration (amitriptyline, quetiapine, tramadol, fluvoxamine, lidocaine, and ibuprofen). Both positive and negative removal was largely driven by the presence of the algae rather than that of the mussels. Compounds with a low pK_a showed negative removal due to the algal growth induced rise in pH, which was not negated by the mussels at the end of the cascade. Ibuprofen was not removed by any treatment and was also the only compound that represented a substantial risk. The cumulative risks indicated that the algal-mussel cascade actually increased the risk due to the negative removal of compounds present in high concentrations such as carbamazepine. Pregabalin and gabapentin also increased in risk, but did, however, not significantly change the overall risk from the analysed compounds due to their low concentrations. Since the presently designed nature-based treatment could not negate risk, it is not suitable for the removal of psychopharmaceuticals.

1: Introduction

Psychopharmaceuticals are a unique category of emerging micropollutants, as they are designed to alter the neurochemistry of the human brain (Józwiak-Bebenista and Nowak, 2014; Wrobel, 2007). Due to the similarities between the nervous systems of humans and other animals (Edsinger and Dölen, 2018; Liebeskind et al., 2017), these drugs can also act on the nervous systems of non-target species, leading to changed species interactions, which may ultimately affect aquatic ecosystem functioning (Bláha et al., 2019; Davey et al., 2022; Hossain et al., 2021; Kubec et al., 2019; Parrott and Metcalfe, 2017; Schwarz et al., 2021; Sehonova et al., 2019, 2018). Psychopharmaceuticals include antidepressants, anxiolytics, antipsychotics, and illicit drugs, amongst others (Davey et al., 2022). These substances are commonly and increasingly used in modern society, but poorly removed from wastewater by conventional treatment steps at WWTPs (Choi et al., 2018; Davey et al., 2025a; Ferrando-Climent et al., 2012b; Gurke et al., 2015) leading to their frequent detection and increasing concentrations in WWTP effluent and receiving water bodies (Boogaerts et al., 2019; Castiglioni et al., 2021; Choi et al., 2018; Coppens et al., 2015; Ferrando-Climent et al., 2012b; Gago-Ferrero et al., 2020; González-Mariño et al., 2018; Gurke et al., 2015; Moreno-González et al., 2014; Ort et al., 2014; Sjerps et al., 2017; Wilkinson et al., 2022). Due to this insufficient removal, legislative concentration-based and risk-based targets are not being met (Davey et al., 2025a; European Commission, 2024; Gurke et al., 2015).

To enhance the removal of psychopharmaceuticals from wastewater, several advanced treatment options have been explored and proven efficient (Eggen et al., 2014; Svahn and Borg, 2024; van Dijk et al., 2023). Therefore, such advanced treatments are currently considered to be a necessity in many developed economies (van Dijk et al., 2023). Yet, the inclusion of advanced treatment processes, such as membranes, activated carbon, ozonation, and other advanced oxidation processes significantly increases the capital, operation, and maintenance costs of WWTPs by a factor of around 1.5-2.1 (Tarpani and Azapagic, 2018), which severely limits the options available for developing regions. Additionally, high energy consumption and CO₂ emissions could put advanced treatment implementation at odds with

other sustainability goals. Therefore, it is imperative to explore alternative and cost-effective treatment options that can achieve efficient psychopharmaceutical removal while minimizing the financial costs involved, allowing a global application.

Nature-based solutions (NBS) have emerged as a potential alternative to tertiary advanced treatments in modern WWTPs, and as an alternative for secondary treatments in older or non-existent WWTPs, offering numerous advantages in terms of efficiency, sustainability, and cost-effectiveness (Cross et al., 2021). NBS involve the utilisation of natural systems, such as constructed wetlands (Vassalle et al., 2023; Verlicchi and Zambello, 2014) or stabilisation ponds (Mahapatra et al., 2022), amongst others (Cross et al., 2021) to polish WWTP effluent. These systems harness the inherent capabilities of plants, animals, microbes, and natural materials to remove contaminants through various physical, chemical, and biological mechanisms. NBS have a range of additional advantages depending on the type of treatment implemented. These advantages can range from mimicking natural ecosystems in the case of constructed wetlands, which in turn promotes biodiversity by habitat creation, to acting as a carbon sink via the production of biomass (Cross et al., 2021). Consequently, the interest in NBS by stakeholders, including the European Commission, has been rising over recent years (Bauduceau et al., 2015). However, NBS encounter frequent challenges, including higher land use compared to conventional treatment, unstandardised designs, and regular maintenance including vegetation maintenance and sediment/sludge removal (Cross et al., 2021).

To circumvent some of the common challenges of larger NBS such as constructed wetlands, a more controlled and concise use of algae has been proposed. Algae have been used to remove nutrients (van der Meer et al., 2023), to provide oxygen for biotic and abiotic degradation processes (de Wilt et al., 2016; Liu et al., 2021), as well as a substrate for adsorption and subsequent sedimentation of micropollutants (Binelli et al., 2014) and heavy metals (Ajayan et al., 2015), albeit with some varying results (Binelli et al., 2014; Liu et al., 2021). However, the removal of sedimented algae can be a costly maintenance process, especially at larger scales (Gouveia et al., 2016). Yet, it is possible to reduce the

algal disposal costs by employing filter-feeders, such as mussels, to consume the algae (Binelli et al., 2014; van der Meer et al., 2023). Hence, an algal-mussel cascade could provide micropollutant removal at low costs, serving as a potential nature-based alternative to advanced effluent treatment.

Therefore, the present study aimed to design and test the effectiveness of a nature-based treatment to remove psychopharmaceuticals from WWTP effluent. The setup consisted of an algae-mussel trophic cascade in which algae were grown in effluent and subsequently fed to mussels. Comparing the concentrations of psychopharmaceuticals in the wastewater effluent at various stages, and in control samples, allowed the estimation of the removal efficiency of psychopharmaceuticals using this low-cost, low-tech NBS. We contextualised the obtained removal efficiencies by calculating the ecotoxicological risk of the remaining psychopharmaceutical concentrations in the wastewater (Davey et al., 2025a) by comparing these to available ecotoxicity data.

2: Materials & Methods

2.1: Materials

A 200 L aliquot of secondary treated effluent was collected from the WWTP of Rhenen (46,000 population equivalents, Remmerden, The Netherlands (51°58'27.6"N 5°31'55.6"E)), which was a conventional University of Cape Town (UCT) carrousel with an additional filtration step (100 µm). The selected psychopharmaceuticals for LCMS analysis consisted of 30 compounds (SI-1). Labelled and unlabelled standards were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Chemie (Schnelldorf, Germany). Stock solutions were prepared using MeOH and stored at -20 °C. Oasis HLB cartridges (6 cc, 150 mg) were purchased from Waters (Etten-Leur, the Netherlands). The solvents used for solid phase extraction (SPE), chromatographic separation and stock solutions were of LC-MS grade, obtained from Biosolve (Valkenswaard, the Netherlands). Ultra-pure water used for SPE and separation was produced by a Milli-Q® Direct Water Purification System from Merck (Damstadt, Germany).

2.2: Algae-mussel trophic cascade

A detailed outline of the algae-mussel cascade is published in van der Meer et al. (2023), as shown in Figure 20. In brief, the effluent was transported to the laboratory, where two 100 L aquaria were filled. Algae (*Tetradesmus obliquus*) were added to one aquarium under a light-dark cycle of 16h:8h, while the other served as a control and was kept in the dark by covering it in aluminium foil, preventing native algal growth (SI-8). After 11 days of algal growth, either 5 L of the algal effluent or 5 L of the control effluent were poured into 16 glass tanks each. Mussels (*Dreissena bugensis*) were added to 8 of the algae tanks and 8 of the control tanks, resulting in a full factorial 2x2 design with 8 replicates per treatment, consisting of: 1] Effluent with algae and mussels (AM); 2] Effluent with algae but without mussels (Algae Control, AC); 3] Effluent with mussels but without algae (EM); and 4] Effluent control (EC) without algae and without mussels. This setup allowed for the calculation of psychopharmaceutical removal by algae and mussels separately, as well as together, by comparing each treatment with the control.

The mussels were placed on a metal mesh suspended over a glass cup to maximise the mussel filtration efficiency. To control for glass adsorption of the compounds, glass cups were also added to the treatments without mussels. The mussels were allowed to filter for 3 days with intermittent stirring to re-suspend settled algae outside of the cup. Water samples of approximately 1 L were collected at each step of the experiment and stored at -20 °C until further analysis. This included the starting effluent (Figure 20 a1/a2), the effluent in the algae tank (Figure 20 b1) and control tank (Figure 20 b2) after 11 days, as well as samples of each experimental replicate after mussel filtration of 3 days (Figure 20 c1-c4).

Figure 20: Schematic overview of the experimental setup (taken from van der Meer et al. (van der Meer et al., 2023)). Algae grown in effluent (a1), and control effluent without algae (a2). End of the 11-day algae growth period (b1 and b2). Mussel filtration phase: effluent with algae and mussels (c1, ALGAE-MUSSEL, AM), effluent with algae but without mussels (c2, ALGAE-CONTROL, AC), effluent with mussels, but without algae (c3, EFFLUENT-MUSSELS EM), and effluent without mussels and without algae (c4, EFFLUENT-CONTROL, EC). P = aquarium pump.

2.3: Solid phase extraction of water samples

Sample extraction was performed according to Davey et al (2025a). Briefly, after thawing, samples were spiked with labelled standards and shaken at 90 rpm for 30 minutes. Outlets, tubes, and adapters were cleaned with ultrapure water followed by methanol. Conditioning of the Oasis HLB cartridges (150 mg, 6 cc) was done with 6 mL MeOH and 6 mL ultrapure water. After sample loading (50 mL, in duplicate), the cartridges were dried for 30 minutes under vacuum and washed with 6 mL of ultrapure water. Before elution, a 0.22 μm polypropylene syringe filter was placed in between the cartridges and SPE inlets. Elution was achieved with 2x5 mL methanol under vacuum. The collected elution fractions were evaporated under a gentle nitrogen flow at 37°C to < 1 mL and reconstituted to 1 mL in methanol and subsequently stored (-20 °C) until analysis.

2.4: UHPLC-HRMS analysis of psychopharmaceuticals

Psychopharmaceuticals were analysed according to Davey et al. (Davey et al., 2025a). Briefly, a LC system (Nexera 30 Shimadzu, Den Bosch, The Netherlands) was coupled to a maXis 4G quadrupole time-of-flight HRMS (qToF/HRMS) upgraded with a HD collision cell and ESI source (Bruker Daltonics, Leiderdorp, The Netherlands). The LC column used was an Acquity UPLC CSH C18 column (130 Å, 2.1 × 150 mm, 1.7 μm , Waters Corporation, Milford) kept at a temperature of 40 °C. The mobile phases consisted of ultrapure water (Milli-Q) with 0.05% acetic acid (A) and MeOH (B). The gradient started with a 7-minute equilibration at 10% B and gradually increased to 100% B in 10 minutes, held at 100% B for 5 minutes, and then brought back to 10% B in 0.5 minutes, totalling 22.5 minutes. The flow rate was 0.3 mL/min and the injection volume 20 μL . The samples were analysed in both positive and negative modes acquiring HRMS1 spectra for 20-1,000 m/z with a resolving power of 30,000-60,000 at full width half maximum (FWHM), with a spray voltage of +3.5 kV and -3.5 kV for positive and negative modes respectively.

Both qualification and quantification of target compounds was carried out with *TASQ* version 2021.0 316 (Bruker Daltonics, Leiderdorp, the Netherlands). Qualification was based on the mass accuracy of full-scan HRMS spectra

and MS/MS ions acquired in data-independent MS/MS mode (DIA), and on their retention time match with the calibration series. During quantification, only the chromatograms with a retention time (RT) of > 1 minute, RT tolerance of ± 0.3 minutes, mass tolerance of 0.002 Da, detectable qualifier ion, mSigma of < 100, and a peak intensity of > 1000 were considered (SI-1). Calibration curves for quantification were obtained by analysing ultrapure water spiked with target compounds, in serial dilutions to obtain 18 concentrations. The 18 calibration solutions were further spiked to contain 10 $\mu\text{g/L}$ of internal standard. Internal standards were also added to the samples to adjust for losses during SPE, which were calculated automatically in TASQ.

2.5: Removal efficiency, risk calculation, & statistics

Data analysis was carried out in Microsoft Excel. Procedural duplicates were averaged, blanks were subtracted, and data were corrected for dilution factors to obtain the concentrations of the pharmaceuticals in the samples. For each psychopharmaceutical, differences in concentration between starting aquaria ($n = 2$ tanks at the start of the experiment), EC, EM, AC, and AM samples (all $n = 8$) were tested using a non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test followed by a Dunn's Test (SI-6) using the *Real Statistics Resource Pack* Excel add-in (version 8.9.1, (Zaiontz, 2023)). Subsequently, removal of the psychopharmaceuticals by the different biological treatments was calculated by comparing the concentrations of the psychopharmaceuticals in the AM, AC, and EM treatments to those in the control samples (EC). Only the treatments that were statistically significantly different from the control (EC) were considered as having removed the pharmaceutical.

To contextualise the removal efficiencies of the psychopharmaceuticals by the organisms, an indicative risk assessment was performed. To this end Predicted No Effect Concentrations (PNEC) for freshwater were obtained from the NORMAN database (NORMAN, 2021, SI-2). The concentrations of the psychopharmaceuticals in each sample were divided by the corresponding PNECs to calculate the Risk Quotients (RQs) per compound, which were then plotted as boxplots. Cumulative risk was calculated by summing the RQs of all compounds per treatment.

Pearson correlations were performed on the removal results to evaluate which physicochemical parameters can explain the observed removals (SI-7). Since biodegradation and adsorption were expected to play the main role in removals, these parameters were selected for the correlations. To this end biodegradation half-lives were predicted using Episuite's BCFBAF module (US EPA, 2023), while pK_a values were obtained from PubChem (Kim et al., 2021), and solubility data at different pH levels was calculated using Chemicalize (ChemAxon, 2024). Ionisation was calculated using the measured pH during algal cultivation and the pK_a for each pharmaceutical using the following formula (SI-9):

$$\text{Ionisation \%} = \frac{1}{1 + 10^{i \cdot pK_a - pH}} * 100$$

Equation 11: Where i is the ionisation type, 1 for acidic, -1 for basic, pK_a is the acid dissociation constant for the individual compound, and pH is the negative log of the proton concentration in solution.

3: Results

3.1: Quantification of psychopharmaceuticals & removal percentages

A total of 27 out of the 30 compounds could be analysed and qualified (SI-3). Caffeine and clozapine were excluded from further analysis due to contamination issues and phenacetin was removed due to poor calibration. One sample (EC-h) had a bad injection, and was thus removed from the study, leaving 7 replicates for the EC results (SI-6). 12 compounds returned concentrations above the limit of quantification in at least one sample. Amitriptyline only returned concentrations in the starting samples, which was therefore excluded from the table on removal percentages (Table 7, SI-4), leaving 11 compounds that returned results in all treatments (Table 7).

Table 7: Mean removal (\pm sd, EC: $n = 7$, others: $n = 8$) defined as the relative difference in concentration compared to the control (EC) samples for the 11 compounds that returned results in all sample types. Kruskal-Wallis significance indicates if there was a significant difference between the treatments.

Psychopharmaceutical	Algae (%)	Mussels (%)	Algae & Mussels (%)	KW Significance
Citalopram	78.4 \pm 47	41.7 \pm 37	95.4 \pm 28	Yes
Lamotrigine	77.4 \pm 18	-40.1 \pm 16	41.1 \pm 29	Yes
Venlafaxine	25.6 \pm 22	-7.6 \pm 19	27.4 \pm 28	Yes
Quetiapine	-34.9 \pm 29	-14.9 \pm 35	4.6 \pm 30	No
Tramadol	9.7 \pm 25	-13 \pm 20	18.8 \pm 35	Yes
Fluvoxamine	-0.1 \pm 20	-19.9 \pm 11	-24.7 \pm 21	Yes
Lidocaine	-5 \pm 12	-8.5 \pm 13	0.2 \pm 19	No
Ibuprofen	-4.5 \pm 23	7.8 \pm 31	2.2 \pm 31	No
Carbamazepine	-78.9 \pm 30	-52.2 \pm 20	-132.4 \pm 40	Yes
Pregabalin	-469.6 \pm 36	-222.3 \pm 36	-448.6 \pm 34	Yes
Gabapentin	-598.7 \pm 25	-299.2 \pm 14	-572.5 \pm 14	Yes

Removal percentages ranged from -600% to 95%, with three compounds (citalopram, lamotrigine, and venlafaxine) exhibiting statistically significant removal by algae, mussels, or both (KW- $\chi^2 = 23.2 - 29.9$, $df = 5$, all p 's < 0.05). Two compounds (quetiapine and tramadol) showed significant decreases relative to the start (KW- $\chi^2 = 5.5 - 16.0$, $df = 5$, all p 's < 0.05), but no difference between treatments and control, fluvoxamine showed a significant increase relative to the start (KW- $\chi^2 = 19.0$, $df = 5$, $p < 0.05$), while another two compounds (ibuprofen and lidocaine) showed no significant changes in concentrations (KW- $\chi^2 = 5.0 - 6.1$, $df =$

5, all p 's = 0.3 – 0.31). Three compounds (carbamazepine, pregabalin, and gabapentin) showing statistically significant negative removal in the algae, mussels, or both (KW- χ^2 = 18.9 – 24.0, df = 5, all p 's < 0.05).

3.2: Concentrations of psychopharmaceuticals & corresponding indicative risks

The 12 compounds were split into three categories: positive removal (Figure 21), no significant changes in concentration (Figure 22), and negative removal (Figure 23). The results for risk showed that RQs were mostly well below 1 (SI-5), except for amitriptyline (Figure 22A, median 0.61 in start), carbamazepine (Figure 23A, median 0.36 in AM), and especially ibuprofen (Figure 23F, RQ > 100 in all samples).

Positive removal of citalopram, lamotrigine, and venlafaxine was driven by algal growth, with mussels mostly playing a non-significant role. For lamotrigine (Figure 21B), mussels appeared to hamper the removal by the algae, since the concentration in the AM sample was not significantly different from the control, while in the algae treatment it significantly differed from the control (SI-6). The RQs for these three compounds were well below 1 in both the starting conditions, and after all treatment types, demonstrating a lack of risk.

Figure 21: Combination boxplots showing both concentration and risk in each sample type for the three psychopharmaceuticals that showed a significant positive removal in at least one of the samples: Citalopram (A), Lamotrigine (B) and Venlafaxine (C). The start concentration is provided for context. An RQ > 1 indicates a risk. Statistical significance categories as identified by the Dunn's test are reported by the letters on the bottom, where a matching letter indicates no significant difference between samples. Structural formulae for the compounds have also been provided. Whiskers represent upper and lower quartiles, while the box represents middle upper and middle lower. The central line indicates the median value (EC: n = 7, others: n = 8).

Figure 22: Combination boxplots showing both concentration and risk in each sample type for the six psychopharmaceuticals that showed no significant changes in concentration in any of the samples: Amitriptyline (A), Quetiapine (B), Tramadol (C), Fluvoxamine (D), Lidocaine (E), and Ibuprofen (F). The start concentration is provided for context. An RQ > 1 indicates a risk. Statistical significance categories as identified by the Dunn's test are reported by the letters on the bottom, where a matching letter indicates no significant difference between samples. Structural formulae for the compounds have also been provided. Whiskers represent upper and lower quartiles, while the box represents middle upper and middle lower. The central line indicates the median value (EC: n = 7, others: n = 8).

The compounds for which no significant changes in concentration was observed fell into two categories, the compounds that did not show significant differences between the four treatments, but their concentrations were significantly different compared to the starting concentrations (amitriptyline, quetiapine, tramadol, and fluvoxamine Figures 22A-D), and the compounds that showed no significant changes in concentration over the entire experiment, including the start concentration (lidocaine and ibuprofen, Figures 22E & F). The amitriptyline concentrations in the four treatments were all below the LOQ. For quetiapine the concentration in the AM samples was significantly lower compared to the starting samples, but did not differ between the control and the other treatments. The tramadol and fluvoxamine concentrations also showed significant differences between the start and two treatments, lower in the case of tramadol, higher in the case of fluvoxamine, but again there were no differences between the treatments and the control. The RQ for amitriptyline was within 1 order of magnitude of 1, while the RQ of ibuprofen exceeded 1 by over 2 orders of magnitude, indicating a very high risk.

Figure 23: Combination boxplots showing both concentration and risk in each sample type for the three psychopharmaceuticals that showed a significant negative removal in at least one of the samples: Carbamazepine (A), Pregabalin (B), and Gabapentin (C). The start concentration is provided for context. An $RQ > 1$ indicates a risk. Statistical significance categories as identified by the Dunn's test are reported by the letters on the bottom, where a matching letter indicates no significant difference between samples. Structural formulae for the compounds have also been provided. Whiskers represent upper and lower quartiles, while the box represents middle upper and middle lower. The central line indicates the median value (EC: $n = 7$, others: $n = 8$).

Negative removal was observed for carbamazepine, gabapentin, and pregabalin, and was mostly significant in the algae containing treatments (AC and AM). While none of the compounds presented a risk, the RQ for carbamazepine was within 1 order of magnitude of 1 in all sample types. It should also be highlighted that the negative removal caused a net gain in risk for the three compounds in this category.

3.3: Cumulative risk

Figure 24: Cumulative risk (in median RQs) of compounds with statistically significant results (see Figures 21 & 23) in each of the treatments.

By adding the risks of all compounds for which significant changes in concentration were observed, either positive or negative, the change in risk due to the treatments was +30%, +24%, and +56% for EM, AC, and EM respectively, indicating that there was a net gain in risk from psychopharmaceuticals due to the presence of both algae and mussels, as well as in combination compared to the control samples. This is largely due to the statistically significant negative removal of carbamazepine (Figures 23a, 24). While the cumulative risk decreased between the start and the control, the addition of mussels or algae appear to negate the reduction in cumulative risk over time, while the combination of mussels and algae produced a higher risk than both the start and the control samples. When all compounds are considered together, then the cumulative risk is identical to the risk of ibuprofen, because this was several orders of magnitude higher than for the other compounds. As the

ibuprofen concentrations remained unchanged, so did the corresponding risk (SI-7).

3.4: Impacts of pH changes from Algae Cultivation on the Physicochemical Properties

Figure 25: Rise in pH of the Algae Cultivation tank (Red) and the ionisation % calculated from the pK_a for the compounds in Figures. 21-23. Amitriptyline is not shown as it fell below the LOQ in the control (Figure 21). Compounds are listed in order of decreasing pK_a in the respective groupings of acidic (blue) and basic (green). Note that the pH measurement on day 9 was anomalous and removed from this figure (SI-8).

During algae cultivation, the pH of the algae tank rose from 6.7 to 11, while the pH in the control tank rose to 8.9 (SI-8). The pK_a of most selected psychopharmaceuticals falls within these pH ranges (SI-7), meaning that many psychopharmaceuticals have undergone a change in ionisation during the algal growth phase of the experiment (Figure 25, SI-9). Broadly, acidic compounds became increasingly ionised (blue, Figure 25) while basic compounds became neutralised with rising pH (green, Figure 25). Carbamazepine, however, remained neutral and Ibuprofen only changed marginally (from 97% to 100% ionised) during the change in pH in the algae tank.

Figure 26: Removal in the AM treatment (Y-axis) and the log half-life multiplied by the change in log solubility between pH 7 and pH 11 (X-axis). Orange points indicate compounds increased in solubility during algal cultivation, while green points indicate compounds with a large (>-2) decrease in solubility. Points highlighted with a bold outline indicate compounds for which the biodegradation half-life was longer than one day.

The change in ionisation state led to a change in solubility of the psychopharmaceuticals, but the observed removal and change in aqueous solubility (ΔLogS) did not correlate significantly ($r=0.6$, $p=0.1$). Yet, when the change in solubility was paired with biodegradability (expressed as log half-life), a significant ($r=0.73$, $p<0.05$) positive correlation was observed, indicating that both solubility and biodegradability played a role in explaining the differences in removal of the psychopharmaceuticals (Figure 26, SI-7).

4: Discussion

4.1: Performance of the algae-mussel cascade

The results for the removal by the algae-mussel cascade were ambiguous, with three compounds showing positive removal, three compounds showing negative removal, and six compounds showing no significant changes in concentration. Differences in removal between different compounds is not uncommon for (psycho)pharmaceutical remediation (Couto et al., 2019). For the compounds that were removed by the setup, removal was driven by algal growth, rather than adsorption to mussels. Citalopram and lamotrigine showed better removal (95% in AM, 77 % in AC, respectively) than some conventional advanced treatments in recent studies, where ozone was reported to remove 63% and 56%, respectively, while GAC removed 58% and 61%, respectively, however most results for pharmaceutical removal using conventional advanced treatments are better (Bourgin et al., 2018; Kårelid et al., 2017; Kharel et al., 2020; Spilsbury et al., 2024b; van Dijk et al., 2023).

The negative removals in combination with the compounds for which no changes in concentration were observed drove the lack of risk reduction, with the bulk of the risk coming from ibuprofen (no significant removal) and carbamazepine (negative removal), which does give an indication that this setup is unsuited to remove these psychopharmaceuticals, and more engineered setups such as ozone or active carbon may be required to mitigate the risk of these compounds.

The mussels effectively consumed the algae (van der Meer et al., 2023), and did not significantly re-release the psychopharmaceuticals back into the water, indicating that the mussels worked as intended. The mussels themselves did not drive any removal of psychopharmaceuticals. While literature on pharmaceutical removal by mussels is scarce, direct mussel removal of pharmaceuticals has been reported with ambiguous results (Binelli et al., 2014).

4.2: Negative removal of psychopharmaceuticals

While the control pH was around 7 during the mussel phase of the experiment (SI-8), the algal culturing of 11 days caused the pH to rise from 7 to 11, which is higher than in other algal setups reported in literature (e.g. 8.6, Matamoros et al., 2016). Consequently, the solubility of pregabalin and gabapentin increased significantly during the algal culturing, owing to the carboxylic group and a lower pK_a than the other compounds, resulting in negative removal (SI-7). Ibuprofen also contains a carboxylic group and showed negative removal in the algae-only treatment, albeit not significant. Algal cell walls also contain carboxylic groups, amongst others, which bind with ions and similar groups in micropollutants, which is the driving force for heavy metal (Spain et al., 2021), and micropollutant removal (de Wilt et al., 2016; Kumar et al., 2023). These interactions have been shown to be disrupted by changes in pH (Dubey et al., 2023), since at high pH the carboxylic groups will become ionised both on the compound and on the cell wall, disrupting the hydrogen bonding between them and introducing electrostatic repulsion. The increase in concentration (i.e. negative removal) for some of the compounds thus suggests that at the start of the experiment they were mostly bound to suspended matter (abiotic organic particles, microorganisms, etc.), but were released again with the rise in pH, explaining the increase in concentration, and subsequent negative removal of these compounds. For carbamazepine the pK_a did not correspond to a change in ionisation, thus remaining neutral throughout the pH swing. However, the pH swing could affect the sorption properties of the algal cell walls, amongst other biota and suspended particles, resulting in a release of carbamazepine into the water phase with increasing pH (Dubey et al., 2023). Other explanations for the observed negative removal include product-to-parent transformation by deconjugation of metabolites (Verlicchi et al., 2012). However, for compounds such as gabapentin, metabolites are not formed (Henning et al., 2018), while others do not have conjugated versions (Wishart et al., 2018), indicating that this was not the case.

While other experimental algal removal studies adjusted the pH (de Wilt et al., 2016), the present study did not opt for this since this would not be in line with an NBS. Consequently, the present setup did not work for some of the

psychopharmaceuticals. However, use of substrates such as gravel or soil have been shown to buffer the pH in stabilisation ponds undergoing an algal bloom, without active pH adjustment (Jin et al., 2017). Moderating the pH via substrates or another method may lead to positive removals for the compounds that were not removed, or reported negative removal efficiencies (Mantovani et al., 2024), but this would need to be tested at scale.

4.3: Pros & cons of risk-based removal

To contextualise the removal of psychopharmaceuticals, the present study paired removal to ecotoxicity to derive indicative risks. While this has been used in recent studies (Davey et al., 2025a), it has some limitations, especially regarding the PNECs extracted from the NORMAN database (NORMAN, 2021). These PNECs contain a mixture of PNECs derived from both experimental data and modelled data, use different assessment factors, do not state if acute or chronic data was used, or what the exact endpoints of the tests were. Missing ecotoxicity data is known to be a major limitation in risk assessment for psychopharmaceuticals (Davey et al., 2022), and therefore the RQs produced in this paper need to be met with appropriate scepticism. Nonetheless, the use of the PNECs does allow to perform an indicative risk assessment to compare the (lack of) risk reduction within a single study.

The current study also did not quantify transformation products, as this would require (labelled) analytical standards of a spectrum of potential metabolites which are not easily available. There are legitimate reasons for studying transformation products, especially since these compounds may be found in higher concentrations than their parent compounds and be biologically active and thus pose a risk (de Jongh et al., 2012; Maculewicz et al., 2022; ter Laak et al., 2014; Zhi et al., 2021). A more comprehensive risk assessment should thus also include metabolites and transformation products from (psycho)pharmaceuticals, and factor in any potential mixture effects (Christensen et al., 2007; Parrott and Metcalfe, 2019; Spilsbury et al., 2024b).

4.4: Rhenen WWTP and demographics

The present study did not detect as many psychopharmaceuticals as anticipated, nor in as high concentrations as expected based on other recent studies in the Netherlands using the same analytical methodology (Davey et al., 2025a). While it was expected that compounds such as carbamazepine would be detected in higher concentrations (Davey et al., 2025a) or a higher number of SSRI antidepressants would be detected in line with Dutch prescription data (Davey et al., 2025a; Zorginstituut Nederland, 2022), this was not the case. Additionally, it was unexpected that ibuprofen returned very high concentrations compared to other recent Dutch studies (Davey et al., 2025a). This is also despite the fact that the setup of Rhenen WWTP is more rudimentary than more sizable WWTPs, such as the nearby Amsterdam West (van Nieuwenhuijzen et al., 2009). This could be explained by demographic differences, since the inhabitants of Rhenen are proportionally older than those in Amsterdam (CBS, 2024), and younger people and teenagers proportionally use more psychopharmaceuticals (Grover et al., 2019; Lee et al., 2024; Parker and Alshaarawy, 2023; Pellechi et al., 2023), while older people are more likely to use analgesics (Enthoven et al., 2014; Lehti et al., 2021). This demographic difference may explain the large differences in concentrations of Rhenen effluent when compared to other Dutch effluents (Davey et al., 2025a).

4.5: Future perspectives

The present study aimed to test the effectiveness of an algae-mussel cascade NBS in removing psychopharmaceuticals, specifically using risk-based removal as a metric for success. The present setup did, however, not achieve a reduction in risk, but an increase. The lack of any significant change in the ibuprofen concentration contributed the most to the overall risk, as ibuprofen carried the highest risk by multiple orders of magnitude, while carbamazepine contributed the most to the negative removal and increase in risk. The three compounds that did show positive removal and reductions in risk were not enough to negate the increase in risk caused by carbamazepine, nor made an impact on the risks from ibuprofen. Hence, the cascade did not remove

psychopharmaceuticals and therefore did not negate the associated risks.

Nonetheless, potential benefits of the cascade were shown. The cascade also does not require any additional chemicals and could be a sizable CO₂ sink at scale, bringing it in line with sustainable development goals and green chemistry principles (Horváth and Anastas, 2007; United Nations, 2015). Furthermore, both mussels and algae have been shown to remove other micropollutants, such as heavy metals and nutrients (Binelli et al., 2014; de Wilt et al., 2016; Kumar et al., 2023; Spain et al., 2021; van der Meer et al., 2023). Further studies are needed into the use of algae and mussels for the purpose of pollutant removal, since these organisms show promise for other substances (de Wilt et al., 2016; Kumar et al., 2023; Spain et al., 2021; van der Meer et al., 2023). It has been shown that different species of algae can remove micropollutants at different rates (Gouveia et al., 2016), which could indicate that there is room for improvement through organism selection. A different selection of mussels would impact the removal of both algae and micropollutants, since filtrations rates vary over species, and depend on environmental conditions such as phytoplankton concentration (Lüskow et al., 2018; Schulte, 1975), salinity (Riisgård et al., 2013), and temperature (Schulte, 1975), amongst other variables. In addition, designing a different nature-based bioreactor containing sediments and other organisms, might be able to buffer the rise of pH stemming from algal growth and activity. These potential changes to the cascade setup might also mitigate negative effects on removal of the tested psychopharmaceuticals, while keeping the setup in line with NBS goals and bringing the cascade more in line with constructed wetlands (Jin et al., 2017; Mantovani et al., 2024).

5: Conclusions

The present NBS for psychopharmaceutical removal using an algal-mussel cascade did not result in a net reduction in risk. pH increase due to algal growth was suspected to cause negative removals of some psychopharmaceuticals due to the changes in solubility, which resulted in an increase in risk. If the pH increase could be buffered by using substrates, then it may be possible to alleviate the negative removal, or even turn these into positive removal. The cumulative risks indicated that the algal-mussel cascade actually increased the risk due to the negative removal of certain psychopharmaceuticals. Since the presently designed nature-based treatment could not negate risk, it is not suitable for the removal of psychopharmaceuticals.

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Chapter Six – Synthesis

Part 1: Utilising Risk in Tandem with Occurrence and Removal

The present thesis aimed to assess the risk, removal, and remediation of psychopharmaceuticals in the aquatic environment. It was argued that these three facets should be addressed together in a more holistic, integrated approach than what is typically done when assessing micropollutant risks in the environment. To this end, risk to the aquatic environment was assessed in tandem with occurrence and removal, which allowed removal to be discussed in the context of risk reduction, or risk-based removal. The thesis addressed five objectives which elucidated new findings (Figure 27):

1. To identify psychopharmaceuticals that represent a high risk for the aquatic environment
2. To define for which psychopharmaceuticals missing occurrence and ecotoxicity data hamper environmental risk assessment
3. To determine occurrence, mass-based, and risk-based removal of psychopharmaceuticals in a modern conventional WWTP
4. To determine occurrence, mass-based and risk-based removal of psychopharmaceuticals by common advanced treatment techniques
5. To assess the effectiveness of an alternative nature-based treatment technique for risk-based removal of psychopharmaceuticals

Figure 27: Overview of the empirical chapters of the present thesis and their key findings.

Possible Hidden Risks Were Not Found, but May Still be Present

By using large datasets over a large timeframe, and across the entire European continent, Chapter 2 identified to the best of our knowledge all risk-carrying psychopharmaceuticals while avoiding biases such as regional and temporal prescription differences or legal status. The study successfully addressed the first two objectives by highlighting that over a quarter of compounds with sufficient data carried risk, and for almost 90% of the compounds data availability was too limited to perform any kind of risk assessment.

The results from Chapter 2 also hinted at possible hidden risks of compounds for which little or no data were available. Psychopharmaceuticals belonging to the same family and designed to treat the same medical conditions carried very different risks, which is at least partly explained by the lack of data for many individual psychopharmaceuticals. The SSRI fluoxetine, for example, was identified as a compound carrying risk in multiple analyses based on good data quality, while in contrast sertraline, another SSRI, did not appear to present a risk despite lower data quality than fluoxetine. It was not clear why exactly the highly studied compounds were associated with higher risks. One possible

explanation is that the risky compounds received more attention in the ecotoxicity literature due to their higher profile, leading to ever lower effect concentrations over time. As these higher profile compounds are better studied, their risk increases, and they receive more attention, resulting in a feedback loop. Another explanation could simply be that that understudied compounds may carry hidden risks, and that psychopharmaceuticals may be riskier than our current data indicate, for example by lacking behavioural ecotoxicity data. Hence, the research prioritisation that came from this study included many compounds with little or no data.

Chapter 3 took the prioritisation from Chapter 2 into account, and an analytical method was developed for a selection of psychopharmaceuticals based on high prescription, high risk, and/or little data. The LCMS and SPE methods developed during this study were robust, and successfully covered most of the selected compounds, and were able to cover an additional five compounds added in Chapter 5, without any alterations. However, the methods were not able to cover all compounds on the initial target list generated from Chapter 2. These analytical challenges point to one of the possible reasons why specific compounds remained understudied or totally unstudied in the scientific literature.

For 42 of the initial 50 compounds selected for screening, internal standards for measurement were available, two failed the SPE validation, six performed poorly in the LC, and four were not detectable by the MS at all. While this study was able to add more occurrence and removal data for several understudied compounds, and five compounds (aripiprazole, phenacetin, phenytoin, pregabalin, and topiramate) were measured for the first time in the Netherlands, none of the understudied compounds carried risks. From an environmental standpoint, these are encouraging results, but it was not feasible to meet the ambitions to screen the initial 50 compounds. The environmental risks associated with the 20 compounds that could not be measured in this thesis remain mostly unknown, with highly prescribed compounds such as betahistine having never been measured anywhere according to the scientific literature.

Specific analytical methods targeting a smaller number of compounds may need to be developed for some of the trickier compounds which can be missed when using more generalised analytical methods, such as those developed in Chapter 3. Furthermore, Chapters 2 and 3 acknowledged the lack of analytical methods and data on metabolites and other transformation products, which may be biologically active or even more toxic than the parent compounds. Hence, more work will need to be done in the future to assess the potential hidden risks associated with understudied compounds.

Calculating Risk-Based Removal Efficiencies Elucidated Hidden Challenges

The present thesis showed the benefits of risk-based removal over concentration-based removal to evaluate wastewater treatment efficiency, which allowed for better comparisons between the different wastewaters, different mixtures of psychopharmaceuticals, and different treatment techniques, despite the risk assessment methods' limitations. By pairing removal efficiencies to ecotoxicity in a preliminary risk assessment for six treatment types (Figure 28), Chapters 3, 4, and 5 demonstrated that generalised, flat percentage, concentration-based removal targets for a defined list of monitoring chemicals are not sufficient to protect the aquatic environment (e.g. 70%, STOWA, 2020, or 80%, Bourgin et al., 2018; Svahn and Borg, 2024). Yet, these percentage removal rates for a predefined list of chemicals are in use in the current guidelines for water managers (e.g. STOWA, 2020). For example, Chapter 3 found that 97% of ibuprofen was removed by a conventional UCT WWTP, but the remaining 3% represented a concentration with a median risk quotient of 22, which still represents a high risk to the environment due to the general high usage of ibuprofen by the population of Amsterdam. Similarly, sertraline represented a high risk despite a high (81%) removal, due to its high ecotoxicity, since it had the most stringent PNEC of all analysed psychopharmaceuticals. Moreover, Chapter 4 showed that despite the application of advanced treatments (ozone or GAC) on top of the traditional treatment at the Bennekom WWTP, the risks of these two compounds persisted for the same reasons. Focusing only on concentration-based removal targets, as currently mandated in legislation for water managers (European Commission, 2024; STOWA, 2020),

would have completely missed these risks. Hence, this thesis highly recommends the use of risk-based removal efficiencies to better evaluate the performance of removal techniques.

Figure 28²: (Concentration-Based) Removal efficiencies and Risk-Based removal efficiencies for all six treatment types covered by this thesis. From left to right: University of Cape Town (Operational Traditional treatment type in Amsterdam), Mussels, Algae, (Algae to Mussel) Cascade, Ozone, Granulated Active Carbon.

The European Union’s proposal for an urban wastewater treatment directive (European Commission, 2022), discussed in Chapter 3, was adopted in November 2024 (European Commission, 2024). This legislation still suggests classical 80% concentration-based removal targets for 12 guide substances in quaternary (advanced) treatment plants. However, article 18 of the directive does state that “*Member States have the obligation to assess the risks caused by urban wastewater discharges to the environment and human health, and, where necessary, take additional measures on top of this Directive’s minimum requirements to address these risks.*” This is significant, as it does show movement in the direction of risk-based removal targets, albeit not a full adoption of them, which would be encouraged by the findings of the present thesis.

² The UCT treatment in Chapter 2 is designed to remove pollutants from influent, while all other treatment types were performed on already treated effluent. In this sense, the UCT treatment already was removing much of the ‘low-hanging fruit’, thus appears to perform better than the other treatments. Refer to Chapters 4 & 5 for discussions on the other treatment types.

This thesis clearly showed the benefits of a risk-based approach, such as establishing the cause of the risk, which could either be high loads, low removal, high ecotoxicity, or a combination. Coupling ecotoxicity with removal could be advantageous in fine-tuning removal techniques and prioritising compounds when resources are limited. However, risk-based removal has multiple drawbacks, which derive from the quality and diversity of the available ecotoxicity data, which should be addressed first before these types of risk assessment can be considered robust for those compounds with insufficient ecotoxicity data.

Ecotoxicology Needs to Catch up to Environmental Chemistry

Chapter 2 serves both as a continent-wide risk assessment using measured data, and an indication of the lack of data for specific psychopharmaceuticals. One of the main conclusions was that ecotoxicity data is most lacking, since for only 15% of the psychopharmaceuticals had at least one effect concentration available. Consequently, for 85% of all psychopharmaceuticals, no ecotoxicity data is available at all, which is concerning. This finding agrees with Gunnarsson et al. (19%, 2019), Spilsbury et al. (2%³, 2024b), and the OECD report on pharmaceuticals in the environment (12%, 2019). Moreover, even this small amount of available data may be criticised, like lacking chronic data for example (Spilsbury et al., 2024b). By trying to maximise available data, Chapter 2 converted all data to either chronic NOEC values or acute EC₅₀, which, as pointed out by a fair critique on Chapter 2 by Spilsbury et al. (2024b), can lead to uncertainties.

Kisielius et al. (2023) expressed a similar viewpoint regarding ecotoxicity data. They specifically argued that using PNECs as targets for the maximum tolerable concentration for a WWTP before advanced treatments are considered, which functionally is the same as risk-based removal targets, is problematic. This is not because of the methodology, but because PNECs are surrounded by uncertainty, and may be unreliable or unavailable. Moreover, as discussed in Chapter 2, only 13% of ecotoxicity data cover behavioural endpoints,

³ Spilsbury et al. (2024b) calculated EMA-style PNECs, and only considered high quality empirical data, hence the percentage from his paper is much lower than this thesis, or the other two papers referenced.

which are typically more sensitive and by far more relevant for psychopharmaceuticals than other endpoints. While Chapter 2 used all available ecotoxicity data for risk assessment, Chapters 3, 4 and 5 used existing PNECs because ecotoxicity was not the primary focus of those chapters. Due to the uncertainties surrounding the PNECs, these chapters all discussed why the PNECs were problematic, a discussion that would not be necessary if robust PNECs were available.

The persisting lack of ecotoxicity data coincides with large advancements in the field of analytical environmental chemistry. Non-target analyses are becoming more common, with the potential of semi-quantitative methods to address some of the limitations regarding unmeasured compounds and transformation products discussed in Chapters 2, 3 and 4 (Helmus et al., 2025, 2022). More chemicals are coming to the market (Z. Wang et al., 2020), all with potential metabolites and (oxidative) transformation products associated with them. This means that the number of quantified and semi-quantified contaminants is increasing at an unprecedented rate. The plethora of newly identified compounds all lack ecotoxicity data to perform further risk assessments (Kisielius et al., 2023), and there is a challenge for the field of ecotoxicology to keep up with this growth. This is further compounded when assessing the lack of data from a regulatory standpoint, where there are stringent criteria for deriving PNECs for environmental quality standards (Moermond et al., 2016; Wess, 2021). As stated by Spilsbury et al. (2024b) "*Empirical data, while in relatively limited supply, remains the gold standard for Environmental Risk Assessment*". In the current situation, it appears that we will not see the "gold standard" of ecotoxicity data for many compounds anytime soon.

In silico Risk Assessment and Prioritisation

Without high quality empirical data, like those used to derive environmental quality standards (Moermond et al., 2016; Spilsbury et al., 2024a; Wess, 2021), other routes to reliable risk assessments need to be assessed and discussed, if ecotoxicology is to catch up with the plethora of data generated by the analytical chemistry laboratories. One of the main reasons for the deviating progress between ecotoxicology and analytical environmental chemistry is that ecotoxicity data is neither quick nor cheap to produce (Mittal

et al., 2022), and experimental approaches are associated with ethical constraints, especially for vertebrates (Coors et al., 2023; Walker, 2008). Therefore, the use of *in silico* models, such as the QSARs used in Chapter 4 (Schultz et al., 2018), could be employed to fill the ecotoxicity data gaps, but these techniques still involve substantial uncertainties and are not used in regulatory contexts without large assessment factors, such as in the US (Belanger et al., 2021), and are no longer used in the EU for the purposes of deriving PNECs (EMA, 2024). Similarly, read-across is also considered unreliable, and is not used to derive PNECs (EMA, 2024; Huggett et al., 2004, 2003; Nallani et al., 2016).

However, this is not to say that *in silico* toxicity models cannot help in bridging the gap, especially considering recent advancements in *in silico* toxicity modelling coupled with semi-quantitative studies (Samanipour et al., 2023; Turkina et al., 2025). Prioritisation of (psycho)pharmaceuticals based on potential hazard could be an effective strategy to better allocate resources to ecotoxicity testing (Berninger et al., 2016; Boxall et al., 2012; Samanipour et al., 2023; Turkina et al., 2025), and large consortia such as PREMIER are seeking to use *in silico* and read-across tools for the prioritisation of *in vitro* ecotoxicity testing as a remedy for the ecotoxicity data gap (PREMIER, 2020).

Part 2: Non-Treatment Solutions May be Necessary

While Chapter 2 tried to establish the magnitude of psychopharmaceutical pollution in the aquatic environment by estimating risks and identifying data gaps, Chapters 3, 4, and 5 identified if wastewater treatment techniques can remedy the risks that these psychopharmaceuticals represent (Chapter 3), and which potential future wastewater treatment options are available to further advance remediation (Chapters 4 & 5). The results of these chapters demonstrated that the risks of psychopharmaceuticals are not sufficiently addressed by the currently employed treatment techniques, and future treatments have significant challenges associated with them.

However, this thesis only addressed the possibilities to combat the risk associated with psychopharmaceuticals already being consumed and discharged into the environment. Alternatively, adjustments may be made in the other parts of the psychopharmaceutical lifecycle in order to reduce the risks for the aquatic environment. Moermond and de Rooy (2022) described the Dutch chain approach to involve stakeholders to provide solutions to reduce (psycho)pharmaceutical risks in the water cycle in three distinct clusters: 1) development and authorisation, 2) prescription and use, and 3) waste and sewage treatment. While cluster three is explored in-depth in this thesis, 1 and 2 are gaining attention as potential alternative ways to reduce the risks of pharmaceuticals in the environment. Two specific approaches gaining interest are Green Pharmacy (Cluster 1) and Prescription Changes (Cluster 2).

Green Pharmacy as a Future Solution?

Green Pharmacy describes the field of (re)developing pharmaceuticals to reduce the risk after use in the environment by designing compounds that are better (bio)degraded, better sorbed to WWTP sludge, and/or less ecotoxic (Puhlmann et al., 2021). A relatively new concept, grown from the conceptions of green chemistry and 'benign-by-design', is the development of novel, or redevelopment of existing pharmaceuticals, aiming to minimise their environmental impact while maintaining therapeutic efficacy (Vidaurre et al., 2024). While the interest in green pharmacy is growing, and criteria for the development of green drugs

have been proposed (Moermond et al., 2022), the actual development of such green pharmaceuticals has not yet taken off. While some early signals for greener antibiotics seem to be promising (Andrä et al., 2018; Leder et al., 2021), there are still many concerns about the trade-offs of (re)designing green pharmaceuticals, such as cost-effectiveness, energy/resource efficiencies, and other negative impacts on the environment (e.g. extraction of minerals, Moermond et al., 2025). This may prove particularly challenging for psychopharmaceuticals, as properties such as persistency and potency (ecotoxicity) are by design for their application (e.g. SSRIs). Due to the similarity of human and environmental metabolism, design criteria for chronic use, active transport, and stable plasma concentration may contradict design criteria for a reduced environmental hazard. Therefore, due to the added complexity that psychopharmaceuticals specifically bring to green pharmacy, it may be necessary to reconsider how and what is prescribed instead.

Reducing Pressure on the Environment with Prescription Changes: The “Kloka Listan” Example

Aside from the two levers of wastewater treatment and drug design that we can collectively pull as a society to reduce (psycho)pharmaceutical risk, there is a third lever that concerns the medical field, which is especially applicable to psychopharmaceuticals. Changes in the psychiatric therapeutic approach, such as changes in prescription amount, length, or use of non-pharmacological therapies can lead to fewer emissions of psychopharmaceuticals (Parker and Miller, 2024). However, this is controversial, as there is an anxiety that this can lead to a decline in therapeutic efficacy (Sindhu et al., 2024). Yet, there has been an attempt to combine therapeutic efficacy with environmental risks in mind.

In 2001, Sweden developed the *Kloka Listan* (Wise List), which is an evidence-based drug formulary which recommends the most effective, safe, and cost-efficient medications, including non-pharmacological advice for common conditions (The Stockholm Drug and Therapeutics Committee, 2025). Importantly, in 2010 environmental risk assessments were included in the drug recommendations, which prioritise pharmaceuticals with lower environmental impact when multiple pharmacological therapeutic alternatives

are available, while still having the patients' health as the main priority (Figure 29, Eriksen et al., 2017; The Stockholm Drug and Therapeutics Committee, 2025). High adherence to the *Kloka Listan* has led to significant changes in prescription behaviour of psychopharmaceuticals in Sweden (Eriksen et al., 2017). These changes in prescription are supposed to lead to changes in the occurrence of these pharmaceuticals in the environment, but this has not been studied yet in Sweden after the implementation of the environmental risk assessments. Once scientific evidence on the effects of this intervention would be available, it could be the case that the *Kloka Listan* represents a model for other countries to reduce (psycho)pharmaceutical risks through relatively small changes in prescription regimes.

Depression

Healthy lifestyle habits

- Behavioral activation and physical activity have a positive effect on depression.

Remember to screen for risky use of alcohol and other substances as well as previous hypomanic or manic episodes.

CBT is an effective treatment and can be offered alone or combined with medication.

The goal of treatment is for the patient to recover from their depression. The effect of treatment should be evaluated using a validated symptom rating scale.

If treatment is ineffective, compliance needs to be evaluated and the diagnosis sometimes reconsidered.

[Depression in the elderly](#)

Depression in adults ;sure.nu [↗](#)

Depression ;knowledgesupportforwardgiver.se [↗](#)

National guidelines for care for depression and anxiety disorders ;socialstyrelsen.se [↗](#)

In the first place

+ escitalopram	↔	Escitalopram ..., Cipralex
+ sertraline	↔	Sertraline ..., Oralin, Sertrone, Zoloft

In the second place

+ duloxetine	↔	Duloxetine..., Aritavi, Cymbalta
+ mirtazapine	↔	Mirtazapine ..., Mirtin

Mirtazapine can be given as adjunctive or monotherapy.

Figure 29: Screenshot of the machine translated 'Kloka Listan' advice for prescribing antidepressants (<https://klokalistan.se/terapiomrade/psykiatri.html>)

Two preliminary studies on the feasibility of implementing the *Kloka Listan* approach in The Netherlands indicated that the risks of SSRIs and benzodiazepines could indeed be reduced by simply changing which individual pharmaceutical was prescribed due to differences in ecotoxicity between the pharmaceuticals. The feasibility of different scenarios was also discussed with psychiatrists during the benzodiazepine study, which were then modelled to estimate the future phase out of the riskiest benzodiazepines. In Figure 30, three scenarios are shown where there is no change in prescription behaviour (blue), the most hazardous benzodiazepine is phased out (red), and the two most hazardous benzodiazepines are phased out (green). The shaded areas represent the range of risk quotients, which shows that the risk of benzodiazepines drop from 2 to below 1 in 6 years for the final scenario.

Figure 30: RQ models for the phasing out of two benzodiazepines for 2017-2032. Taken from the Master's thesis of Evelina Gorjatšova.

Since these preliminary studies were performed, recent literature has also demonstrated that prescription behaviour can be altered in The Netherlands simply through educational letters, similar to *Kloka Listan* (Luykx et al., 2025). Changing psychopharmaceutical prescription could be the quickest way of reducing the associated risks while maintaining therapeutic efficacy, but this requires the positive involvement of all stakeholders (Eriksen et al., 2017; Moermond et al., 2025; Parker and Miller, 2024; Sindhu et al., 2024). Furthermore, there are metrics other than aquatic risk and therapeutic efficacy that would need to be accounted for in such a system. Environmental impact from production, such as material and energy use, and supply chains would need to be properly assessed to qualify if a change in prescription is

better for the environment as a whole (Van Wilder et al., 2024). Yet, the *Kolka Listan* approach could be the simplest first step for many other authorities to take in order to reduce the environmental risks associated with psychopharmaceutical prescription.

Conclusions and Final Outlook

Psychopharmaceutical pollution carries risks for the aquatic environment, which ultimately derive from inefficient removal from WWTPs. By utilising current analytical techniques, the current thesis published extensive data on the occurrence, as well as on the risk, removal, and remediation of psychopharmaceuticals in the aquatic environment. Six treatment techniques were investigated using risk-based removal as the metric for successful removal, including traditional WWTP setups, advanced treatments and nature-based solutions. While the current treatment techniques and nature-based solutions investigated were insufficient, advanced treatments such as ozone and GAC showed promise in reducing psychopharmaceutical risk for the environment.

Changing the design of psychopharmaceuticals to facilitate breakdown in the environment could pave the way for new pharmaceuticals that cause less risk for the environment. Changing the way we prescribe psychopharmaceuticals may also reduce pressure on the environment and WWTPs. Upgrading WWTPs with advanced treatments may be able to negate the risk at the end of the pipe. There are therefore many different, and often complimentary options to reduce the risk of psychopharmaceuticals, which all have advantages and disadvantages. It is therefore evident that a holistic and integrated approach is needed with inputs of all stakeholders. Recent movements in the field have been promising, such as integrating the healthcare sector as a primary stakeholder. Still, further research is required to address the remaining data gaps, and to prioritise where the limited resources can maximise their impact. It is concluded that long term strategies to mitigate the environmental risk of psychopharmaceuticals should address the immediate challenges, but also should set the stage for sustainable practices that protect both human health and the integrity of our ecosystem.

Summary

Psychopharmaceuticals are a vital part of the modern medicinal arsenal, characterised by their interactions with neural and nervous systems. Due to the evolutionarily conserved architecture of these systems, psychopharmaceuticals designed to aid humans may elicit effects on non-target aquatic organisms, threatening aquatic ecosystem health. With the increasing presence of psychopharmaceuticals in surface waters, resulting from human use and subsequent insufficient removal by Wastewater Treatment Plants (WWTPs), this threat becomes increasingly prominent.

Prior to the beginning of this project, a comprehensive risk assessment of the presence of psychopharmaceuticals had not been performed. Moreover, many psychopharmaceuticals are not included in WWTP monitoring lists, so the removal efficiencies for both conventional and advanced treatments may also remain unknown. These missing data are further compounded by a lack of standardised testing of the micropollutant removal efficiencies of advanced treatments, making comparisons between different treatments challenging. Removal studies tend to offer removal rates without discussion or assessment of the effects on the environment and implicitly assume a high removal rate equals a low environmental risk. Since this may not be the case, the present thesis advocated for a more substantial measure of removal success by including ecotoxicity into the removal equation, defined as risk-based removal.

Given the identified data gaps, the present thesis aimed to assess the risk, removal, and remediation of psychopharmaceuticals in the aquatic environment. This aim translated into the following objectives:

1. To identify psychopharmaceuticals that represent a high risk for the aquatic environment
2. To define for which psychopharmaceuticals missing occurrence and ecotoxicity data hamper environmental risk assessment

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3. To determine occurrence, mass-based, and risk-based removal of psychopharmaceuticals in a modern conventional WWTP
 4. To determine occurrence, mass-based and risk-based removal of psychopharmaceuticals by common advanced treatment techniques
 5. To assess the effectiveness of an alternative nature-based treatment technique for risk-based removal of psychopharmaceuticals

Chapter 2 provides a review of the current literature on the environmental occurrence and ecotoxicity of psychopharmaceuticals and combined these data to perform a risk assessment. First, the availability and quality of data on the concentrations of psychopharmaceuticals and illicit drugs in European surface waters (occurrence) and on the ecotoxicity to aquatic organisms (hazard) were reviewed. If both occurrence and ecotoxicity data were available, risk quotients (risk) were calculated. Where abundant ecotoxicity data were available, a species sensitivity distribution (SSD) was constructed, from which the hazardous concentration for 5% of the species (HC₅) was derived, allowing to derive integrated multi-species risks. A total of 702 compounds were categorised as psychopharmaceuticals and illicit drugs based on a combination of all 502 anatomical therapeutic class (ATC) 'N' drugs and a list of illicit drugs according to the Dutch Opium Act. Of these, 343 (49%) returned occurrence data, while only 105 (15%) returned ecotoxicity data. Moreover, many ecotoxicity tests used irrelevant endpoints for neurologically active compounds, such as mortality, which may underestimate the hazard of psychopharmaceuticals in the aquatic environment. Due to data limitations, risks could only be assessed for 87 (12%) compounds, with 23 (3.3%) compounds indicating a potential risk. Primary bottlenecks in risk calculation included the lack of ecotoxicity data, a lack of diversity of test species and ecotoxicological endpoints, and large disparities between well studied and understudied compounds for both occurrence and toxicity data. Moreover, for several highly prescribed drugs neither occurrence nor ecotoxicity data were available at all. This chapter identified which compounds merit concern, as well as the many compounds that lack the data for any calculation of risk, driving research priorities, therewith aiding compound prioritisation for the subsequent experimental chapters of this

thesis. Despite the large knowledge gaps, this chapter concluded that the presence of a substantial part (26%) of data-rich psychopharmaceuticals in surface waters present an ecological risk for aquatic non-target organisms.

While Chapter 2 gave a broad perspective on the current risks across the European aquatic environment, Chapter 3 focused on a single specific WWTP, Amsterdam West, which is one of the largest WWTPs in The Netherlands, serving around 800,000 population equivalents, but has not undergone advanced treatment upgrades yet. In this chapter, risk-based removal was first used to add context to the removal of psychopharmaceuticals by the WWTP. Here, 30 highly used psychopharmaceuticals were studied during one week in the wastewater of the Amsterdam West WWTP using solid phase extraction and Ultra High-Performance Liquid Chromatography–Quadrupole Time of Flight–High Resolution Mass Spectrometry (UHPLC-qTOF-HRMS). 20 target compounds were detected in the influent (17 ng – 99 µg/L) and 16 in the effluent (34 ng/L – 17 µg/L). Removal efficiencies during treatment ranged from 24% to >99%. Paracetamol, amphetamine, fluoxetine, levetiracetam, phenacetin, and sertraline demonstrated almost complete removal, while tramadol, lidocaine, lamotrigine, fluvoxamine and carbamazepine reported removals below 50%, with lidocaine demonstrating the lowest removal (24%). Utilising available ecotoxicity data, a preliminary risk assessment was performed to contextualise the calculated removal efficiencies by calculating risk-based removal. This revealed that sertraline and ibuprofen still demonstrated a potential risk, despite high removal efficiencies, which proved the added value of risk-based removal, albeit with a worrying outcome. Hence, Chapter 3 highlighted that wastewater contains abundant numbers and ecotoxicologically relevant concentrations of psychopharmaceuticals that are insufficiently removed by the WWTP. The implementation of risk-based removal targets in legislation is discussed, in order to facilitate the reduction in emissions of psychopharmaceuticals, for example by adequate WWTP upgrades with advanced treatments to ensure a toxic free environment.

Building on Chapter 3 that provided the removal and risk-based removal of a modern WWTP, Chapter 4 aimed to explore the removal and risk-based removal efficiencies of two

common advanced treatment technologies. Specifically, it investigated the removal efficiency of psychopharmaceuticals by ozonation and granular active carbon (GAC) in wastewater effluent, using risk as the metric for adequate removal instead of aqueous concentrations. Conventionally treated effluent was subsequently treated with ozone or GAC until there was a 25% reduction in UVA₂₅₄ absorbance, to allow for a direct comparison of the two treatment types. Samples were analysed using a newly developed UHPLC-qTOF-HRMS protocol, allowing to quantify 20 mostly psychotropic pharmaceuticals, and risk-based removal was calculated using Predicted No Effect Concentrations (PNECs). To compare the relative toxicity of new chemical species being formed by the ozone treatment, a further risk assessment was performed using Quantitative Structural Activity Relationships (QSARs) for both parent compounds and their Oxidation Transformation Products (OTPs). The concentration-based median removal efficiency across all compounds was 63% for ozone, which also yielded a 63% risk-based removal of the parent compounds. The median concentration-based removal efficiency for GAC was 54% and 60% for risk-based removal. In contrast, when incorporating the newly formed OTPs into these risk calculations, the median risk reduction for ozone became negative (-39%), indicating that there may be a dramatic increase in risk during ozonation. This chapter again demonstrated the merits of the risk-driven approach over concentration-based removal targets as laid down in current legislation, but also highlighted major knowledge gaps, especially concerning the limited availability of ecotoxicity data. It is concluded that for (psycho)pharmaceuticals, OTP toxicity may negate the reduction in risk from ozone treatment, and that tandem oxidation-adsorption setups may alleviate concerns over OTP toxicity.

Advanced treatment technologies such as ozone and GAC are not the only options for polishing WWTP effluent, since in recent decades Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) have gained interest as potential low cost, low carbon emitting alternatives. Therefore, Chapter 5, the final experimental chapter of this thesis, aimed to explore the effectiveness of an alternative nature-based tertiary treatment of WWTP effluent to remove psychopharmaceuticals. To this end, an algae-mussel trophic cascade setup was designed in which algae

were grown in effluent over the course of 11 days and subsequently fed to mussels for a further 3 days.

Removal of 30 psychopharmaceuticals for each of the treatments (algae, mussels, algae + mussels) was calculated relative to control samples, and removal efficiency was contextualised by performing an indicative risk assessment, again expressed as risk-based removal. 12 psychopharmaceuticals were quantified during the experiment, with 11 encountered in all treatments. The compounds fell into 3 categories: positive removal (citalopram, lamotrigine, and venlafaxine), negative removal (carbamazepine, gabapentin, and pregabalin), and no significant changes in concentration (amitriptyline, quetiapine, tramadol, fluvoxamine, lidocaine, and ibuprofen). Both positive and negative removal was largely driven by the presence of the algae rather than that of the mussels. Compounds with a low pK_a showed negative removal due to the algal growth induced rise in pH, which was not negated by the mussels at the end of the cascade. Ibuprofen was not removed by any treatment and was also the only compound that represented a substantial risk. The cumulative risks indicated that the algal-mussel cascade actually increased the risk due to the negative removal of compounds present in high concentrations such as carbamazepine. The risk of pregabalin and gabapentin also increased, but did, however, not significantly change the overall risk from the analysed compounds due to their low concentrations. Since the presently designed nature-based treatment could not negate risk, it was considered unsuitable for the removal of psychopharmaceuticals.

The present thesis aimed to assess the risk, removal, and remediation of psychopharmaceuticals in the aquatic environment. It was argued that these three facets should be addressed together in a more holistic, integrated approach than what is typically done when assessing micropollutant risks in the environment. To this end, risk to the aquatic environment was assessed in tandem with occurrence and removal, which allowed removal to be discussed in the context of risk reduction, or risk-based removal.

Psychopharmaceutical pollution carries risks to the aquatic environment, which ultimately derive from inefficient removal from WWTPs. By utilising current analytical

techniques, the current thesis published extensive data on the occurrence, as well as on the risk, removal, and remediation of psychopharmaceuticals in the aquatic environment. Six treatment techniques were investigated using risk-based removal as the metric for successful removal, including traditional WWTP setups, advanced treatments and nature-based solutions. While the current treatment techniques and nature-based solutions investigated were insufficient, advanced treatments like ozone and GAC showed promise in reducing psychopharmaceutical risk in the environment.

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Recent developments in the field have been promising, such as integrating the healthcare sector as a primary stakeholder. Still, further research is required to address the remaining data gaps, and to prioritise where the limited resources can maximise their impact. It is concluded that long term strategies to mitigate the environmental risk of psychopharmaceuticals should address the immediate challenges, but also should set the stage for sustainable practices that protect both human health and the integrity of our ecosystems.

Samenvatting

Psychofarmaca, die worden gekenmerkt door hun interacties met het menselijk zenuwstelsel, vormen een essentieel onderdeel van de moderne geneeskunde. Vanwege de evolutionair geconserveerde structuur van het zenuwstelsel kunnen psychofarmaca die ontworpen zijn voor mensen echter ook effecten hebben op in het water levende organismen, wat de gezondheid van aquatische ecosystemen kan bedreigen. Door de toenemende aanwezigheid van psychofarmaca in het oppervlaktewater als gevolg van menselijk gebruik en onvolledige zuivering door rioolwaterzuiveringsinstallaties (RWZI's) wordt deze bedreiging steeds groter.

Voor de start van dit project was er nog geen uitgebreide risicobeoordeling van psychofarmaca in het milieu uitgevoerd. Bovendien was de verwijderingsefficiëntie van psychofarmaca van zowel conventionele als geavanceerde rioolwaterbehandelingen veelal onbekend, omdat ze meestal niet routinematig worden gemonitord in RWZI's. Daarnaast maakt het gebrek aan gestandaardiseerde testen om de verwijderingsefficiëntie van geavanceerde behandelingen van microverontreinigingen te bepalen het moeilijk om de verschillende behandelingen onderling te vergelijken. De uitgevoerde onderzoeken geven vaak verwijderingspercentages zonder de effecten op het milieu daar in te betrekken, en gaan er impliciet van uit dat een hoog verwijderingspercentage ook een laag milieurisico betekent. Dit is echter lang niet altijd het geval. Daarom pleit dit proefschrift ervoor om gebruikmakend van ecotoxiciteitgegevens een meer milieurelevante maat voor het verwijderingsrendement te berekenen, gedefinieerd als risicogebaseerde verwijdering.

Gezien het gebrek aan kennis over de gevolgen van de aanwezigheid van psychofarmaca in het oppervlaktewater, was het doel van dit proefschrift om het risico, de verwijdering en de zuivering van psychofarmaca in het aquatisch milieu te beoordelen. Om dit te bereiken zijn de volgende doelstellingen geformuleerd:

1. Het identificeren van psychofarmaca die een hoog risico vormen voor het aquatisch milieu

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2. Achterhalen voor welke psychofarmaca ontbrekende gegevens over blootstelling en ecotoxiciteit de risicobeoordeling bemoeilijken
 3. Het bepalen van de aanwezigheid en de verwijdering van psychofarmaca in een moderne conventionele RWZI en de daaruit voortvloeiende afname van het risico
 4. Het bepalen van de aanwezigheid en de verwijdering van psychofarmaca door middel van gangbare geavanceerde behandelingstechnieken en de daaruit voortvloeiende afname van het risico
 5. Beoordelen van de effectiviteit van een alternatieve, op natuurlijke processen gebaseerde behandelingstechniek voor de verwijdering van psychofarmaca op basis van risicoreductie

Hoofdstuk 2 geeft een overzicht van de huidige literatuur over de blootstelling in het milieu en de ecotoxiciteit van psychofarmaca en combineert deze gegevens voor het uitvoeren van een risicobeoordeling. Eerst zijn de beschikbaarheid en kwaliteit van meetgegevens van psychofarmaca en illegale drugs in Europese oppervlaktewateren (blootstelling) en hun ecotoxiciteit voor waterorganismen (gevaar) beoordeeld. Als zowel gegevens over blootstelling als over ecotoxiciteit beschikbaar waren, werden risicoquotienten (risico) berekend. Wanneer er genoeg gegevens over ecotoxiciteit beschikbaar waren, werd een *Species Sensitivity Distribution* (soortgevoeligheidsverdeling; SSD) opgesteld. Daaruit werd de concentratie berekend waarbij 5% van het aantal soorten potentieel negatief beïnvloedt wordt (HC₅), waardoor de geïntegreerde risico's van de psychofarmaca op levensgemeenschappen konden worden ingeschat. Op basis van een combinatie van alle 502 geneesmiddelen in ATC-klasse 'N' (zenuwstelsel) en een lijst van illegale drugs volgens de Nederlandse Opiumwet werden 702 verbindingen gecategoriseerd als psychofarmaca en illegale drugs. Van 343 (49%) verbindingen werden meetgegevens gevonden over hun voorkomen in oppervlaktewater. Van slechts 105 (15%) werden gegevens over de ecotoxiciteit gevonden. Bovendien werden in veel ecotoxiciteitstesten niet-relevante eindpunten voor dit soort neurologisch actieve verbindingen gevonden, zoals mortaliteit, waardoor het gevaar van psychofarmaca in het aquatisch milieu mogelijk wordt onderschat. Vanwege de beperkte

hoeveelheid gegevens konden voor slechts 87 (12%) verbindingen de mogelijke risico's worden berekend, waaruit bleek dat 23 (3,3%) verbindingen een potentieel risico vormen. De belangrijkste knelpunten bij de risicoberekening waren het gebrek aan ecotoxiciteitsgegevens, een gebrek aan diversiteit van testsoorten en ecotoxicologische eindpunten, en grote verschillen tussen goed bestudeerde en weinig bestudeerde verbindingen, zowel wat betreft meetgegevens als toxiciteitsgegevens. Bovendien waren voor verschillende veel voorgeschreven geneesmiddelen helemaal geen gegevens over blootstelling of ecotoxiciteit beschikbaar. In hoofdstuk 2 werd dus vastgesteld welke verbindingen risicovol zijn, en voor welke verbindingen de gegevens ontbreken om het risico te kunnen berekenen. Op basis hiervan werden onderzoeksprioriteiten bepaald en verbindingen geprioriteerd voor de volgende experimentele hoofdstukken van dit proefschrift. Ondanks de grote kennislacunes concludeert dit hoofdstuk dat een aanzienlijk deel (26%) van de psychofarmaca waarvoor wel gegevens beschikbaar zijn een ecologisch risico vormt voor het oppervlaktewater.

Terwijl hoofdstuk 2 de huidige risico's van de aanwezigheid van psychofarmaca in het Europese aquatische milieu vaststelde, richtte hoofdstuk 3 zich op één specifieke RWZI, namelijk Amsterdam West. Dit is een van de grootste RWZI's in Nederland, met een capaciteit van ruim 800.000 inwonerequivalenten, maar is nog niet uitgerust met geavanceerde zuiveringstechnieken. In dit hoofdstuk werd de risicogebaseerde verwijdering van psychofarmaca door de RWZI bepaald. Hiertoe zijn 30 veelgebruikte psychofarmaca in het rioolwater gedurende één week geanalyseerd met behulp van vaste-fase-extractie en *Ultra High-Performance Liquid Chromatography–Quadrupole Time of Flight–High Resolution Mass Spectrometry* (UHPLC-qTOF-HRMS). Twintig van de 30 doelstoffen werden gedetecteerd in het influent (17 ng – 99 µg/L) en 16 in het effluent (34 ng/L – 17 µg/L). De verwijderingsefficiënties varieerden van 24% tot >99%. Paracetamol, amfetamine, fluoxetine, levetiracetam, fenacetine en sertraline werden bijna volledig verwijderd, terwijl tramadol, lidocaïne, lamotrigine, fluvoxamine en carbamazepine voor minder dan 50% werden verwijderd, waarbij lidocaïne de laagste verwijdering vertoonde (24%). Op basis van beschikbare ecotoxiciteitsgegevens werd een voorlopige risicobeoordeling uitgevoerd om de berekende

verwijderingsefficiënties in context te plaatsen, uitgedrukt als risicogebaseerde verwijdering. Hieruit bleek dat sertraline en ibuprofen ondanks de hoge verwijderingspercentages nog steeds een potentieel risico vormden. Dit toont de toegevoegde waarde van risicogebaseerde verwijdering aan, en laat bovendien zien dat de zuivering niet alle risico's voor het aquatische ecosysteem verwijdert. Het rioolwater bevat ecotoxicologisch relevante concentraties psychofarmaca die onvoldoende worden verwijderd door de RWZI. Ten slotte wordt de implementatie van op risicogebaseerde verwijderingsdoelstellingen in de wetgeving besproken.

Deze doelstelling kan worden gebruikt om de noodzakelijke vermindering van de lozing van psychofarmaca met behulp van aanvullende zuiveringsstappen in RWZI's te bepalen, om gifvrij oppervlaktewater te bereiken.

Voortbouwend op hoofdstuk 3, waarin de verwijdering en risicogebaseerde verwijdering van psychofarmaca door een moderne conventionele RWZI werd behandeld, richtte hoofdstuk 4 zich op de verwijderingsefficiëntie en risicogebaseerde verwijderingsefficiëntie van twee veelgebruikte geavanceerde behandelingstechnieken. In dit hoofdstuk werd daarom de verwijderingsefficiëntie van psychofarmaca door ozonisatie en granulaire actieve kool (GAC) in effluent onderzocht. Daarbij werd net als in hoofdstuk 3 in plaats van de concentraties in het water, het overblijvende risico als maat voor verwijdering gebruikt. Conventioneel behandeld effluent werd nabehandeld met ozon of GAC totdat de UV absorptie bij een golflengte van 254 nm met 25% afgenomen was. Op deze wijze kon de verwijdering van psychofarmaca door de twee zuiveringstechnieken direct worden vergeleken. De monsters werden geanalyseerd met een nieuw UHPLC-qTOF-HRMS-protocol, waarmee 20 (voornamelijk psychotrope) geneesmiddelen gekwantificeerd werden. De risicogebaseerde verwijdering werd berekend met behulp van concentraties waarvan voorspeld was dat ze geen nadelige effecten zouden veroorzaken (PNEC's). Om de relatieve toxiciteit van transformatieproducten die door de ozonbehandeling worden gevormd te vergelijken met die van de ouderstoffen, werd een risicobeoordeling uitgevoerd met behulp van *Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationships* (QSAR's) voor zowel de oorspronkelijke verbindingen als hun oxidatietransformatieproducten (OTP's). De mediane verwijderingsefficiëntie op basis van concentratie voor alle

verbindingen was 63% voor ozon, wat ook resulteerde in een op risico gebaseerde verwijdering van 63% van de moederverbindingen. De op concentratie gebaseerde mediane verwijderingsefficiëntie voor GAC was 54% en 60% voor de op risico gebaseerde verwijdering. Wanneer de nieuwgevormde OTP's in de risicobeoordeling werden meegenomen, werd de mediane risicoreductie voor ozon daarentegen negatief (-39%). Dit wijst erop dat het risico tijdens ozonisatie kan toenemen. Dit hoofdstuk toonde opnieuw de voordelen van de risicogebaseerde verwijderingsdoelstellingen aan ten opzichte van de op concentratie gebaseerde verwijderingsdoelstellingen zoals vereist in de huidige wetgeving. Maar het bracht ook belangrijke kennislacunes aan het licht, met name wat betreft de beperkte beschikbaarheid van ecotoxiciteitsgegevens om het risico te kunnen bepalen. Op basis van deze resultaten werd geconcludeerd dat voor (psycho)farmaceutica de toxiciteit van OTP's de risicoreductie door ozonbehandeling teniet kan doen, en dat een combinatie van oxidatieve en adsorptie technieken het risico van OTP's gevormd tijdens de oxidatieve behandeling kan verminderen.

Geavanceerde behandelingstechnologieën zoals ozon en GAC zijn niet de enige opties voor het zuiveren van rioolwater. Op natuurlijke processen gebaseerde oplossingen (*Nature-Based Solutions*, NBS) worden de afgelopen decennia steeds vaker toegepast als potentiële goedkope alternatieven met een lage CO₂-uitstoot. Daarom richtte hoofdstuk 5, het laatste experimentele hoofdstuk van dit proefschrift, zich op de effectiviteit van een alternatieve, op natuurlijke processen gebaseerde nabehandeling om psychofarmaca te verwijderen uit rioolwatereffluent van zuiveringsinstallaties. Hiertoe werd een opstelling met algen en mosselen ontworpen, waarbij de algen gedurende 11 dagen in rioolwatereffluent werden gekweekt en vervolgens gedurende 3 dagen als voeding voor de mosselen dienden. De verwijdering van 30 psychofarmaca werd getoetst in een opstelling met enkel algen, enkel mosselen en opeenvolgende behandelingen met eerst algen en daarna mosselen, waarvan de resultaten werden vergeleken met die van de controlemonsters. De verwijderingsefficiëntie werd vervolgens wederom in context geplaatst door een indicatieve risicobeoordeling uit te voeren, en de risicogebaseerde verwijdering te berekenen. Tijdens het experiment werden 12 psychofarmaca gekwantificeerd, waarvan er 11 in alle behandelingen voorkwamen. De

verbindingen werden onderverdeeld in 3 categorieën: positieve verwijdering (citalopram, lamotrigine en venlafaxine), negatieve verwijdering (carbamazepine, gabapentine en pregabaline) en geen significante verwijdering (amitriptyline, quetiapine, tramadol, fluvoxamine, lidocaïne en ibuprofen). Zowel positieve als negatieve verwijdering werd grotendeels veroorzaakt door de aanwezigheid de algen. Verbindingen met een lage pKa vertoonden negatieve verwijdering als gevolg van de pH-stijging door algengroei, wat niet voorkomen kon worden door de aanwezigheid van de mosselen. Ibuprofen werd door geen enkele behandeling verwijderd en was de enige verbinding die een aanzienlijk risico vormde. De cumulatieve risico's van alle psychofarmaca werden door de behandeling met de algen-mosselcascade hoger door de negatieve verwijdering van carbamazepine, die een relevante bijdrage aan het cumulatieve risico leverde. Het risico van pregabaline en gabapentine nam ook toe, maar dat veranderde het totale risico van de geanalyseerde verbindingen niet significant vanwege hun lage concentraties. Aangezien deze op natuurlijke processen gebaseerde behandeling het risico niet reduceerde, werd deze in de huidige opstelling ongeschikt geacht voor de verwijdering van de bestudeerde psychofarmaca.

Het doel van dit proefschrift was het beoordelen van het risico van psychofarmaca in het aquatisch milieu en het toetsen van hun verwijdering met conventionele en aanvullende zuiveringstechnieken voor gemeenschappelijk afvalwater. Het toetsen van effluent van rioolwaterzuiveringsinstallaties en het rendement van aanvullende zuiveringstechnieken op een risicogebaseerde wijze leidde tot een meer holistische, geïntegreerde benadering dan wat gebruikelijk is bij de beoordeling van risico's van microverontreinigingen in het milieu. Door de verwijdering te evalueren vanuit het perspectief van risicobeperking kan het aquatisch milieu beter worden beschermd.

Verontreiniging door psychofarmaca brengt risico's met zich mee voor het aquatisch milieu, die voortkomen uit niet volledige zuivering door RWZI's. Met behulp van geavanceerde analytische technieken publiceerde dit proefschrift uitgebreide gegevens over de blootstelling, het risico en de verwijdering en de zuivering van psychofarmaca

in het aquatisch milieu. Zes behandelingstechnieken werden onderzocht met risicogebaseerde verwijdering als maat voor het verwijderingsrendement. Dit betrof een traditionele RWZI-opstellingen en diverse geavanceerde en op de natuur gebaseerde zuiveringstechnieken. Conventionele technieken en op natuurlijke processen gebaseerde technieken bleken ontoereikend, maar geavanceerde behandelingen met ozon en GAC bleken veelbelovend voor het verminderen van het milieurisico van psychofarmaca.

Het aanpassen van het ontwerp van psychofarmaca om afbraak in het milieu te bevorderen, zou kunnen leiden tot een vermindering van risico's voor het aquatische milieu. Een andere manier van voorschrijven kan ook de druk op het milieu en de RWZI's verminderen. Het moderniseren van RWZI's met geavanceerde behandelingen kan het risico voor het milieu eveneens verminderen. Er zijn dus veel verschillende en vaak complementaire opties om het milieurisico van psychofarmaca te verminderen. Deze maatregelen hebben allemaal voor- en nadelen. Een holistische en geïntegreerde aanpak, waarbij alle belanghebbenden worden betrokken, is daarom noodzakelijk.

Recente ontwikkelingen op dit gebied zijn veelbelovend, zoals het betrekken van de gezondheidszorg als primaire belanghebbende. Toch is verder onderzoek nodig om de resterende kennislacunes op te vullen en te bepalen waar en welke maatregelen het meest effect hebben. Geconcludeerd wordt dat de risico's van psychofarmaca onmiddellijk moeten worden aangepakt, en dat daarnaast langetermijnstrategieën nodig zijn om het milieurisico op een duurzame manier op te lossen om zowel de menselijke gezondheid als onze ecosystemen te beschermen.

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Chapter 2: Occurrence, Hazard, and Risk of Psychopharmaceuticals and Illicit Drugs in European Surface Waters

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Chapter 5: Removal of Psychopharmaceuticals from WWTP Effluent by an Algae-Mussel Trophic Cascade: A Potential Nature-Based Solution?

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Author Profile

Charlie James Edward Davey was born in Hemel Hempstead (United Kingdom) on the 29th of September 1993 and was raised in the neighbouring city of Saint Albans. Charlie attended Windermere primary school, followed by Beaumont secondary school in his early years. While at school, he took an interest in science, particularly Chemistry and Physics, but also developed an interest in Environmentalism and Sustainability. Charlie stayed on at Beaumont for 6th form, where he studied Chemistry, Physics, and IT for his A-levels, which earned him the grades to be accepted into the Bachelors' programme for Chemistry at the University of Leicester (UK) in 2013.

During his studies in Leicester, Charlie was introduced to the topics of Environmental Chemistry and Ecotoxicology through an optional elective course. These subjects resonated much more with Charlie due to the course's unique combination of application, theory, and public welfare. For Charlie, this contrasted against the often industrial-focused subjects aimed to prepare students for industry over academia. Unsurprisingly, it was also during his Bachelors' that Charlie became more politically engaged, where Charlie joined and volunteered for the UK Green Party, where he became more familiar with matters of environmental policy.

After the 2016 Brexit referendum, Charlie "rage quit" the UK to travel south Asia for 6 months, where he decided to move to the European mainland to follow a Masters degree. In 2017, Charlie moved to Amsterdam to follow a course in Chemistry, Energy, and Sustainability at the University of Amsterdam, where he was able to cater his studies towards his interests of Environmental Chemistry, Ecotoxicology, Sustainability, and applied subjects such as energy, policy, and epidemiology.

In the final year of his Masters, Charlie did an internship with Avantium on the topic of biodegradable plastics in the environment, where he was invited to co-author two papers. Seeing that the academic world was not as intimidating as he once thought, he decided to start applying for PhDs in early 2020, finding a position back at the University of Amsterdam on the Psychopharmac'eu project, where he worked on the topic of Psychopharmaceuticals in the environment, specifically focussing on occurrence, risk, and mitigation strategies until late 2024. After he finished his PhD, he started working as a postdoctoral researcher at Radboud University in Nijmegen on the PREMIER and Transpharm projects, performing fate, hazard, and risk modelling of pharmaceuticals, where he continues to work at the date of publication.

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